

**Exploring Gender Inequality Regimes: A Study of
Women in Management in Scottish Call Centres**

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Declaration

This thesis is the result of my own investigations and has not been accepted nor concurrently submitted in candidature for any other degree.

Signed: Safia Khalid

Date: December 2024

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Abstract

Call centres are a significant and essential component of modern organisational structures. Despite the extensive research conducted on call centres more generally, the scholarly examination of gender-related issues within the call centre context has been relatively limited (Matos, 2018). However, the initial promising research in this area has not been meaningfully built upon or expanded in the extant literature (Belt, Richardson and Webster, 2002, 2010). The aim of this research is to explore the ways in which gender inequality regimes influence the context of women in management in call centres in order to better inform organisational policies and practices on diversity and equality both in call centres and in the wider context.

This research uses Acker's (2006b, 2009, 2012) inequality regime framework as an overarching framework to analyse the processes and practices that create inequality regimes. Acker's theoretical framework is enhanced by the addition of two elements from Connell's (2002) gender regime, which recognises the importance of the pay gap and occupational segregation. It is further refined by the inclusion of two further factors from McDonald's (2015) gender inequality regime, namely marital status and motherhood. Using a combined framework makes an important contribution to knowledge by providing a detailed understanding of women in senior management positions, an area that has been significantly under-researched.

The research adopted a qualitative, interpretive approach. Between December 2019 and February 2021, seventeen interviews were conducted, fifteen of

which involved women managers and two with key informants in the Scottish call centre sector, including one male participant. The data was analysed using a thematic analysis approach to explore women's experiences. Braun and Clarke's framework was also applied to the interview data, which was supported by NVivo, a common tool for qualitative data analysis.

The findings revealed that women face barriers in reaching the top levels, especially in relation to domestic and childcare responsibilities that stifled career progression hence, the existence of gender inequality regimes in call centres in Scotland is evident. The findings also suggested that there is a need, firstly, for robust government statistics and research on call centres and, secondly, for organisational cultures that involve flexible working arrangements for women managers and include women in training and development activities. While the study was limited to a single social domain and geographic region, with a research sample of 17 interviews, the findings still provide valuable insights. The call centres included in the sample were located solely within the Scottish region due to the COVID-19 pandemic lockdown restrictions. The study's findings have important implications for policy and practice, underscoring the need for a comprehensive approach to promoting gender equality in the call centre industry, not only in Scotland but also more broadly.

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Chapter 1 - Introduction

1.1 Introduction

This chapter provides the background for the research study by first explaining the research rationale within the context of Scotland's contact centre industry. It then outlines the main aim and objectives, as well as the contributions to knowledge. This is followed by an introduction to the research design and methods applied in this study. Finally, the limitations of the research are specified before highlighting the structure of the thesis by providing a summary of the content of each chapter.

1.2 Research rationale and gap

This thesis explores the ways in which gender inequality regimes influence the context of women in management in call centres in order to better inform organisational policies and practices on diversity and equality both in call centres and in wider contexts. Currently, there is limited research exploring gender inequality in call centres in general, and in Scotland in particular. Furthermore, there is a lack of studies on women in management in call centres. In addition, with the increasing reliance on call centres as a channel for service delivery in both public and private sectors, the significance of the need for such a study is amplified.

Over the past four decades, the Scottish economy has been restructured and has transitioned from traditional heavy industry to increasingly service-based

occupations. Call centres are one of these service-based industries, employing millions of people worldwide (Global Contact Centre Industry, 2024). The UK call centre industry was projected to have an estimated market size of approximately £6.5 billion in 2023, with forecasts indicating it could reach £8.1 billion by 2027. This anticipated growth is largely driven by the increasing popularity of call centre industry outsourcing to third-party providers (Reportlinker, 2024).

There are many call centres in Scotland that create jobs for its people (Taylor and Anderson, 2012). Call centres are perceived as a relatively new industry (Scholarios and Taylor, 2010), with a majority (61.82%) of female employees (Office of National Statistics, 2023a). However, as stated, there is very little research on women in management in call centres, and this gap in the literature will be addressed by this thesis. In the United Kingdom (UK), women make up 48.4% of those in employment (Office of National Statistics, 2024), but only 36.93% of those in management (Office of National Statistics, 2023a). As women climb the managerial career ladder, their numbers diminish, and they hold only 16.8% of Executive Directorships in FTSE100 (Vinnicombe and Tessaro, 2022).

Women managers working full-time experience a gender pay gap of 10.1% (Office of National Statistics, 2023b), while for all women working full-time, the pay gap is 7.7% (Office of National Statistics, 2023b). In Scotland, women constitute 50.7% of those in employment (Office of National Statistics, 2024), more than in the UK as a whole. However, they make up only 37.29% of those

in management, albeit slightly higher than in the UK as a whole (Office of National Statistics, 2023b). There is also a pay gap for women managers working full-time in Scotland. Additionally, 74% of part-time workers in Scotland are women, with this pattern being more common among women with dependent children, compared to only 6% among men (Brett and Macfarlane, 2022). In order to explore this under-representation of women in management, the research examined key concepts of Acker's (2006 p.443) "inequality regime". Connell's (2006, p.839) "gender regime" and the "gender inequality regime" (McDonald, 2015, p.42) and the roles and experiences of women managers within call centres.

Acker (2006, p.443) argues that this gender inequality can be explained by the concept of the "inequality regime", which, she contends, exists in all organisations. Acker (2006, p.443) defines inequality regimes as "loosely interrelated practices, processes, actions, and meanings that result in and maintain class, gender, and racial inequalities within particular organisations". These "...practices, processes, actions, and meanings..." (Acker, 2006 p.443) include, for example, occupational segregation, the pay gap, senior management's awareness of inequality, organisational culture, and human resource management policies and practices.

Connell (2002, 2006 p) posited a similar approach, termed a "gender regime". The gender regime includes occupational segregation, power relations, human relations, and culture. Connell (2002,2006) contends that these four dimensions exist in both the workplace and society. McDonald (2015 p.42)

recognises this societal dimension as an important extension of the inequality regime, particularly about caring responsibilities as well as the household division of labour and uses the title “gender inequality regime”. In addition, McDonald (2015) also incorporates marital status (now defined by the 2021 census as ‘legal marital status and cohabitation status’) and motherhood into this ‘gender inequality regime’. This research, therefore, aims to use this extended ‘gender inequality regime’ to investigate women in management in call centres.

This thesis also addresses the issue of how gender inequality regimes influence the context of women in management in Scottish call centres. As stated, advanced industrial countries have transformed economically in the past four decades. This change has resulted in a decline in manufacturing sector jobs and increased employment in the customer service sector. As a result of that change, employment in many countries is now dominated by the service sector and within this sector, call centres have emerged as a relatively new form of employment (Lloyd, 2016).

The call centre industry is one of the world's fastest-growing sectors and has emerged as a critical platform for businesses to engage with clients through information dissemination or telemarketing. The core objective of a call centre is to manage existing and prospective client inquiries, product assistance, and routine transactions (Mabotja and Mkhomazi, 2024). A call centre focuses on customer interactions and can serve as a crucial contact point for collecting customer information in a company (Sato, 2018). According to IBISWorld

(2024), over the last five years, the industry revenue has increased at a compound annual rate of 4.7%, projected to hit £3.2bn in 2024. Additionally, an increasing number of companies are leveraging technology to improve customer engagement and broaden their revenue sources, which is boosting the need for call centres. The COVID-19 pandemic heightened the demand for call centres to assist with the Test and Trace program. While revenue has decreased from the highs seen during COVID-19, it remains positive.

The workforce in call centres is predominantly female. In 2004, 67% of call centre employees were women (CfA, 2012). In 2018, the figure was 63% (ONS, 2018a). However, it is worth noting that the percentage has not remained constant during this period (ONS, 2018a). While there are some problems in obtaining data on call centre employment, these figures are generally accepted. It would, therefore, be expected that call centres would provide wider opportunities for women's advancement into management and should also provide role models for advancement (Scholarios and Taylor, 2011). However, there is little data on women in management in call centres. In a survey of 3,200 contact centres, Contact Babel (2003) found that women and men share the role of first-line managers equally in the UK. However, management in the IT sector is still dominated by men, while women predominate in HR and training. There is, therefore, a gap in the literature in terms of women in management in call centres, which this thesis will address.

Gender discrimination is one of the most persistent issues in employment, and Gans et al. (2002) point out that over the years, many studies have appeared

documenting the patterns and trends of gender bias across various jobs. Russell (2008, p. 213) highlighted there is very little research on gender in call centres and suggested that “more research is needed into the leadership role that managers of call centres can assume”. Little has been done in that regard. In fact, only a few studies conducted in Australia, China, Denmark, Israel, and the US have shed some light on leadership within a contact centre environment, in the face of a complete absence of those in Scotland or the overall UK. Besides the limited literature, there are several significant difficulties manifested in these studies (Belt, 2002; Belt, Richardson and Webster, 2002; Durbin, 2017). Not least, they are essentially descriptive accounts, often based on selective qualitative data and frequently speculative in their conclusions.

There has, though, been research on call centres internationally. However, further research on this workplace is essential for several reasons. The examination of women's managerial roles within call centres depicts a multifaceted environment marked by both prospects and substantial obstacles. Although women comprise a significant majority, estimated at around 70%, of the call centre workforce in regions such as the UK, Australia, Canada, and New Zealand, scholarly research investigating their managerial roles within this sector remains limited and underdeveloped. The limited academic research examining women's managerial positions within the call centre industry is particularly concerning, given the sector's prominence as a significant employer of women. Existing studies suggest that traditional

obstacles continue to hinder women's prospects for achieving equitable career progression in this domain (Hunt and Rasmussen, 2010).

Perhaps the most important one is that call centres have become a major source of employment, and therefore, there must be in-depth analyses of gendered employment patterns (Deery and Kinnie, 2002; Holtgrewe and Kerst, 2002; Kinnie and Parsons, 2004; Holman et al., 2007). Besides, call centres are often shown to be just another type of "women's work" therefore, it is essential to conduct research as female workers dominate these workplaces (Buchanan and Koch-Schulte, 2000; Kinnie and Parsons, 2004; Collin-Jacques and Smith, 2005a). There is a limited number of studies which have focused on the position of women in call centres.

Furthermore, there is a gap in the literature in terms of women in the management of call centres (Belt, 2002) therefore, this study will focus on women in management in call centres, from first-line management to the top of the organisation's management. As the topic of gender has not yet been investigated in contact centres in Scotland, there is a lack of knowledge regarding the gendered practices adopted by managers in their daily work.

Finally, call centres have a flat organisational structure (Buchanan and Koch-Schulte, 2000; Belt, 2002; Belt, Richardson and Webster, 2002; Kaushik, Sharma and Kaushik, 2014; Durbin, 2017). Castells (2000) argues that a flat organisational structure will affect career development and progression. Acker (2006) also argues that a flat team structure assists in providing more opportunities and equality for professional women. Therefore, it is important to

research the effect of this flat structure on women in management in call centres.

1.3 Research problem statement, aims, and objectives

1.3.1 Research Problem Statement

Do call centres have a gender inequality regime? How do the gender inequality regimes in call centres constrain the progression of women into management in Scottish call centres?

1.3.2 Research Aim and Objectives

This research aims to explore the ways in which gender inequality regimes influence the context of women in management in call centres in order to better inform organisational policies and practices on diversity and equality both in call centres and in wider contexts.

In order to achieve the aim, the following four objectives have been set:

- 1) Establish the level of women's representation in managerial positions within call centres in Scotland.
- 2) Explore women's perceptions of organisational factors that constitute gender inequality in call centres.
- 3) Identify the perceived barriers to women's progression in management in call centres.

- 4) Explore potential solutions to reduce the impact of gender inequality regimes on women's progression in management through improved organisational policies and practices.

In light of the above, this study aims to address the following research questions:

Research question one (RQ1): What is the level of women's representation in managerial positions within call centres in Scotland?

Research question two (RQ2): What do managers think about factors that constitute gender inequality in their call centres?

Research question three (RQ3): What barriers do women face while progressing in call centre management, and how do they successfully navigate them?

Research question four (RQ4): What effective policies and strategies are available for call centres to reduce gender inequality?

1.3.3 Contribution to knowledge

This study aims to make both theoretical and practical contributions to advancing gender equality within the call centre management domain. First, it theoretically enriches the existing body of knowledge in this field, joining three frameworks (Acker, 2012; Connell, 2006; McDonald, 2015). Second, the research offers practical implications for human resource management

practitioners and organisations to create more gender-balanced and inclusive environments.

The area of women in management in call centres is under-researched and has not been looked at from a woman's perspective, particularly at the senior management level. This thesis adds to the body of knowledge on women in management in call centres, filling a gap in the literature in both theoretical and empirical ways. In terms of a theoretical contribution, this thesis has constructed a conceptual framework entitled the gender inequality regime, combining aspects from existing frameworks (Acker, 2012; Connell, 2006; McDonald, 2015).

This study's empirical contribution is to provide research demonstrating the key elements of the gender inequality regime as they apply to call centres and their women in management. Firstly, the study uncovered and analysed the shape and degree of inequality in call centres by researching the organisational structure, occupational segregation, the gender pay gap, marital status and motherhood. In doing so, it produced a key finding and contribution to knowledge in uncovering the lack of robust government statistics on occupational segregation and the gender pay gap, which compounds the difficulties associated with discovering the levels of women's representation in management in Scotland and the gender pay gap experienced by these women.

A second key finding and contribution to knowledge concerning the effects of the flat organisational structure on severely limiting women's promotion

opportunities is the opposite of Acker's belief that a flat structure would enhance women's opportunities. The study showed no reduction in power differentials in call centres with flat hierarchical structures, nor did they provide more opportunities for women to enter senior management positions. On the contrary, the study found that when fewer opportunities exist, more people compete for them, and women occupy fewer positions. Not many opportunities were available in the call centres studied, where the structure was flat. Women had to fight harder to access those limited senior roles in the In-house call centres, where the structure was more hierarchical.

Secondly, the research meticulously outlined the organisational sub-structure of call centres. It did so by thoroughly investigating the call centres' organising processes and practices, including work organisation, organisational careers and stereotyping. In doing so, it highlighted the barriers to women's career progression and demonstrated that they were similar to those experienced by women in other industry sectors. The research also explored the degree of awareness of gender inequality and the legitimacy of gender inequality. It found that 41% of women respondents had experienced sexual harassment in call centres.

The research integrated marital status and motherhood into the conceptual framework, showing their effects on women's choices regarding how to manage their domestic and childcare responsibilities alongside their work responsibilities.

The researcher used in-depth interviews to capture the nuanced ways gender inequality is experienced in call centres. To sum up, this thesis makes a theoretical and empirical contribution to the knowledge of women in management in call centres in Scotland.

1.4 Research methodology, approach and design

This research adopts an interpretive philosophy and approach as it is important to study gender discrimination in its natural environment to make sense of and understand the views of women in management in call centres. It is expected that this will enable a broader understanding of gender discrimination in call centre management in the UK. The research methodology is qualitative, which is firmly located in the interpretivism paradigm (Denzin and Lincoln, 2003).

The research setting is Scotland, which was chosen due to its high proliferation of call centres. There are estimated to be 400 call centres in Scotland, employing around 98,000 people, with 49% of those employed in Glasgow and its 'hinterland' (Taylor and Anderson, 2012). Where possible, the sample of women managers was drawn from this region of Scotland. The sampling strategy was purposive, as is usual in qualitative research (Holloway, 1997). Data was collected using in-depth interviews, which are also usual in qualitative research (Mason, 2002; Rubin and Rubin, 2012). A total of seventeen interviews were carried out Between December 2019 and February 2021. Fifteen were with women managers, and two were with key informants in the sector, one of whom was male. Scotland is the main location for this study; therefore, it will be discussed in the following section. The data was

analysed using thematic data analysis, which is a common approach to analysing qualitative data. Braun's and Clarke's (2020) framework was also applied to analyse the interview data. NVivo supported thematic analysis, which is customary when analysing qualitative data. This research examines gender inequality regimes in the call centres in Scotland. It is, therefore, important to discuss the concept of the call centre in Scotland, which will be explored in the next section.

1.5 Scotland's call centre industry

This contemporary research examines gender inequality regimes in Scotland's call centres. This section presents an overview of the call centre industry and information about Scotland. Therefore, it is important to present some informative material regarding Scotland's population, with a particular emphasis on the working women population, given the research focus on gender, as well as the broader Scottish economy.

Scotland has a population of 5,479,900, compared to the UK's population of 67,026,300 (Nomis, 2021). Its working population (age 16-64) is 3,494,500, of whom 2,750,000 are economically active, which at 76.7% is less than the UK overall at 77.9% (Nomis, 2021). Scotland has a slightly higher population percentage of women at 51%, while the population of men is 49%, and this almost even split has been supported over the decades (Scottish Government, 2018), and this is set out in Figure 1.1.

Figure 1.1 Scotland's population of women

Source: (National Records of Scotland, 2020)

Content redacted due to copyright restrictions

1.5.1 Scotland's economy and call centres

Table 1.1 sets out the 2019 working population of Scotland by industry sector compared to the UK (Nomis, 2019). In the past four decades, the Scottish economy has undergone major reform, and it has evolved from traditional heavy industry to a more service-based industry, like many Western economies. As can be seen from Table 1.1, only 6.9% of jobs are now in manufacturing. Health and Social Work is the largest industry at 14.7% and other industries with large employment bases include Retail and Wholesale (13.1%), Accommodation and Food Services (7.1%) and Education (7.6%) (Nomis, 2019). Outsourced call centres are included in the Administrative and Support Services Activities figures. However, call centres cover a wide range of industry sectors, including financial services (banking), telecom, civil

servants, technical support, utilities, and insurance and the numbers working in these sectors are included in the totals for each sector and so it is not possible to extract these figures.

An industry report by IBIS World (2024) indicates that the UK call centre market is experiencing significant growth, driven by factors such as increased outsourcing and the rise of e-commerce. Industry analysts at IBIS project the sector will reach £3.2 billion in revenue by 2024, demonstrating a 4.7% compound annual growth rate over the past five years. While outsourcing to countries with lower labour costs remains a prevalent trend, the growth of online retail is simultaneously fuelling demand for call centre services. Furthermore, technological advancements, particularly in artificial intelligence, are expected to shape the future of the industry, potentially reducing reliance on labour while creating new opportunities for innovation.

The number of people employed in this sector in 2016 was 130,000 people, and the industry added £2.5 billion to the Scottish economy. In addition, Scotjobsnet (2020) highlighted that Taylor and Anderson (2011) make an important point about call centres, that both onshoring and offshoring could grow simultaneously. Call centres are present across Scotland but are more visible in Glasgow. As per data from 2012, 12.2% of the working population was employed in call centre-related work. In West Lothian, 7.7%, and in Greenock, 7.2% of those employed were working in this sector (Taylor, 2020). Therefore, call centres are an important source of employment in Scotland.

Furthermore, it is crucial to note that most of the call centres in Scotland are mainly located within the Central Belt (Scotjobsnet, 2014)

Table 1.1 Workforce jobs by industry section (SIC 2007)- seasonally adjusted (June 2020)

	Scotland (Level)	Scotland (%)	United Kingdom (Level)	United Kingdom (%)
Total	2,786,000	-	35,412,000	-
A : Agriculture, Forestry And Fishing	43,000	1.5	362,000	1.0
B : Mining And Quarrying	33,000	1.2	59,000	0.2
C : Manufacturing	191,000	6.9	2,652,000	7.5
D : Electricity, Gas, Steam And Air Conditioning	18,000	0.6	149,000	0.4
E: Water Supply; Sewerage, Waste Management	21,000	0.8	234,000	0.7
F: Construction	164,000	5.9	2,296,000	6.5
G: Wholesale And Retail Trade; Repair Of Vehicles	364,000	13.1	4,999,000	14.1
H: Transportation And Storage	124,000	4.5	1,792,000	5.1
I: Accommodation And Food Service Activities	199,000	7.1	2,404,000	6.8
J: Information And Communication	98,000	3.5	1,546,000	4.4
K: Financial And Insurance Activities	94,000	3.4	1,138,000	3.2
L: Real Estate Activities	40,000	1.4	657,000	1.9
M: Professional, Scientific And Technical Activities	217,000	7.8	3,205,000	9.1
N: Administrative And Support Service Activities	198,000	7.1	2,868,000	8.1
O: Public Administration And Defence	167,000	6.0	1,563,000	4.4
P: Education	211,000	7.6	2,970,000	8.4
Q: Human Health And Social Work Activities	411,000	14.8	4,491,000	12.7
R: Arts, Entertainment And Recreation	92,000	3.3	994,000	2.8

S: Other Service Activities	99,000	3.6	994,000	2.8
T: Activities Of Households As Employers;...	1,000	0.0	40,000	0.1

Notes: % is a proportion of total workforce jobs Source: (Nomis, 2020)

The Central Belt can be seen in Appendix 6. It is the largely urban area of Scotland between, and north and south of, Glasgow and Edinburgh. Although it comprises only 10% of Scotland's land, it contains around 80% of its population. As The Scotsman (2020) points out it "...[north] of the Scottish central belt is referred to as the Highlands [and Islands] and anything south, the Lowlands".

This research is conducted in call centres in Scotland. It is essential to study this sector of the economy, and the number of people employed in this sector. Usually, call centres are the unacknowledged area of research in Scotland (Taylor, 2020). Taylor has published a number of audits, which are listed below in Table 1.2. Taylor (2020) stated that the data demonstrates a considerable expansion of Scotland's call centre industry, with employment rising from 16,000 to 90,000 between 1977 and 2012. This growth encompassed both customer-facing and non-customer-facing roles. According to the most recent comprehensive audit, published in 2012, Scotland's contact centre sector employed 90,000 individuals, including those in non-customer-facing positions who were integral to the centres' operations. While a fresh audit is required, and upon checking, no new audit has been published to ascertain current trends and the impact of automation, the available evidence suggests that employment levels have largely been maintained. In 2016, the

working population of Scotland (16-64) was 2,588,000 (Scottish Government (2017), with call centre employment of 130,000 constituting 5.02%.

Table 1.2 Number of people employed in call centres in Scotland

Year	Number of people employed
1977	16,000
2001	46000
2003	56,000
2008	86,000
2012	90,000

Source:(Taylor, 2020)

In addition, Scottish call centres have shown resistance to the trend of offshoring to lower labour costs in countries such for instance the Philippines and India (Holman et al., 2007).

1.6 Limitation of the research

When interpreting the findings and conclusions of this research, several limitations should be considered. The interviews were conducted remotely via Zoom rather than in-person as initially planned due to the COVID-19 pandemic. This mode of data collection may have resulted in the researcher missing some nonverbal cues from participants. However, this methodological adaptation did not significantly impact the overall quality or validity of the research findings.

The use of an interpretative paradigm and qualitative methodology, which incorporate the researcher's insider (emic) viewpoint, may potentially limit the credibility and authenticity of the findings. This is because diverse analyses, interpretations, and conclusions drawn from such an approach may be susceptible to bias (Denzin and Yvonna, 2005), although reflexivity was employed.

While the sample size of 17 participants is not unusually small for qualitative research, it is relatively limited, potentially constraining the ability to generalise the findings to a broader population. The research was also confined to a particular geographic region, Scotland, which may limit the transferability of the findings to other national contexts. Additionally, due to the COVID-19 pandemic lockdown, the call centres included in the sample were located solely within the Scotland region, further limiting the geographic scope of the study. Future research could expand the geographic scope, incorporate a mixed-methods approach, and involve a larger sample size to address these limitations.

The researcher's prior experience working in the call centre industry could potentially introduce bias due to their existing knowledge of the context. To mitigate this, the researcher employed reflexivity, maintained a research journal, and took detailed notes to enhance the accuracy and objectivity of the analysis and interpretation.

Overall, despite the limitations of the study, the research results are worthwhile for contributing to an understanding of gender inequality regimes in call centres

in Scotland as well as providing information that can be used in order to better inform organisational policies and practices on diversity and equality both in call centres and in wider contexts.

1.7 The Structure and organisations of the Thesis

This section sets out the format of this research. This first chapter presents the background of the thesis, its rationale, aims and objectives, and brief information about the methodology used in this research. This section also establishes Scotland's profile in terms of its population, geography, economy and the historical development of the call centre industry.

Chapter two constitutes the literature review. This chapter evaluates previous empirical research and theoretical conceptualisation. The primary theoretical approach of this study is Joan Acker's and Raewyn Connell's sets of gender processes. In her framework, Acker (2012) discusses the gendering of the organisation, including both visible and invisible elements. Besides that, two other factors are added, marital status and motherhood, as these influence women's decisions about the amount and type of paid work they carry out (McDonald, 2015). This chapter also discusses call centres and management within call centres.

Chapter three presents the details of the research methodology. The process of carrying out the fieldwork and particulars about conducting and analysing the interviews are given in this chapter. The research philosophy, research setting and sample, the research strategy, and methods used for data

collection and analysis are also discussed. At the end of this chapter, the ethical consideration of this research is explored.

Chapter four discusses the results of the interviews. The data collected were qualitative. The interviews were analysed using thematic analysis. Node analysis was performed in NVivo to identify the emerging themes from the interviews. It also includes a discussion that draws together the themes of the findings in the previous chapter with the broader literature, presents possible explanations in relation to the literature and theoretical framework, and explores how they answer the research questions.

Chapter Five, the final chapter, contains the conclusion and recommendations. It discusses the extent to which this research met the objectives and summarises the conclusion reached in this study, presenting its limitations and implications for future research.

Chapter 2 - Review of the Literature

2.1 Introduction

Following the introduction, this chapter aims to examine the existing literature on gender and women in management and provide a strong background to inform the study. The chapter starts with a theoretical review of the literature on gender theories before examining UK legislation regarding gender equality. It then sets out the results of a traditional literature review into the measurable forms of gender inequality. It follows that by discussing the glass ceiling, the approaches that seek to explain it, and the effects that hinder women's progression in management. It then examines the call centre industry, including an inclusive investigation of call centres and women's employment in call centres. It concludes by setting out the conceptual framework for the thesis. This framework will guide the analysis of how call centres are structured and practices in Scottish call centres. The themes explored in the literature review will ultimately inform and support the development of the research questions presented at the end of the literature review. The following section will discuss gender.

2.2 What is gender?

It is important at the outset of this thesis to understand gender: its meaning and the difference between gender and sex. According to Oxford Dictionaries (2018), the term gender has been used since the 14th century, firstly denoting the masculine, feminine and neuter pronouns and nouns used in language.

However, it was less generally at that time also used to denote a person's biological sex, that is male or female. However, by the 1960s and 1970s, the distinction between sex and gender had been recognised by feminists and others attempting to develop a more critical account of women's and men's relations and positions in society. It was a way of making it clear that what was often thought of as natural and biological (sex) was, in fact, social, cultural, historical, and indeed political (gender) (Hearn and Parkin, 2002). Connell (2009) concludes that until the 1970s, the term "gender" was not commonly accepted globally.

The debate about the meaning of gender has continued to develop (Parkin and Hearn, 2001), and the term has become part of everyday language (Acker, 1992); its meaning is assumed to be relatively clear, namely, to refer to social expectations and sex roles and this is the stance adopted by this thesis. However, this thesis also accepts Marshall's (1995) argument that the term gender has taken on a much broader and more diffuse set of meanings; it has become a general label for talking about women, men, the relationships between them, and related aspects of organising processes through which gender differentiated issues of power take various forms.

It is also important to point out that the term gender has often been seen as binary, that is, referring to male and female, as has the term sex. However, it is generally recognised that not everyone's sex is binary, as some individuals are born intersex (EHRC, 2011). In addition, not everyone identifies with their sex at birth, and this is recognised by the Equality Act 2010, which prohibits

discrimination for being transsexual, that is, a person whose gender identity is different from that assigned to them at birth (EHRC, 2018). It is worth pointing out that the term 'trans' is also used as an umbrella term to represent people who "may describe themselves using one or more of a wide variety of terms, including (but not limited to) transgender, transsexual, gender-queer (GQ), gender-fluid, non-binary, gender-variant, crossdresser, genderless, agender, nongender, third gender, two-spirit, bi-gender, trans man, trans woman, trans masculine, trans feminine and neutrois" (Stonewall, 2017). It is, therefore, important to state that this thesis adopts this broader and non-binary approach to the term gender, reflecting the evolving nature of the concept.

In conclusion, therefore, what is clear is that the term gender has been used not just for decades but for centuries. However, over more recent decades, the term has evolved from merely being used to define human biology in a much broader approach in order to reflect, firstly, the concerns of second-wave feminism and, secondly, the recognition that gender is non-binary. It is, therefore, this broader definition of gender that is adopted by this thesis.

2.3 Gender and inequality in the workplace

Gender inequality is a persistent issue in the workplace, and scholars have suggested that gender discrimination can be a significant contributor to gender inequality (Heilman and Caleo, 2018). Gender inequality policies in the UK are bound up with other policies related to family and women. Historically, the United Kingdom has a long history of gender-segregated labour and social policies that were helpful to men (McDonald, 2014). For example, until the mid-

nineteenth century, men were legally viewed as the head of the household, were their wives 'guardians' and had custody of any children (McDonald, 2014), and it was not until 1929 that women became persons 'of their own right' (Hughes, 2000). In the late 19th and early 20th centuries, the UK's women began to gain political and civil equality: for example, in the 1920s, women gained voting rights (Crompton and Feuvre, 2000); they were able to attend and graduate from universities; they could enter the professions and become doctors, accountants, lawyers and civil servants (McDonald, 2014). However, despite these social and political reforms, the workplace remained heavily segregated and was geared towards the 'male breadwinner' (Crompton, 2001). For example, until the 1960s, young men in British banks received a pay rise when they got married; however, when women got married, they would be shifted to a lower-level job with non-promotable grades (Crompton, 2001). In addition, women could be dismissed on marriage and/or when becoming pregnant.

During the 1960s and 1970s, the efforts of second-wave Western feminism resulted in gender equality legislation that attempted to eliminate inequality in the workplace, and this is discussed in Section 2.4. In addition to workplace legislation, other reforms in Western countries included: the decriminalisation of abortion in the UK and France; in the US, a constitutional guarantee of equal rights for women; in Australia, reform in rape laws. Also, it is worth mentioning that many countries extended state provisions for childcare, encouraged non-sexist education, and provided protection against sexual harassment (Connell, 1990). During this period, more women entered professional and managerial

occupations, jobs which used to be filled by men. Therefore, the segregation of occupations has decreased (Blau et al., 2013). However, women remain under-represented in management, and this will be discussed further in Section 2.7.4. Despite this, there has been a change in gender inequality in the last half-century. They sometimes called it the 'gender revolution'. This progress happened from 1970 till 2018; in recent decades, the change has slowed or stalled based on some indicators. The causes of the slowdown suggested that progress further requires substantial cultural and institutional change. It is suggested that to progress, it is required that men participate in care and household work and government provision of childcare and that organisations need to adopt policies that reduce gender discrimination and help women and men combine family care responsibilities with jobs (England et al., 2020, p. 6990).

2.4 UK legislation on gender equality

This section presents the UK's legislation on gender equality. It is important to examine this legislation and its effectiveness in removing inequality in society, though the latter will be explored in the following section. It is also worth noting that The Sex Discrimination Act (SDA) was introduced in 1975 in the UK to reduce discrimination against women, outlawing discrimination against men and women in education, work and training on the grounds of sex or marital status. Until then, a woman could be dismissed from employment on marriage.

The Employment Protection Act was also introduced in 1975, providing maternity pay under certain circumstances and making it illegal to dismiss a

woman because she was pregnant. In the same year, the Equal Pay Act (1970) came into effect, prohibiting the less favourable treatment of women in terms of pay and conditions of service. The SDA also established the Equal Opportunities Commission (EOC) to promote equality and work against different kinds of discrimination (UK Legislation, 1975). Since the 1970s, there have been various pieces of legislation extending women's rights at work, the latest being the Equality Act (2010), which substituted the previous anti-discriminatory laws with a single Act and combined the previous commissions, such as the EOC, into the Equality and Human Rights Commission (EHRC). This Act aimed to make the law easier to recognise and to strengthen anti-discrimination measures (Equality Act 2010, 2013). According to this act, it is illegal for an employer or a company to discriminate against workers due to their sex (ACAS, 2015). According to the EHRC (2015), it is the basic right of every individual that they should not be discriminated against on the grounds of their sex. It is generally recognised that there are four types of sex discrimination: direct discrimination, indirect discrimination, victimisation, and harassment (EHRC, 2015). Thus, it can be established that a significant amount of attention has been given to gender discrimination in the workplace. In the past forty years, a number of pieces of legislative measures have been introduced to reduce and overcome discrimination issues. However, a review of available literature suggests that discrimination in different forms still exists.

2.5 Forms of gender inequality

Gender inequality manifests in numerous ways across societies and impacts various aspects of life. According to the United Nations (2023) report, half of the global population believes that men are better suited for leadership positions in business and politics than women, reflecting deeply embedded societal biases. These biases are also reflected in the severe underrepresentation of women in leadership positions. On average, the share of women as heads of a country or heads of government has remained around 10 per cent since 1995, and in the labour market, women occupy less than a third of managerial roles (United Nations, 2023). This section will discuss various forms of gender inequality, beginning with the gender pay gap, one of the most visible manifestations. The gender pay gap, a persistent and widespread issue, highlights women's systemic disadvantages in the labour market (Ortiz-Ospina, Hasell and Roser, 2024). Another form of gender inequality is occupational segregation, where certain occupations are dominated by one gender, which is a significant driver of inequality (Carranza, Das and Kotikula, 2023). Finally, the "glass ceiling" is a powerful metaphor for analysing the invisible yet formidable barriers that prevent women from reaching the highest levels of leadership and power across various sectors (BF, 2018). While gender issues have not yet reached the core issue on most international and domestic agendas, there is growing attention and official commitment to promoting gender equality (Engeli and Mazur, 2018). This section will examine measurable forms of gender inequality: the pay gap, occupational segregation and the glass ceiling.

2.5.1 Gender pay gap

Pay and rewards are important to employees in any organisation (Punshon *et al.*, 2019). The issue of the gender-based pay gap has been the subject of extensive scholarly inquiry over several decades. Yet, it continues to be an area of active and innovative academic research (Blau and Khan, 2017).

Females traditionally dominate the call centre industry. Blau and Khan (2017) state that the over-representation of women in low-paying, female-dominated occupations also contributes to the pay gap. This section will examine the literature on the gender pay gap between women and men. For many years, the issue of the gender pay gap has been of concern for economists and policymakers, who have been working on explaining and reducing it. Other names for the gender pay gap are the “gender wage gap” (Blau and Kahn, 2007), the “gender gap in earnings” (Blau and Kahn, 2007) or “male-female income disparity”. In this thesis, it will be referred to as the gender pay gap. The gender pay differential commonly refers to the discrepancy in average hourly compensation between men and women employees, even after accounting for variations in human capital characteristics like educational attainment and work experience (Blau and Kahn, 2006).

There is a robust body of research examining the persistent gender-based wage gap. Numerous studies have explored the magnitude of the earnings differential between men and women, the underlying factors driving its persistence and evolution, and the ramifications for economic well-being and societal advancement. The disparity has frequently been ascribed to a

confluence of factors, including women's personal and occupational attributes, the structural composition of the labour market, and the influence of institutional, cultural, and social norms and traditions (Ñopo et al., (2012).

Close the Gap (2019) identified several key factors contributing to the gender pay gap, including occupational segregation, lack of high-quality part-time and flexible work, undervaluation of female-dominated jobs, women's disproportionate unpaid care responsibilities, biased recruitment and progression practices, male-oriented workplace cultures, and direct pay discrimination. According to Striking Women (2022), for every pound a man earns, women still earn just 87 pence.

Close the Gap (2023) also presents data on the gender pay gap in Scotland, building upon the statistics previously published in March 2022. It delves into the intricacies of accurately measuring and reporting gender pay disparity. The existence of the gender pay gap is evident from a brief review of labour force statistics. The data was taken from the UK Office for National Statistics, which publishes annual data on the gender pay gap in its Annual Survey of Hours and Earnings. Data from 2021 to 2022 indicate a modest increase in Scotland's mean gender pay gap, rising from 10.1% to 10.9%.

Similarly, the average pay disparity between male and female full-time workers has grown from 6.6% in 2021 to 7.9% in 2022. Moreover, on average, women employed in part-time roles earn 26.3% less than their full-time male counterparts, representing a slight decline of 0.6 percentage points. These figures underscore the systemic undervaluation of 'women's work', which

remains concentrated in low-paid, part-time positions. Notably, women constitute the majority of part-time workers, being three times more likely to work reduced hours compared to men, at 38.3% and 13.4%, respectively. The EHRC (2011) found out that men working full-time continue to have higher average hourly, weekly, and annual earnings than women (Perfect, 2011).

Although there is considerable evidence of the gender pay gap, study after study demonstrates that many individuals are not aware of the gender pay gap (Blackaby et al., 2005; Lang, 2008). Several scholars (Jackson and Grabski, 1988; Jamali et al., 2008; Lang, 2008) documented that their sampled respondents did not perceive the existence of the gender pay gap, even when the gap was statistically determined. Eurobarometer (2010) study found that around 50 per cent of Europeans consider the gender pay gap as a priority in the field of gender equality. Moreover, around 82 per cent of Europeans consider the issue of the gender pay gap should be addressed urgently.

The UK introduced an active policy concerning the gender pay gap. Recently, UK law was amended to require all British employers with 250 or more employees to publish their gender pay gaps annually (Gov.uk, 2017).

Interestingly, women are generally paid 6.1% more than men in call centres in the UK (ONS, 2018a), and this requires further investigation. It is also worth noting that the gender pay gap in Scotland (5.7%) is lower than in the UK (8.6%) (ONS, 2019a). However, overall, according to the World Economic Forum (2021), it is projected that it will take 135 years to close the global

gender pay gap at the current rate if progress continues. While empirical evidence suggests the existence of this gap, awareness among the general population appears to be lacking.

2.5.2 Occupational segregation (horizontal)

The decreasing gender segregation in occupations has been a key structural change in the economy over the last 60 years (Busch, 2020). Occupational segregation by gender is related to the inequality in the distribution of women and men among different occupational categories and job types (England et al., 2020). Even though legislation prohibits discrimination on the grounds of gender in education, training, and employment, most of the occupational sectors and jobs and training in Scotland remain gender segregated. The effects of gender segregation are clear in vocational training programs, where women are frequently directed towards lower-tier apprenticeships compared to their male counterparts (Campbell and Gillespie, 2017). Matteazzi et (2018) illustrated that the UK is not the only country in the EU that is facing the issue, but in the member states of the European Union, similarities are found in the patterns of occupational segregation.

There are two types of occupational segregation: vertical and horizontal (Hakim, 1979). Horizontal segregation “exists where men and women are most commonly working in different types of occupation”, while vertical segregation “exists where men are working most commonly in higher grade occupations, and women are most commonly working in lower grade occupations or vice versa” (Hakim, 1979:19, cited by Beechey, 1986:91).

In many European states, the science, engineering, and technology (SET), ICT, agriculture, manufacturing, construction, and financial services sectors remain dominated by men. Women continue to remain very under-represented in areas such as engineering and sciences (Toosy *et al.*, 2022). While on the other hand, Thewlis *et al.* (2004) mentioned that the service sector, including healthcare, social work, and education, remains largely dominated by women. These are examples of horizontal segregation. According to (Matteazzi *et al.* 2018), gender segregation in the different areas of employment remains a key factor contributing to the gender gap in earnings.

The UK labour market is among the most segregated in Europe. Scott (1994) found that 66% of men worked exclusively or mainly with other men, and 54% of women worked exclusively or mainly with women. In 1995, half of the women employed were in just three occupational groups: clerical and secretarial, personal and protective services, and sales, compared to about one-fifth of men (Court, 1995). By 2018, this figure had dropped to only 44% (ONS, 2018b). It can be observed that there has been progress in gender discrimination; in reality, the occupational sector remains segregated. Segregation also exists in occupational hierarchies, which will be discussed in the following section.

2.5.3 The glass-ceiling or vertical job segregation

The term 'glass ceiling' became popular in 1986 in the United States and was used by Morrison *et al.* (1987) in their ground-breaking book, which illustrated that women face different issues in their journeys towards executive-level

positions in corporate organisations. The term immediately got attention from policymakers, journalists and the public, which then led to the US government legislating the Glass Ceiling Act, for which the Glass Ceiling Commission (GCC) was formed. Their task was to conduct a study and to come up with some recommendations on “eliminating artificial barriers to the advancement of women and minorities” to “management and decision-making positions in business”. Their report found that there was a barrier for women and persons of colour to get to the highest level of organisations (Federal Glass Ceiling Commission, 1995, p.5). The report also found that 97% of the senior managers of Fortune 1000 industrial and Fortune 500 companies were white; 95 to 97% were male. In Fortune 2000 industrial and service companies, 5% of senior managers are women, and of that 5%, virtually all are white (Federal Glass Ceiling Commission, 1995). Furthermore, the GCC report established that fewer women were hired into positions that would lead to top or executive-level positions. They were more usually hired in personnel and human resource positions as compared to line manager, sales, marketing or production positions. It was also found that organisations occasionally required a mixed kind of experience in order to progress, and women were not in a position to develop this sort of experience (Federal Glass Ceiling Commission, 1995).

In 1971, the number of women in management in Great Britain was 21% (Hakim, 1996), but by 2018, women only held 34.88% of managerial jobs in the United Kingdom 2018 (NOMIS, 2018). This contrasts with the number of women in the workplace, which has risen from 36% in 1975 (Equal

Opportunities Commission (EOC), 1983) to 47.03% in 2018 (Office of National Statistics (ONS), 2018a). In terms of women in executive and leadership positions in the United Kingdom, research has been carried out since 1999 into FTSE 100 companies, and this shows that the number of women Directors has risen from 69 (5.8%) in 2000 to 121 (10.5%) in 2005 (Ruth et al., 2007), 163 (15%) in 2012 (Sealy and Vinnicombe, 2012) and 305 (29%) in 2018 (Vinnicombe et al., 2018). It is important to note that there is a government-backed target for women on boards of 33% by 2020, which 32 companies have already reached (Vinnicombe et al., 2018). During the same period, the number of women Executive Directors rose from 11 (2%) in 2000 to 14 (3.4%) in 2005 (Sealy et al., 2007), 20 (6.6%) in 2012 (Sealy and Vinnicombe, 2012) and 25 (9.7%) in 2018 (Vinnicombe et al., 2018). Over the same period, the number of women non-executive directors has risen from 60 (9.1%) in 2000 to 107 (14.5%) in 2005 (Sealy et al., 2007), 143 (22.4%) in 2012 (Sealy and Vinnicombe, 2012) and 280 (35.4%) by 2018 (Vinnicombe et al., 2018). In 2000, there were 42 companies without any female directors (Sealy et al., 2007), but by 2011, this had fallen to 11 (Sealy and Vinnicombe, 2012) and to zero by 2014 (Vinnicombe et al., 2018).

However, progress in the FTSE 250 has been less consistent. In 2018, there were ten companies with no women at the board level; the percentage of women on boards was 23.7%, and the number of women executive directors stood at only 6.4% (Vinnicombe et al., 2018). This indicates that there may be problems for women in progressing from FTSE 250 to FTSE 100 companies.

All this shows that despite the progress in the UK over the past fifty years, women are still under-represented in the upper levels of organisations.

Hoobler et al. (2011, p.151) contend that the glass ceiling is a “persistent problem” and, in addition, it “stymies the opportunity for a substantial proportion of the US workforce, that is, women, to contribute to organisations via powerful managerial roles”. It is, of course, not only in the US that this problem exists. However, as pointed out by Eagly and Carli (2007 p.2), the glass ceiling can no longer be considered an “absolute barrier” at the most senior organisational level, as some women now reach those most senior levels, albeit often by a more complex route than that of men in similar positions. Eagly and Carli (2007 p.2), therefore, argue that a better term is the glass maze or labyrinth, defined as a “complex journey...not simple or direct...full of twists and turns both expected and unexpected...[but] with a viable route to the centre”. However, they also contend that, in fact, blockages to women’s progress, such as those set out earlier, exist at all organisational levels and that “the scarcity of female corporate officers is the sum of discrimination that has operated at all ranks, not evidence of a particular obstacle to advancement as women approach the top” (Eagly and Carly, 2007 p.3). This view is echoed by Acker (2009).

Women appear to have more choices in their employment paths, but still, they are more likely to be employed in less secure and low-paying jobs, while men continue to dominate higher-status occupations. The workforces in call centres are predominantly female, and it would be expected that call centres would

provide wider opportunities for women's advancement and should provide flexible employment, career opportunities, "female-friendly" workplaces, semi-professional knowledge work, semi-skilled clerical and service work" (Scholarios and Taylor, 2011 p.64). However, they point out there are also negative aspects of call centres, which have been called 'a female ghetto', where the jobs are demanding, there is a glass ceiling that stops women from progressing, there is limited progression, and, therefore, the jobs in the call centre are low-status and feminised. Scholarios and Taylor (2011) also found out that more women are segregated into mass production roles compared to mass customisation roles, in other words, team leader and managerial roles. They suggest that the reasons behind this are greater domestic responsibilities, less career support from managers, and lower educational qualifications. However, they also suggest that it is difficult for women to get a team manager role even if she has the same qualifications as men.

There is little data on women in management in call centres. However, as set out in figure 2.1, in a survey of 3,200 call centres, Contact Babel (2003, cited in Department for Trade and Industry, 2004) found that women and men share the role of first-line managers, that is, Team Leader, equally in the UK. Management in the IT sector is still dominated by men, while women predominate in HR and training. It is important to point out that research objective one is to establish the level of women's representation in managerial positions within call centres in Scotland. Therefore, it is important to examine the vertical segregation of call centre jobs.

Globally, call centres have flat organisational structures; 71% of employees in call centres are female, and 12% are managers (Holman et al., 2007). Managers in call centres encounter many challenges while performing their jobs. They operate in a capital-intensive environment where there is a high demand for continual investment and a need to keep updated with speedy technological developments (Robinson and Morley, 2006). Managers in the call centre manage numerous employees, usually working across different shifts. Akroyd et al. (2006) added that in the call centre environment, the manager has a crucial role as a link between customer service representatives and senior management.

Figure 2.1 Managers by Gender

Source: ContactBabel cited in Department for Trade and Industry, 2004

However, research into the industry by the then Department of Trade and Industry DTI (2004) found that there is a difference in the numbers of managers in different parts of the UK and Ireland. In traditionally more patriarchal regions,

such as Ireland and Scotland, men are more common in management. In Wales and East Anglia, contact centres have a larger female proportion of managers in call centres. Having established the glass ceiling, the next section will discuss approaches to the glass ceiling.

2.6 Approaches explaining the under-representation of women in management

Women in management are often thought of as a late 20th-century phenomenon. However, research shows that women have a long history in management (Kwolek-Folland, 1998; McDonald, 2015). Examples through the centuries in the United Kingdom include, firstly, the pre-industrial times, farmer's wives who traded in dairy, cheese making and butter (Hakim, 1979). Secondly, there were nineteenth-century women who ran lodging houses and shop businesses. Finally, in 1911, early twentieth-century women constituted nineteen per cent of employers and 20 per cent of administrators and managers (Hakim, 1979). The emergence of the managerial class in the second half of the 20th century did not initially provide more opportunities for women to move into management. In 1951, women constituted 15% of management. By 1961, it had only risen to 16%, and by 1971, it was 21%, scarcely more than sixty years earlier (Hakim, 1979). It was this lack of progress that prompted research into women's under-representation in management in the 1960s and 1970s. The research of that time tended to explore the phenomenon using one of two approaches: firstly, the person-centred approach (Horner, 1972; Terborg, 1977; Riger and Galligan, 1980) and secondly, the situational or organisational structure approach (Kanter,

1977) and these will be examined in the following sections. It is worth pointing out that these two approaches are still used today.

2.6.1 The person-centred approach

This approach focuses on the biological, psychological and sociological differences between men and women and the ways in which these influence the behaviours, attitudes, traits, skills and abilities of men and women in management and the extent to which these can explain women's under-representation in management (Parker and Fagenson, 1994). However, Fagenson (1990) counsels that this approach can only provide tentative results as sex differences tend to show up only in the laboratory, rather than in field research. It is also worth pointing out that this approach also needs to be viewed within its cultural context.

Two of the earliest pieces of research on biological, psychological and sociological differences were undertaken by Horner (1969) and Henning and Jardim (1977). Horner (1969) argued that the absence of women in management was due to women's fear of success, while Henning and Jardim (1977) contended that it was due to women's lack of risk-taking. However, research following up Horner's found that fear of success could be re-interpreted as fear of punishment for 'deviant' behaviour (Riger and Galligan, 1980). A more recent example of this approach comes from Hoobler et al. (2011, p.152), who points out an example of recent research that has focused on "the role testosterone plays in male risk-taking, and the role oxytocin and empathy play in female career choices", which can be used to argue that

“differences in career achievement are [due to] a natural, predetermined difference between men and women, justifying the status quo”. However, it is worth pointing out that there have also been studies which show that there are few differences in the way men and women behave in managerial and leadership roles (Donnell and Hall, 1980, cited by Parker and Fagenson, 1994; Nieva and Gutek, 1981, cited by Adler and Izraeli, 1994; Powell, 1988, cited by Adler and Izraeli, 1994; Ragins, 1991, cited by, Adler and Izraeli, 1994).

While there is maybe little in the way of definitive research outcomes from this approach, a key cultural element is that of sex role stereotyping, and in fact, it has been argued that this is the “primary roadblock” to women’s management careers (Dipboye, 1987, p.120). Schein (1994) coined the phrase ‘think manager, think male’ to summarise her research which showed that “[there is] a deeply held belief that managerial positions are ‘for men only’ or ‘only men are really qualified to do these jobs’” (Schein, 2007:12). As women have climbed higher up the managerial ladder to executive positions, further research has demonstrated the existence of the ‘think leader, think male’ stereotype (Koenig *et al.*, 2011).

Stereotyping is reflected in social role theory (Eagly, 1987). Stereotyping or “gender role beliefs form as people observe male and female behaviour and infer that the sexes possess corresponding dispositions” (Eagly and Wood, 2012, p. 458). In addition, (Dipboye, 1987, p. 121, emphasis in original) argues that sex-characteristic stereotypes refer to how women “are” and sex role stereotypes to how they ‘should be’ and he argues that they overlap in a sense

that “what men and women are the way they should be”. These beliefs, such as women being ‘caregivers’ and men being ‘providers’, are then translated into the workplace and help to explain occupational segregation. Stereotyping can also provide an explanation for the unequal division of unpaid work that men and women do in the home. While women spend, on average, 26 hours per week on activities such as childcare, laundry and cleaning, men spend only 16 hours per week on such work (ONS, 2016).

2.6.2 The situational or organisational structure approach

This approach stems from Kanter’s (1977) ground-breaking work on women in organisations and contends that structural and situational factors within organisations result in women’s lack of progress within management. Research carried out since the 1970s has identified many of these factors: organisational career paths that ‘filter’ out women at different levels (Bartol, 1978); the continuing stereotyping of management jobs (Powell, 1993; Powell et al, 2002); the small numbers of women at senior levels remaining a barrier to the progression of women, but a critical mass of women at all levels proving an aid to the promotion of women to all levels (Cohen et al., 1998); the importance of women performing to a higher standard than men, developing management styles which are acceptable to men, managing their careers by seeking out key organisational assignments and having a mentor (Ragins et al, 1998); the importance of networking (Ragins et al, 1998), but the difficulties in accessing social capital (Timberlake, 2005; Kumra and Vinnicombe, 2010) and the role of impression management (Kumra and Vinnicombe, 2010);

prejudice towards female leaders based on role congruity (Eagly and Karau, 2002); and family-work conflict biases towards female employees (Hoobler et al, 2014).

Elacqua et al. (2009) introduced a model for understanding that why women managers rarely reach the highest level of organisations and suggest that organisational variables of interpersonal and situational nature are positively related to the perception of treating women differently, and in turn, it is related to the glass ceiling. Interpersonal issues discuss the factors related to treating women differently based on their interpersonal matters or relations. These factors include the role a manager can play as a mentor, which points out towards the presence of the old boy networks and the effect that being friends with the decision maker in the company has on the promotion. These relations among women and men within an organisation have an influence on how women and men are treated differently (Elacqua *et al.*, 2009). Mentoring is one of the interpersonal issues. A mentor is someone who is a higher-ranking, knowledgeable, and experienced employee who is dedicated to providing help and support to lower-level employees to move up the career ladder (Raabe and Beehr, 2003). Raabe and Beehr (2003) further added that mentoring can assist in making a relationship between mentor and mentee providing career development, role modelling and social support.

After discussing Kanter's approach and discussing the organisational reasons for women's lack of progress, the next section will highlight Fagenson's (1990) gender-organisation-system approach.

2.6.3 The Gender-Organisation-System Approach

The importance of society to the person-centred and organisational structure approaches is recognised by Fagenson (1990), who developed the gender-organisation-system (GOS) approach. She contends that this GOS approach “suggests that women’s behaviour and limited corporate progress in organisations can be due to their gender, the organisational context and/or the larger social and institutional system in which they function” (Fagenson, 1993, p. 6) adding a further two factors namely that “(a) an individual and his or her organisation cannot be understood separate from the society (culture) in which he or she works, and (b) when the individual, the organisation, or the system in which they are embedded changes, the other components change as well” (Fagenson, 1993, p. 6). Parker and Fagenson (1994, p. 19) contend that “the GOS approach suggests that people, organisations, roles and societies all change simultaneously in response to environmental shifts, albeit at different paces”. As a result, “progress occurs not as the result of singular action but, rather because of interaction among social forces, including political and legal activity, societal beliefs and values, and organisational and individual action” (Parker and Fagenson, 1994, p.19). One example of this approach can be found in the effects of the actions of second-wave feminists in agitating for equality legislation, the initial resistance to this by some trade unions and employers and the effects of the 1970s equality legislation on ensuring that women could not be dismissed on the grounds of pregnancy. Of course, one of the barriers to change is not just societal culture but also organisational culture, and this will be explored in the next section.

2.7 Gender theories

This research focuses on identifying barriers to women's progression in management within call centres. It begins by looking at the development of the concept of feminism. It then presents the background and key concepts of a number of gender theories that seek to explain the inequalities that women face when climbing the career ladder into management and senior management positions in organisations. Thereafter, specific barriers to gender inequalities will be identified. The following section will discuss gender theories to discover some of the disadvantages women may face during their careers when trying to get into senior management.

2.7.1 Feminism theory

Historically, the term 'feminism' was created in France in the 1880s. The word feminism is the combination of two French words (femme) for woman and (isme), which "referred to a social movement or political ideology" (Freedman, 2002, p.336). The usage of the term feminism then spread across Europe in the 1890s, and it reached South America by 1910 (Freedman, 2002). This was the period of first-wave feminism, of the suffragette movement, when women were fighting for voting rights. The term was also part of feminism's second wave in the 1960s, with its slogan 'the personal is political when women were fighting against all inequality, including within the workplace, the family and reproductive rights (Burkett, 2021). Third-wave feminism emerged in the 1990s, with its focus on intersectionality and multiculturalism (Fernandes, 2010). There is a contention that fourth-wave feminism emerged in 2012 with

a focus on sexual harassment and rape culture and the subsequent MeToo movement, although this is challenged by some feminists (Tikkanen, 2021). Feminism is also described as an intellectual and political project, a movement for equality and social justice and a process for theory development (Calás and Smircich, 2014; Benschop and Verloo, 2016).

In terms of women generally, and the focus of this thesis on women in management in particular, it can be argued that the efforts of second-wave feminists were responsible for much of the equality legislation of the 1960s and 1970s, particularly in Western economies. This legislation made it possible for women to progress into management jobs. Third-wave feminism, through its emphasis on multiculturalism, brought to light the different experiences of black women as compared to white women. In contrast, fourth-wave feminism has highlighted the previously ignored and hidden issue of the sexual harassment experienced by women in the workplace and in society. It is worth noting that the UK government is currently consulting on creating a new criminal offence specifically targeting public sexual harassment (Home Office, 2022), and it is difficult to see how this would have been deemed important without the 'MeToo' movement.

2.7.2 Social role theory

Social role theory (Eagly, 1987) suggests that gender stereotypes are created due to the different roles that women and men hold in society (Eagly, Wood and Diekmann, 2000; Eagly and Wood, 2012). Historically, they argue, these were determined by men's strengths and women's childbearing

responsibilities, and that is why men associated themselves with roles like hunting and labouring occupations in the public domain while women continued to look after the home life and children. Similarly, when societies became more industrial, women were blocked from participating in the economy as they had the demanding job of rearing and childbearing. As a result, men were provided with the opportunity to develop skills in this area (Eagly and Wood, 2012). Linked to social role theory is the distinction between descriptive and injunctive norms of behaviour (Cialdini et al., 1991). The former is based on what people actually do, and the latter on what they 'should' do. Therefore, women's roles usually involve openness, caring, intimacy, solidarity, cooperation and connections. Opposingly, men's roles generally focused on mastery and self-assertion, promotion, expansion and protection. This results in occupational segregation, where roles are numerically dominated by one gender (Range and Jenkins, 2010). This theory, therefore, helps to explain the reasons why, in call centres and generally, men dominate the IT sector while women are more focused on customer service. In addition, this theory is particularly important to this thesis on women in management as it resonates with Schein's (1973, 1994) 'think manager, think male' research.

2.7.3 Gender Schema Theory

The gender schema theory (GST) was developed by Bem (1981) and is considered one of her significant contributions. Gender schema is the cognitive theory of sex typing; it focuses on the processing of information. The drive to make associations and categorise based on gender is called gender schematic

reasoning (Serbin *et al.*, 1993). Bussey and Bandura (1999) further added that the theory mainly focuses on individual differences in gender's schematic processing of information. This approach concentrates on how people at an early age in society become gendered and the impact of this gendering on their cognitive and categorical processing throughout their lifetime. Children acquire theories and ideas about what it means to be feminine and masculine at an early age, called gender schemas. Children use these theories to categorise information, make decisions and regulate behaviour (Starr and Zurbriggen, 2016), and age renders them more complex (Martin and Halverson, 1981). Range and Jenkins (2010) argued that GST is mainly used as a general theory of an overarching theoretical framework.

This theory is important in that it sets out how gender schemas are internalised from a young age (Range and Jenkins, 2010). It also explains how gender schema translates into the workplace. For example, Lemons and Parzinger (2007), in their research into discrimination experienced by women in IT, demonstrate that men in IT seem to hold traditional gender schema, making their cognitive processing gender schematic, while women in IT appear to hold non-traditional gender schema. Similarly, Orser *et al.* (2012), in their research on women in IT in Canada, observe that research has shown that gender schema exerts an influence over women in the workplace at the level of the individual, the organisation and the industry. In terms of working with and overcoming traditional gender schema, Orser *et al.* (2012) also indicate the importance of strategies including mentoring and networking for women at the

individual level as well as the importance of the CEO's attitude towards equality at an organisational level.

2.7.4 Preference theory

Preference theory is a relatively new theory. It contends that it predicts and explains "women's choices between family work and market work" and argues that it is "historically informed, multidisciplinary, empirically based, prospective rather than retrospective in orientation, and applicable in all rich modern societies" (Hakim, 2000 p.1). According to preference theory, women in those societies can choose between family work and market work and make their choice based on their preference for one of three lifestyles: family work, paid work, or one that is a combination of family work and paid work. Hakim terms these three groups: home-centred who, she contends, account for 20% of women and who prefer not to work but are focused on their families; work-centred, again around 20% of women who are committed to working; and adaptive, who account for the remaining 60% of women that both want to work and to have time with their families, but who are not committed to their work or careers.

Preference theory assumes that there are no constraints on women's choices and ignores structural constraints, such as lack of childcare (McRae, 2003). Leahy and Doughney (2014, p.38) agree and argue that Hakim's theory ignores "the crucial phenomenon of 'adaptive preferences', whereby women adjust their preferences in response to persistent gender inequality" in society. They further contend that women tend to take career breaks at the peak of

their working age due to childcare responsibilities, which leads to women's careers and progression being compromised. In addition, Leahy and Doughney (2014) state that to reduce this problem, household work and the social nature of care must be taken into account. They argue that a societal dimension requires a societal discussion and an agreed social contract providing care without hurting women's careers. They posit that societal attention should also be given to the nature of jobs, especially if the culture of a job penalises care work. Care responsibilities are not just about children, as women also often take primary responsibility for elderly relatives (Leahy and Doughney, 2014). Therefore, Leahy and Doughney (2014) argue that neither women nor men should be punished if they have family care responsibilities.

Despite its limitations, especially in its assumption of choice or free will, preference theory is useful in explaining the different types of work, family, paid or a combination of the two, that are open to women and deemed acceptable by society. It is also useful in that it acknowledges the importance of the family to women's working lives. This is especially relevant to the call centre industry, which offers part-time work at the customer service level. Having examined these four theories and their relevance to this thesis, the next section will explore call centres themselves.

2.8 Call centre research

It is argued that the call centre is an attractive research area as it's the world's fastest-expanding industry (Mabotja and Mkhomazi, 2024). At their inception, as early as 1977, call centre contact was by making and receiving telephone

calls (DTI, 2004). Technological advancements have facilitated the emergence of novel modes of customer interaction, including email, online chat, and social media platforms, among others, thus driving the evolution of call centres into broader contact centres (Saber et al. 2017). As a result of negative media attention, some organisations are differentiating their operations and have changed their title from call centre and contact centre to, for example, “customer satisfaction centre” or “customer service centre” (Taylor and Bain, 1999 p.111). However, for the purposes of this research, the term call centre will be used.

It is important to present some contextualisation of call centres in order to understand women in management in call centres. This section will review previous call centre research generally and from a gender perspective in particular. It will start by defining the term call centre. It will then analyse the call centre industry in terms of its inception. If the call centre is a new industry, it will have implications for gender inequality regimes.

2.8.1 Definition, use and work of call centres

The call centre sector, which has grown since 1990, provides a classic example of a new industry sector emerging in response to changing consumer needs and the development of integrated communication technology (ICT) (Dean, 2002). They are often the main point of contact for customers accessing organisations, and they have a key role to play in the overall perception customers have of the entire organisation (Dean, 2002). The call centre is explained by Taylor and Bain (1999) as a dedicated operation in which

employees use the computer, receive inbound calls, and make outbound calls; those calls are controlled and processed using an Automatic Call Distribution (ACD) system. This was the traditional approach in call centres. However, with the emergence of social media and its associated technology, call centres have evolved into contact centres. In addition to making and receiving calls, contact centre employees have other contact channels at their disposal, such as live web chat and email, as well as traditional methods such as letters. It is also important to point out that both call centres and contact centres have received bad media attention, and as a result, some organisations are differentiating their operations and have changed their title from call centre and contact centre to, for example, “customer satisfaction centre” or “customer service centre” (Taylor and Bain, 1999). However, for the purposes of this research, the term call centre will be used.

There is no universally accepted definition of the term “call centre”. As stated above, according to Taylor and Bain (1999), a call centre is a dedicated operation in which computer-utilising employees receive inbound or make outbound telephone calls, and the calls are processed and controlled by either an automatic call distribution (ACD) or predictive dialling system. Robinson and Morley (2006) identified the characteristics of a call centre as the integration of telephone and visual display unit technologies. Malhotra and Mukherjee (2004) explained that contact centres assist companies in communicating with their customers remotely via telephone. Prabhaker et al. (1997) illustrated that call centres allow a company to build, maintain, and manage customer relationships by solving problems and resolving complaints

quickly. According to Burgess and Connell (2004), contact centres play an important role in providing service to customers and have turned out to be a fundamental contact point for different companies, institutions, government and even more, they play a strategic role for the companies (Armistead *et al.*, 2002). Prabhaker *et al.* (1997) further added that call centres are the main point of contact for customers' queries in a company. The call centre's agents answer customer questions every hour of the day and all year round. It has been agreed by other researchers as well that call centres allow companies to maintain, manage and build customer relationships by resolving customers' complaints and issues quickly and, providing information and being available all the time (Mitchell, 1998). Perhaps the most succinct and inclusive definition is that of the International Call Centre Management Institute. It states that a call centre is a coordinated system of people, processes, technologies, and strategies that effectively integrates organisational resources and multiple channels of communication to enable customer interactions that create value for the customer and the organisation (Yaşlıoğlu *et al.*, 2013).

There are two distinct responses of companies moving to the use of call centres. Firstly, some organisations decentralise routine or back-office jobs in-house to keep them away from their core corporate business. Secondly, there is the feature of outsourcing or contracting this non-core business to a third party (Mabotja and Mkhomazi, 2024). Examples of the former are banks and insurance companies, while examples of the latter include utility and entertainment companies. It can, therefore, be argued that companies either

decided to keep their routine work in-house away from their core business or they would outsource that non-core business to a third party.

Voice-to-voice encounters are critical because the telephone can be the first interaction with a company. Consumers may call companies to find out more information or check prices before a transaction. This initial contact or pre-transaction stage with the firm can cause customers to do business with the firm or cause the customer to take their business elsewhere (Whiting and Donthu, 2006). Many organisations provide the main (or the only) customer interface for after-sales and supplementary service, information, complaint resolution, reservations, and ticketing (Anton, 2000; Whiting and Donthu, 2006). However, call centre jobs also generate high levels of psychological stress for employees, resulting in health impairment and demotivation (Rohrmann et al., 2011). It is also important to point out that it is difficult to compare call centre agents' jobs with the more historical jobs of industries, for example, such as, retail or banking, because the customer service roles are not the same (Collin-Jacques and Smith, 2005).

Collin-Jacques and Smith (2005, pp 5-6) contend that call centres are “a new technological and organisational field” with employees who are a “new generation” of industrialised “clerical” work without “occupational consciousness” to which they can relate their work historically and comparatively.

2.8.2 Historical development of the UK call centre industry

The beginning of the 20th century is said to be the start of a new age in communication. In 1876, a few decades earlier, the telephone had been invented, and the services provided over the telephone had grown quickly. Therefore, people's dependency on it expanded, and people started to expect a more reliable service from telephone companies (Adizes, 2003). Interestingly, the start of the call centre has been traced back to 1908. Primarily, telephone companies in the USA made it possible to use telephone services to sell advertisements through telephone guidebooks.

By the 1960s, the Ford Motor Company was looking to find potential buyers for their cars and made 20,000,000 phone calls to consumers (Norman, 2005). As stated by the Department for Trade and Industry (2004), call centres in the UK technically started in the 1970s and intensified their operations throughout this and the following decades. However, in the 1970s, companies constantly concentrated on outbound telemarketing, usually through cold calls. This process was very costly, and they were keen to find a way where prices could be reduced by providing customer services remotely. In 1984, British Telecom was deregulated and offered cheaper telephone costs, which helped to develop the call centre industry. Essentially, Direct Line (1985) and First Direct (1989) were the pioneer organisations that used call centres, with the former offering insurance and the latter banking.

The Department for Trade and Industry (2004) report indicates that there have been five different stages in the development of the UK call centre industry.

The first stage is termed “Proof of Concept (1990-1995)”. Fundamentally, this was during the late 1980s and early 1990s when larger organisations decided to open their call centre operations to save costs associated with sales and distribution channels (DTI, 2004).

The second stage has been termed the “Drive to Growth” in the years 1995-2000 (DTI, 2004). Fundamentally, during this period, the UK call centre industry development was enhanced because of multiple reasons, including the increase in demand for customer services, the increase in demand for retail channels, and consequently, contact channels for existing and new customers. Henceforth, the development of technology led organisations towards integration. For example, ACD and computer telephone integration have allowed companies to save huge amounts of money (DTI, 2004). In fact, during this period of time, further deregulation of the telecommunication, financial services and utilities industries occurred. A few of the sectors aimed to minimise expenses further by setting up international operations.

The third stage is called the “Increase in Outsourcing” (DTI, 2004) and took place in the years 1998-2001. During this stage, faster, cheaper, and more effective professionalisation of customer service roles became evident. The fourth stage is known as the “Rise of Offshoring” in the years 2000-2003 (DTI, 2004). This phase started around 2001 when UK companies started offshoring their call centres, especially with lower salaries in these offshore countries. The fifth state is said to have begun in 2005 and is termed “Automation and

high-value work” (DTI, 2004). However, in the past decade, some call centres have begun to relocate back to the UK due to customer discontent.

Since the mid-1990s, call centres have provided the most dynamic area of growth in white-collar employment internationally (Taylor and Bain, 1999). The call centre industry has expanded not only in developed economies such as the USA, Australia, Germany, the UK, Sweden, and Greece but also in developing economies. The expansion is also noticeable in India, South Korea, and other developing countries (John and Connell, 2017).

Meanwhile, the global economy has been positively affected by the frequent growth in the development of call centres. In the historical context, factory jobs were the main symbol of work in the industrial nations. However, those jobs have now been replaced by call centres and customer services in the forms of employment such as retail, cleaning, care, and food services (Brophy, 2011). Thus, since the 1970s, the transformation of the economy has brought growth in the communication development workforce, with the emergence of call centres playing a central role in the more recent economy (Brophy, 2011).

Holman et al. (2007) highlighted research covering 2500 call centres in 17 different countries, which demonstrated that the industries use call centres as a primary linkage between customers and service providers. These industries include airlines, hotels, retail banks, public security, postal services, telecommunications, insurance, electricity, banking, traffic control, securities, community, shopping, IT, the TV industry, and credit card companies.

Workman and Bommer (2004) In many countries, call centres are a growing part of the service industry and play an important role in the service sector.

In addition, call centres operate internationally. According to Holman et al. (2007), the call centre sector has developed globally at the same time as locally, in around five to ten years. Primarily, it provides customer service to clients of almost every industry sector. Further, it offers widespread services. Fundamentally, this sector has provided a crucial source of employment. Moreover, the flexibility in the operation of the call centre sector is typical for service work globalisation. Holman (2007) also points out that call centres operationalised in quite similar ways in terms of their service offerings, basically being built up as per the target market and organisational features.

Moreover, about 80 per cent of call centres internationally perform their operations in-house, meaning that companies' operations are based on their premises. In this environment, employees provide better customer service as they have greater knowledge of the product. The in-house call centre provides employees with training to achieve better quality. However, multiple organisations use outsourced call centres, providing more flexibility and innovative technologies (Consulting, 2019).

Contact-centres.com (2024) surveyed the trend in call centres and found this has changed over time, pointing out that about 80 per cent of call centres internationally perform their operations in-house, meaning that companies' operations are based on their premises. This recent survey of the industry during the summer of 2024 also revealed that voice remains the primary

medium for customer interactions. The data indicates that 67.6% of customer contacts are conducted via voice channels, encompassing both inbound and outbound calls. However, the survey also highlighted an intriguing trend shift; while inbound calls have experienced a slight decline, dropping from 55.4% to 53.1%, outbound calls have risen, growing from 12.7% to 14.5%. This suggests that call centres are doing more outbound calls. Some of the reasons for that presented in the survey are that companies offer callbacks at peak times to offer better customer service, and the AI chat box answers straightforward inquiries, so companies make outbound calls for complex inquiries. The next section sets out the structure of the thesis.

2.8.3 Call centres and limited career progression for women

Women continue to enter employment in increased numbers in developed countries. There have been many factors which contributed to this trend. Firstly, the industrialisation of the economy; secondly, the service sector progress, which provided more opportunities for women; and thirdly, the growth of the nonprofit and public sectors has created new opportunities for women. Finally, this trend is supported by a change in attitude towards working women, especially toward women with children, as well as legal and political initiatives supporting it too (Davidson and Burke, 2011). However, the rate of progress for women professionals and managers continues to be uneven and slow in different cultures and countries. It is also argued that career progress is limited for women in call centres, which contributes to a glass ceiling where

women enter the industry easily; however, they will find barriers to progressing into senior and decision-making roles (Barreto, Ryan and Schmitt, 2009).

The gendered background of call centre employment can be traced back to the emergence of telephone switchboard operators. They were often referred to as 'hello girls' (Frahm, 2004). Women were hired as switchboard operators because of their patience and ability to communicate, and young women were thought to possess these skills naturally. Similarly, women continued to be recruited for call centre jobs because of those gendered-related skills. As a result, women's over-recruitment in the call centre workforce reflects broader beliefs based on established skills and abilities.

As already stated, call centres have emerged as a new service industry. New and modern organisations are often assumed to be not just gender neutral but class, sexual orientation, race, age and ability neutral. However, Acker (1990, 2006) and Connell (2006) argue that their underlying inequality regimes recreate hierarchical power relations and patterns of idealised workers, femininities, masculinities, and other socially constructed identities. In terms of call centres, it is important to question if call centres are actually new industries and if modern industries are gender neutral or if different underlying inequality regimes have recreated hierarchical power relations.

Even though call centres create opportunities for women and others in terms of getting a job, the circumstances that create women's careers are less encouraging given the flat organisation structure and the flexible characteristics of the work, which result in providing little room for promotion

and career advancement (Batt, Doellgast and Kwon, 2004). This is in contradiction to the view that call centres are a new industry and suggests that there is a gender inequality regime in call centres.

According to (Hultgreen, 2018), 71 per cent of the global call centre industry are women. Call centres are named 'female-friendly workplaces. Women are significantly overrepresented in call centres. Women in the call centre industry are mostly working in customer service roles. Fewer women make it to executive roles, only 48 per cent. Some of the reasons presented by (Vincent, 2022) are that women are associated with family than with business, with emotion over competence, and with compliance instead of achievement. It is added that women will sacrifice going ahead in order to be liked. It is important, therefore, to explore women's employment and representation in the call centre.

This section reviewed the call centre literature generally and from a gender perspective. It began by locating the gendered construction of telephone work and the discussion of women and technology and moved on to the flat organisation structure. The following section will explore the flexible feminised work of the call centre, the labour market pattern, and women's representation in the call centre.

The second feature of this industry is the use of technology, which is one of the main characteristics that differentiate call centres from other organisations. Call centres have adopted the use of information technology to organise, control, and monitor their work. Automated call distribution (ACD) enabled call

centres to set the context and pace of work while generating real-time statistical information on call centre activities. Another feature of the call centre is that it follows a systematic and clear approach and does mean any employee can deal with any customer as businesses shift away from the person-specific approach. This is also enabled by the technology that call centres have a centralised storage of both products and customer information on interactive databases (Houlihan,2001). This centralised function of the call centres has provided strategic importance compared to previously secondary back-office functions, and this innovation marked call centres as a distinctive work organisation that could be characterised as a unique hybrid of clerical/ office and interactive service work (Boreham et al., 2008).

Call centres, in terms of the nature of the company, are inbound and outsourced. The call centre is differentiated in terms of the decentralised, portable structure of the industry. The call centre work is more interactive and performative, and the industry is associated with globalisation, resulting in a new industry of outsourcing (Wajcman, 1991; Larner, 2001). A new kind of work has emerged in terms of outsourcing the call centre industry. Globally, the restructuring of production and capital has been facilitated by new technologies and has resulted in the flattening of organisational hierarchies. It can be argued that technology has supported the emergence of a flat organisation structure. A flat organisational structure means the reduction and reorganisation of responsibilities and tasks. In this structure, work is organised based on teams, and the organisation uses different methods to increase flexibility. This structure is the same across the industry, so it is essential to

examine if the structure supports or reduces gender inequality (Jenson, 1989; Smith, 1993).

2.8.4 Domestic responsibilities, marital status and motherhood

The gendered ideology of 'separate spheres' of femininity and masculinity emerge in North America and Europe from the 18th century onward (Crompton, 2001, p. 267). This brought to attention the separation of private and public life, 'work' as employment and compared to domestic life (Crompton, 2001, p. 267). Gender literature on call centres has highlighted women's role in the household and hours spent on domestic responsibilities; however, the suggestions are usually theoretical. As a result, the influence of these issues remains unincorporated (Scholarios and Taylor, 2011), and therefore, this study, which focuses on women in management in call centres, from first-line management to the top of the organisation's management, will consider these issues.

Women with children's responsibilities were discussed in the research by Belt (2002) that showed how call centres preferably recruit women returning to work after a career break to look after their children. The study by Belt (2002 p.54) found that call centres intentionally attempt to target these women during the recruitment process, with one manager stating that he termed these women a 'female underclass that are mainly working-class women with childcare responsibilities, usually at the bottom of the career ladder". Belt further suggests that this approach is consistent with the work of Crompton and Harris (1998). Table 2.1 below sets out full-time and part-time employment

in call centres by gender in the UK. It is important to point out that this only relates to employment in outsourcing call centres.

Table 2.1 All call centre employment status by Occupation and Sex, full-time/part-time and male/female -April 2008-June 2011

	April-June 2008		April-June 2009		April- June 2010		April- June 2011	
	000s	%	000s	%	000s	%	000s	%
All employed	97		84		100		107	
All employed Full time	68	70%	61	73%	64	64%	84	79%
All employed Part-time	28	29%	23	27%	36	36%	23	21%
Males Employed full time	30	31%	28	33%	30	30%	42	39%
Males Employed Part-time	*	*	11	13%	12	12%	4	4%
Females Employed full time	38	39%	33	39%	34	34%	42	39%
Females Employed Part-time	22	34%	12	14%	24	24%	19	18%

Source: ONS (2011)

As can be seen from Table 2.3, in 2011, 79% of call centre employees were full-time, and 21% were part-time. The percentage of males and females employed full-time was identical at 39%. However, males constituted only 4% of part-time employees, compared to 18% of females.

2.8.5 Women, call centres and the labour market

This thesis focuses on women in management in call centres; therefore, it is important to establish the number of people, specifically women, working in call centres. In inshore and offshore, the call centre industry depends on women's employment. According to (Batt, Doellgast and Kwon, 2004), women comprise 73 per cent of the workforce. The women's work in the call centre has been presented in Table 2.2, which shows the UK's total number of agents and operators from 2004 to 2018 by gender.

Table 2.2 Call centre agents and operators by gender in the UK

Call centre agents and operators by gender					
	Male		Female		Total
April to June	000s	%	000s	%	000s
2004	31	33	62	67	93
2005	37	42	51	58	88
2006	44	39	67	60	112
2007	36	35	68	65	104
2008	37	39	59	61	96
2009	39	46	46	55	84
2010	42	41	58	58	100
2011	46	43	61	57	107
2012	41	40	62	60	103
2013	45	42	60	57	106
2014	52	46	61	54	114
2015	56	48	60	52	116
2016	57	48	62	52	119
2017	53	48	59	53	111
2018	43	37	72	63	115

Source: (CfA Business Skills @ Work, 2012) and (ONS, 2012-2018)

From Table 2.1, it can be observed that there is a higher number of females employed in call centres. It is broadly believed that there is a high proportion

of women in call centre employment, and the figures above support this theory. A report from Data Vantage (2004) has found similar results, stating that 63 per cent of agents employed in in-house call centres are women. However, as can be seen in Table 2.1, over this period, the percentage of females in call centres has been declining, while the percentage of males has been increasing, though in 2018, this reversed, and the gap widened again. Batt et al. (2004) acknowledge that across the industry, women are concentrated in lower-pay call centre jobs.

CfA Business Skills @ Work (2012) states that there is limited data available on the gender distribution of jobs in call centres. It is important to point out that there are problems in obtaining data on call centre employment. For example, the data in Table 2.1 comes from the UK government's Labour Force Survey. However, as CfA Business Skills @ Work 2012) points out, this data only covers employees working in outsourcing call centres, not in-house call centres, such as those in banking and insurance. In terms of government statistics, the latter would be classed as financial services employees. Besides, most call centre employees can also be classified as customer service employees, as set out in Table 2.2. According to the UK's Office of National Statistics survey, 60% of females are employed in customer service overall. This broadly mirrors the number of females in call centre employment. It is also worth pointing out that the percentage of females in Scotland is slightly higher (62%) than that of the UK as a whole.

Table 2.3 All Customer Service Employment Male/Female Analysis by UK Countries July 2010-June 2011

Sub major: customer service occupations	United Kingdom		England		Wales		Scotland		Northern Ireland	
	Number	%	Number	%	Number	%	Number	%	Number	%
All employed	568,300		470,700		28,000		56,800		12,900	
Male	229,100	40%	188,700	40%	12,300	44%	21,800	38%	6,300	49%
Female	339,200	60%	281,900	60%	15,700	56%	35,000	62%	6,600	51%

Source: ONS annual population survey- online workplace analysis (NOMIS,2012)

The labour force in the call centres is mainly female, with more women working at the service level in the call centre (Hunt, 2004). In the UK, the call centre industry is a major employer. In 2018, there were more than 6,200 call centres, and they employed more than 4% of the country's working population, and the number of people employed is increasing annually (Ismail, 2017). It has been claimed that call centres are responsible for approximately 70 per cent of all contact between companies and their customers (Cheong et al., 2008). It can be concluded that the call centre industry in the UK and across the globe has expanded as more businesses need to extend their support and interaction with customers. The previous section looked at the literature on call centres. The next section will explore the culture of the call centre in relation to gender.

2.8.6 Culture of the call centre in relation to gender

Organisational culture is one of the components of leadership that leaders use to develop a dynamic organisation (Boniface, 2011). Historically, scholars have used various definitions to describe an organisation's culture (Sun, 2009). One of the popular definitions of organisational culture is that of Schein (1987, p. 383), who stated that organisational culture is the “pattern of basic assumptions which a given group has invented, discovered or developed in learning to cope with its problems of external adaptation and internal integration, which have worked well enough to be considered valid, and therefore to be taught to new members as the correct way to perceive, think and feel in relation to those problems . . . it is the assumptions which lie behind values and which determine the behaviour patterns and the visible artefacts such as architecture, office layout, dress codes, and so on”.

Bellot (2011, p.30) draws from the work of scholars Mats Alvesson, Edgar Schein and Benjamin Schneider's views on organisational culture (Martin and Siehl, 1983; Druckman et al., 1997). Firstly, they all agreed that organisational culture exists. Even though it appears simple, however, it took years of research and theories to find out that organisational culture exists. Secondly, organisational culture is fundamentally ‘fuzzy’ in that it includes paradoxes, contradictions, confusion, and ambiguities. Organisation culture is not a “surface” phenomenon. Instead, it is “infused with symbols and symbolism” (Druckman e, 1997, p. 69), and usually, it is undetectable (Cameron and Quinn, 1999). As defined by Druckman et al. (1997), organisation culture

is infused with symbols and symbolic gestures and will reinforce the brand value will motivate call centre advisors and will reinforce behaviours. This confusion and lack of clarity led to a detailed evaluation of the cultural concept. Thirdly, the theme of organisational culture is socially structured and is related to groups. It is based on shared experiences. It is not a produced individual assumption regarding the culture of an organisation that differentiates it from other constructs. It is the group nature of the concept. Finally, every organisation's culture is flexible, unique and can be changed. However, Smircich (1983) argues that changing culture depends on whether culture is something that an organisation 'has' or something that an organisation 'is'. Initially, it was argued by scholars that organisations were cultured in themselves (Rousseau, 1990. Bellot (2011) further added that organisational culture is a property that an organisation possesses. When an organisation possesses a culture, that means that it can be controlled, at least influenced and eventually, it can be changed by the members of the organisation. Culture is developed over time; it is not a static property, and there is a contention that organisational culture is distinct. However, some of the approaches to culture have shown that culture can be separated into broad categories. The belief that culture is malleable has attracted more attention from managers in organisations. Those who support the theory believe that melding an organisation's culture in an ideal form will improve organisational performance. Supporting Bellot (2011), Boniface(2011) added that the organisation's senior leaders are the main source in creating and reinforcing the organisation's ideology, norms and articulation of the core values. Usually, the main value of

an organisation is a preference for certain behaviours and results. The norms in an organisation communicate behaviour which is accepted by others. They are acceptable ways of achieving cultural goals. The leaders of an organisation set out the boundaries of formal communication and interaction. Once an organisation communicates its norms and values, it is established and permanent in its culture. Therefore, leaders in organisations must always operate from the foundation of high ethical and moral discipline.

A study by Elacqua et al. (2009) presented that a further investigation of factors that affect the perception of treating women differently could be the culture that is implemented in the organisation. It explained that the culture of an organisation is shared values and beliefs that mirror employees' judgement of how things should be and really are (Lord and Maher, 1991).

A global report by Deloitte (2016) found that CEOs are focused on understanding and creating a shared culture and that culture has become one of the most important business topics in 2016. They added that CEOs now recognise that culture drives innovation, customer service and people's behaviours. In that report, 82 per cent of the survey respondents believed that culture could provide an organisational potential competitive advantage. They argued that culture is a business issue, not an HR issue and that the CEOs in the organisations should take responsibility for the culture of an organisation. Even though it is considered important, it is still not well understood. And many organisations find it difficult to manage it. Only 28 per cent of survey

respondents understand their culture well, and 19 per cent believe they have the right culture in their organisation.

The importance of the call centre culture is described by Gait (2010) as a “state where people are proud to come to work and deal with customers”. The consequence of a bad culture is when the employees don’t look forward to coming to work. Even though it is difficult to see what is lacking or not lacking in an organisation's culture, it is easy to know what is not right about the culture of an organisation. The culture of a call centre has a negative impact on the reputation of the call centre, as well as its customer service and bottom-line customer service. It can be concluded that call centre culture is important as it improves productivity. The next section will discuss frameworks that attempt to explain women’s under-representation in management, starting with Connell’s gender regime. It will then discuss Acker’s inequality regime and McDonald’s gender inequality regime.

2.9 The Theoretical Frameworks of the Research

There are different frameworks for understanding gender inequality regimes (Duberley *et al.*, 2017). Firstly, using Connell’s framework of gender regimes and Acker's framework of inequality regimes, this thesis examines the process and practices of gender inequality in Scottish call centres. It highlights the nature of discrimination in call centres and how this is experienced by the managers who progress to middle and senior management positions. According to Price (2008), Acker and Connell’s frameworks provide valuable insight into understanding inequality regimes and gendered organisations.

The roots of Acker's framework are feminist and gendered organisational theory. Acker's framework emphasises how organisations reproduce gender divisions, power distributions and inequalities favouring masculine practices (Bates, 2022). Connell's theory of gender regimes complements this by highlighting dimensions such as power relations, gender division of labour, cultural symbolism and emotional aspects in organisations (Duberley *et al.*, 2017). McDonald (2015) combines both these frameworks in what she terms 'gender inequality regimes', a term used in this thesis also and adds two additional elements marital status and motherhood. This section establishes the groundwork and context for the remaining work. The theoretical framework introduced here will be revisited in subsequent chapters to maintain a cohesive narrative throughout the thesis. The following section will examine the gender regime approach Connell (2006) and discuss the inequality regime (Acker, 2012c) and McDonald's (2015) gender inequality regime - theoretical frameworks relevant to and employed in this research. These three frameworks will now be discussed in Sections 2.9.1, 2.9.2 and 2.9.3.

2.9.1 Gender Regime Approach

Connell (2006, p. 839, emphasis in original) puts forward a conceptual framework to explain the glass ceiling and terms this a gender regime which, she argues, describes the "overall pattern of gender relations within an organisation". She argues that a gender regime has four dimensions: gender division of labour, both in the workplace and the home; gender relations of power, in the workplace, the home, and society; emotion and human relations,

amongst people and groups; and gender culture and symbolism, including language and attitudes, that define gender relations. These dimensions, she contends, can be used to uncover an organisation's gender regime.

Connell (2006) argues that there are several aspects to each dimension. In terms of the gender division of labour, she notes that it is important to establish whether this is historical or due to technological change. This aspect may well apply to call centres as call centres came into existence due to new technology. This allowed companies to provide new services and opportunities for organisations to create new avenues of profit (Schumann et al., 2012). This dimension is similarly emphasised by Adriaanse and Claringbould (2016), who analysed how sports organisations assign roles and responsibilities, revealing a consistent disparity that favours male leadership participation. In the context of call centres, this gender division pertains to the roles and tasks allocated to women and men in call centre management and senior management.

In terms of power and gender, she includes the problems women face in "establishing...[their]...authority" (Connell, 2006, p. 846). Many of the issues identified earlier, for example stereotyping, fall into this dimension. In the context of call centres, this aspect highlights men's dominance and influence in decision-making and how they promote their interests throughout the process. The third dimension, emotion and human relations, she argues, are impacted by occupational segregation and changes to occupational segregation. Emotional relations in call centres relate to the pattern of attachment and hostility that exists between men and women. In this thesis,

Connell's emotions and human relations, the third dimension, were used to refer to the ways in which attachment and opposition between people are organised along gender lines. Connell insisted that emotional connections are an important dimension of the gender regime. This also encompassed "emotions of gender transition" (Connell, 2006, p. 843). Gender transition refers to the gendered attitudes and behaviours that arise as horizontal and vertical segregation change the gender makeup of parts of the workforce. For example, in call centres where restructuring has disrupted the older, male-dominated culture, in the case of this study, the entry women in the ICT department of the call centre. Sexual harassment in call centres can also be explored under these headings. This looks at the emotional conflict in terms of the anti-discrimination and harassment roles and procedures.

Finally, she argues that the fourth dimension, gender culture and symbolism, is not gender neutral. When examining the dynamics of gender within call centres, it is essential to recognise how symbolic relations manifest in perceptions of gender and the underlying issues of gender inequality. This encompasses a range of beliefs and attitudes surrounding gender parity, particularly in relation to leadership roles and equality within management structures. Under this headline, call centres' ingrained notions about the suitability of genders for specific roles, impacting their hiring practices and promotion opportunities, will be discussed. This can lead to disparities in the representation of women and men in leadership positions. Overall, understanding how these symbolic relations operate provides a fuller picture of the challenges and opportunities facing gender dynamics in call centres, as

well as the potential paths towards achieving true equality in the workplace. Adriaanse and Claringbould (2016) pointed out that these four structures of gender relations can be distinguished, yet they do not function independently; rather, they are interwoven and continually interact with one another. These four Connell's interrelated dimensions of gender, which are discussed above, have been highlighted in the diagram below:

Figure 2.2 *Connell's Gender Regime*

Source: Author

2.9.2 Inequality Regime Approach

Acker suggests a much-required framework and, through her framework, argues that the gendering of organisations, both visible and invisible, can be understood (Parsons et al., 2012). According to Martin and Collinson (2002), Joan Acker's (1990) paper marked the birth of gendered organisations. Her approach highlights the processes in organisations, the gendered norms about men and women, and masculinity and femininity, and how these are repeated and rooted and, in turn, enable the continuation of gender inequality (Acker, 2012). She contends that her framework can be used to analyse organisations in order to find out the reasons why organisations are structured in such a way that women often work as subordinates (Acker, 1990). Acker (2006) explained that a systematic gender theory is needed for several reasons. Firstly, the

gendered segregation of work, which includes the divide between paid work and unpaid work, is partially created through the organisation's practices. Secondly, status and income inequality among men and women is also created partially in the organisation's processes; therefore, it is essential to understand these processes in order to better recognise gender inequality. Thirdly, the organisation is an area where you can find different cultural images of gender, created and reinvented. Fourthly, the characteristics of individual gender identity and specific masculinity are produced in the organisational processes and practices. Finally, an important feminist project is to make large-scale organisations more democratic and supportive of human goals. Acker (1990) further elaborated that gendering happens in an organisation in at least five interacting processes. Subsequently, four processes (Acker, 2004), and this process recreates gendered organisations. The five points outlined represent key components of the conceptual framework presented in Table 2.4.

Firstly, the divisions of labour; it is important to understand gender division to find out differences in frequency. She further added that there is also variation in the pattern and extent of the gender division. Men occupy higher positions in the organisation's power, and managers' decisions usually initiate gender divisions and practices, and organisations maintain them.

The second process is constructing the images and symbols that express, reinforce, and sometimes disagree with those divisions. The construction of images happens in many forms, for example, through media, languages, and

popular cultures. An example of this will be linking men's image of masculinity and their gender with technical skills.

Thirdly, the gender social structure that produces gender inequality is the interaction between women and men that creates inequalities.

Fourthly, internal individual identity means people create gender-appropriate behaviours in the organisation in which they are working. Finally, she added that gender is a well-defined element in the organisation's logic. It sees gender as neutral but has an underlying sub-structure that is gendered. The substructure is reproduced in the daily work of the organisations. She added that organisational logic assumes, for example, that lower-level positions in an organisation are mainly filled by women. This observation is relative to this study as women mostly work as a lower-level customer advisors in call centres. Acker (1990) discussed five sets of processes, but later, Acker (1992) highlighted four sets of processes and dropped the fifth set of gender processes, which is the organisational logic and renamed it as the gendered "substructure of the organisation" (Acker, 1992, p.259). Kantola (2008, p.223) pointed out that the fifth process was a "larger theoretical rather than analytical point" and that the four other dimensions contributed to the gendered organisation logic. In this thesis, it is referred to as organisation sub-structure. It is further added that the order in which each process is used does not signify any form of hierarchical importance in Acker's work. In this study, all five gendered processes will be discussed in terms of the gendered processes in call centres.

Figure 2.3 Gendered processes within organisations

Source: Author

It is important to point out that Acker (2006b, p. 443) acknowledges that gender is only one of what she terms “the bases of inequality”, the others being ethnicity, race, age, sexual orientation, disability, class, race and religion. These, of course, are similar to the ‘protected characteristics set out in the UK’s Equality Act 2010, which are age, disability, gender reassignment, marriage and civil partnership, pregnancy and maternity, race, religion or belief, sex, and sexual orientation. People can be discriminated against on more than one characteristic.

Acker (2006b p.443) contends that all organisations have inequality regimes, which she defines as “interrelated practices, processes, actions and meanings

that result in and maintain...gender...inequalities within particular organisations". She defines inequality as "systematic disparities between participants in power and control over goals, resources and outcomes; workplace decisions such as how to organise work, opportunities for promotion and interesting work; security in employment and benefits; pay and other monetary rewards; respect; and pleasures in work and work relations". Acker further points out that these disparities can vary between organisations and are "fluid" and can change. Acker (2006, p.444) argues that inequality regimes have certain characteristics, namely "the bases of inequality, the shape and degree of inequality, organising processes that create and recreate inequalities, the invisibility of inequalities, the legitimacy of inequalities and the controls that prevent protest against inequalities".

Nkomo and Rodriguez (2019) pointed out that Acker has developed the most insightful framework in the field of gender and organisation. Initially, in her framework, she focussed on the gender sub-structure in an organisation's life (Acker, 1990, 1992). Acker's (1990) article provides a robust analytical tool for disputing the concept that organisations are gender neutral. Her theory of the gendered organisation and the concept of the inequality regime were found to be the most influential theories and are frequently used in the field of management and organisation studies (MOS) (Nkomo and Rodriguez, 2019).

During the 1990s, organisations were becoming more gendered. Ackers' theories, both 'Hierarchies, Jobs, Bodies: A Theory of Gendered Organisations' (1990) and 'Gendering Organizational Theory' (1992), were

published. These articles played a crucial role in uncovering the process of a gendered organisation. Her later article, 'The Gender Regime of Swedish Banks,' highlighted how the process of older gender discrimination had been reinvented with the assistance of new work orders and new technologies (Czarniawska, 2019).

Acker has developed her framework from insight into the scholarly work of other writers, including earlier socialist feminist and Marxist feminist debates, to the postcolonial feminist debate from the 21st century (Acker, 2006a). Besides that, she used her research on women returning to work: a comparable worth project in Oregon, women's gender and class (Acker, 1989). Her work began in 1987, and then she built on them in the 1980s. Some of the other studies included the study of female bank workers in Sweden (Acker, 2006b) and the study of organisational restructuring in late 1990. As she called it, an abstract discussion has also informed her framework (Acker, 2006a).

Some other areas of Acker's research, for example, her book focuses mainly on the racialised and gendered nature of globalisation and capitalism (Acker, 2006). According to Nkomo and Rodriguez (2019), this has not been picked up comprehensively in discussions except for the work of Frenkel (2008) and Metcalfe and Woodhams (2012). Some other work she has done is in the field. For example, the sex structuring of the organisation was not that well-known. It was published in her earlier research (Acker, 1989). Using Acker's framework in this study will assist in both studying genders and exposing discriminatory practices in the call centre sector. Through this framework, a

multi-level analysis of the call centre will be done, and relevant information about the call centre's gendered practices, culture, the interaction between the employees and internal practices in the call centre will be uncovered.

2.9.3 Gender Inequality Regime (McDonald, 2015)

As detailed earlier, McDonald (2015) merged elements of Acker and Connell's frameworks and added marital status and motherhood as important factors, calling her framework the gender inequality regime to reflect her focus on women in management. It is this title that is used in this research, and the conceptual framework, which, though predominantly based on Acker's writing, includes some of McDonald's additions to Acker's framework as set out in table 2.4.

2.10 Conceptual Framework

This research has used Acker's (2012) Connell's (2006), and McDonald's (2015) sets of processes in order to focus on a broader set of gender processes in call centres. To answer the research questions, the researcher thought it was essential to use more sets of the process to fill the gap.

An inequality regime has interconnected dimensions (Acker, 2006a). Firstly, the bases of inequality include gender, race, and age. This research mainly focuses on the gender element of it. Secondly, the organising processes maintained inequalities such as hiring, job design, wage setting, and the expectation about performing your job based on undistracted role models of a worker who doesn't have any obligation outside of work. Horizontal and

vertical segregation of positions and jobs. Besides that, functional segregation based on gender is maintained through managerial positions.

Third and fourth are the visibility and legitimacy of inequality. Inequalities are legitimated by gender, and the images are racialised. For example, the image of a manager is that of a white man with specific characteristics. Fifth is the system of control that is embedded in bureaucratic rules. She added that controls are created and recreated in the daily interaction between employees in the organisation. Finally, competing interests and organising change, the change can come from an outside organisation or can come from inside, for example, managers. These dimensions are explained in the table below.

The conceptual framework for this research is set out below. It combines elements from the literature set out in Sections 2.9, 2.9.1, 2.9.2, 2.9.3

Firstly, the framework sets out the key features of gender inequality. The shape and degree of gender inequality are the visible parts of gender inequality in an organisation. Acker (2006b) points out that there are three visible elements to the shape and degree of inequality in an organisation, and these are its hierarchical structure, occupational segregation, and the pay gap. Acker (2006b:445) argues that “the steepness of [the] hierarchy” is important, with bureaucratic organisations having the steepest of hierarchies and with men more likely to hold their most senior positions. Flatter organisations with team structures provide women with more opportunities as they offer more “responsibilities and decision-making authority” (Acker, 2006b:445).

Call centres, of course, tend to have flat structures and are team-based. It is important to point out that Acker (2006b p.445) believes these opportunities are only available to women if they “function like men”. The second element is occupational segregation. Acker argues that while occupational segregation has reduced since the 1970s, it is still evident in organisations. This was discussed in Section 2.4.3. The pay gap is the third element in the shape and degree of inequality. This was discussed in Section 2.6.1, and Acker (2006b p.447) points out that, on average, a CEO in the United States in 2003 “earned 185 times the earnings of the average worker”. A report by the High Pay Centre and the CIPD in 2018 found that a UK CEO earns 133 times the pay of the average worker (The Guardian, 2019). Concern about the pay gap and occupational segregation at the most senior levels of organisations has resulted in certain UK firms now being required to publish information on the numbers of women on their boards and their organisational pay gaps. Connell (2002) also recognises the importance of the pay gap and occupational segregation, although he argues that what he terms the “gender division of labour” in the home should also be taken into account. McDonald (2015) adds two further factors, marital status and motherhood, as these influence women’s decisions about the amount and type of paid work they carry out.

Acker (2006b, 2009, 2012 p.219) contends that an organisation’s gender inequality regime can be understood by examining its “gendered sub-structure”, which “continually recreate[s] gender inequalities”. A key part of this sub-structure is an organisation’s organising processes and practices: the way in which the work is organised, often based on an ‘unencumbered white man’;

job evaluation; recruitment and selection; pay; supervision; and networks (Acker, 2006).

McDonald (2015) states that the elements that constitute and influence women's career paths are also part of this sub-structure. These have been identified by the research set out in Section 2.7.6 and include career paths, key assignments, recruitment and selection, filtering processes, performance standards, mentors, networking, social capital, and impression management.

The importance of stereotyping is set out in Section 2.4.3, and McDonald (2015) contends that it also forms part of the organisational sub-structure as it is used to reinforce occupational segregation. The final two parts of the organisational sub-structure are what Acker (2006) terms the degree of awareness of gender inequality and the legitimacy of gender inequality, both of which vary between organisations. Acker (2012) points out the importance of workplace interactions. Connell (2006) also acknowledges the importance of workplace interactions but develops this within a broader category of emotion and human relations. McDonald (2015) posits that using Connell's framework allows the exploration of the causes of these factors and the effects of workplace change. Finally, the importance of culture is recognised by Acker (2012) and Connell (2006), and both focus on its gendered nature and its different levels (Schein, 1984). The table below has brought together elements from Acker (2012), Connell (2006), and McDonald (2015). Table 2.4 below presents elements from Acker (2012); Connell (2006); McDonald (2015), which constitute the framework of this research.

Table 2.4 Gender inequality regime

<p>Acker:</p> <p>Key features of gender inequality</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ The shape and degree of gender inequality • Structure of the organisation • Occupational segregation (Vertical and horizontal segregation) • Pay gap • Marital status • Motherhood <p>Organisational Sub-structure</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Organising processes and practices • Organisational processes (Ideal worker) • Organisational interactions • Stereotyping • Organisational culture ➤ Systemic inequality and perceived legitimacy 	<p>Connell:</p> <p>Emotions of human relations</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Workplace behaviour and interactions • Gender transition
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Source: The Author (Acker, 2012; Connell, 2006; McDonald, 2015)

2.11 Conclusion

The literature review initially discussed gender and women in management, and it later moved on to discuss the call centre and gender discrimination in the call centre. This chapter established concepts about gender regimes in management and call centres. Gender is a complex concept yet to be clarified. There are numerous definitions of the term. Besides, multiple theories of gender add to the complexity of the issue. Through this chapter, the fundamental concepts, such as the pay gap, occupational segregation, and the glass ceiling, which are important to employees, are discussed. This chapter assists in the creation of the interview guide. It means the themes and concepts in the interview guide are derived from the literature review chapter.

It is essential to point out that by critically analysing the literature, the researcher developed the conceptual framework presented in Table 2.4 to explore call centres from gender perspectives. The researcher used sets of gender processes presented by Acker (1992, 2006, 2006b:445) and Connell recognised the importance of the pay gap and occupational segregation (2002), and McDonald (2015) added two additional factors, marital status and motherhood. These sets of processes assist the researcher in concentrating on the essential aspects of gender. The researcher chose to use Acker's, Connells's and McDonald's sets of processes to focus on a wider range of gender processes than by using a single one of them. Acker is one of the first to pull a framework together that encompasses the organisation and the woman. The literature on gender in management is disparate. Under the organisational structure approach, there is a range of research literature

concentrating on individual variables, for example, mentoring, and these individual variables can then be slotted into the appropriate parts of the framework. It can be observed from the literature review that there is a gap within the literature on gender in management in call centres.

Acker's framework is the overarching framework. It is complemented by Connell and McDonald's input. Gender discrimination is one of the most persistent issues in employment, and many studies have appeared documenting the patterns and trends of gender bias across various jobs (Gans et al., 2002). However, there is very little of this research on call centres (Russell, 2008). Besides little literature, there are several major difficulties manifested in these studies (Belt, 2002; Belt, Richardson and Webster, 2002; Durbin, 2017), not least that they are essentially descriptive accounts and, often based on selective qualitative data, frequently speculative in their conclusions.

It can be concluded that the study of gender in call centres is still in the earlier stages of research. There are different issues in terms of gender in the call centre. That call centre is a gendered workplace, as discussed in the literature. Besides that, in terms of career progression, there are limited opportunities for career progression due to the flat organisational structure. The customer service level of the management is mostly women. It is important to find out how much progress is available for women managers from one sector to another sector.

2.12 Research Question

The literature review has presented an overview of the concept of gender inequality regimes in the context of call centres in Scotland, as well as the theoretical perspectives on gender inequality. However, the examination of the gender regime has also raised several questions that may warrant further investigation:

This research seeks to answer the following questions based on the framework and literature.

Research question one (RQ1): What is the level of women's representation in managerial positions within call centres in Scotland?

Research question two (RQ2): What do managers think about factors that constitute gender inequality in their call centres?

Research question three (RQ3): What barriers do women face while progressing in call centre management, and how do they successfully navigate them?

Research question four (RQ4): What effective policies and strategies are available for call centres to reduce gender inequality?

This chapter has provided a critical review of the recent literature on gender regimes within call centres. The following chapter will explicate the methodology employed to address the research aim and objectives, as well as to bridge the identified gap in the existing literature.

As shown in Table 2.4 above, the themes discussed in the Literature Review directly inform the research questions posed. To effectively address these questions, an appropriate methodology and research design will be formulated, which will be detailed in the subsequent chapter.

Chapter 3 - Methodology

3.1 Introduction

Research can be defined as a “process that people undertake in a systematic way in order to find out things, thereby increasing their knowledge” (Saunders et al., 2016, p5). From this definition, it can be emphasised that research must be carried out systematically, and to do that, the researcher must understand the research methodology. Saunders et al. (2016) also argue that data should be collected and interpreted systematically and that the research has a clear aim. The aim of this chapter is to explain the research methodology used for this thesis. The chapter begins by setting out the research philosophy, which is interpretivism. It goes on to examine the research methodology, which is qualitative. It then explores the research setting, which is call centres in Scotland, after which it explains the choice of research methods, which are predominately qualitative, although some quantitative data, primarily from secondary sources, is also used. The sampling method used in this thesis was non-probability sampling. The purposive sampling strategy was adopted and was focused on women call centre team leaders, operation managers, operation directors and above. It sets out the approach taken to data analysis using NVivo. Finally, it concludes by discussing reflexivity, as well as access and ethical issues.

3.2 Research Philosophy

Research philosophy plays an essential role in any research as it is related to the development of knowledge and the nature of that knowledge (Saunders et al., 2009). There are many reasons that a researcher must understand research philosophy before exploring a specific field (Crossan, 2003). Easterby-Smith et al. (2010) present the following three reasons to highlight the importance of clarifying the research philosophy. Firstly, it will assist in clarifying the research design. This includes considering what evidence is needed and how it will be gathered and interpreted. Thus, it will provide the best answer to the research questions. Secondly, it will assist in clarifying the limitations of a specific approach. Finally, it can assist the researcher in creating or identifying a design that may be outside his or her experience.

Three popular philosophies are available for the researcher to take. They are positivism, critical realism, and interpretivism, and these will be discussed in the following three sections (Saunders et al, 2016).

3.2.1 Positivism

Positivism is a research framework that believes in applying the method of the natural sciences to the study of social reality (Bryman and Bell, 2011). Saunders et al., (2016, p.136) point out that positivism entails working with “causal relationships in your data to create law-like generalisations”. According to Easterby-Smith et al. (2008), positivism assumes that the researcher should be independent of what is being studied and what to choose for a study, and how to do the study should be determined by objective principles and not by

the researcher's beliefs and interests. As Veal (2018) discusses, positivism emerges from an epistemological position that uses the hypothetical-deductive model; this model uses the process of deduction, as shown in Figure 3.1 below, to test the predetermined hypothesis, using quantitative data, to establish causal laws.

Figure 3.1 The process of deduction

Source: (Bryman and Bell, 2011)

However, critics of positivism argue that people cannot be studied in the same way as objects, as people have free will (Holder, 2016). They also argue that the researcher is not independent of the subjects studied and that social scientists can never entirely separate themselves from their own values and beliefs (Ryan, 2018). Positivism has also been heavily criticised in terms of the study of women (Oakley, 1974). For these three reasons, positivism was rejected as a research philosophy.

3.2.2 Realism

Realism is mainly based on the assumptions of the scientific approach (Saunders, et al., 2016). Realism can be divided into two groups: direct realism and critical realism.

Direct realism emphasises that what you see is what you get (Saunders et al., 2012), meaning that the world is portrayed through the senses accurately. Criticisms similar to those levelled at positivism can be levelled at realism, and for this reason, it was rejected.

Critical realism is one of the most common forms of post-positivism. Trochim and Donnelly (2006:19) express the view that “a critical realist believes that there is a reality independent of a person’s thinking about it that science can study.”. Critical realism emphasises that images and sensations of the real world can deceive us and do not represent the real-world picture (Saunders et al. 2016). Critical realism introduces two steps to understanding the world: first, there is a sensation of the event that we observe; and second, there is mental processing going on sometime after the experience (Reed, 2005). Despite its acknowledgement of mental processing and its effects on perception, its similarities to positivism were the reason for the rejection of this philosophy.

3.2.3 Interpretivism

Interpretivism is usually used as an alternative to the positivist orthodoxy and is based “...upon the view that a strategy is required that respects the differences between people and the objects of the natural sciences and therefore requires the social scientist to grasp the subjective meaning of social action” (Bryman and Bell, 2003, p.16). This shows that this approach focuses on human beings and their way of making sense of and understanding their reality.

The study of phenomena in their natural environment is significant to the interpretivist philosophy, together with the acknowledgement that scientists cannot avoid affecting the phenomena they study. Interpretivists admit that there may be many explanations of reality (Hudson and Ozanne, 1988), but maintain that these interpretations are in themselves a part of the scientific

knowledge they are pursuing (Gray, 2017). In addition, an interpretive approach emphasises the importance of developing a deep understanding of complex topics in a suitable theoretical way (Andrade, 2009).

The aim of this research is to explore the ways in which gender inequality regimes influence the context of women in management in call centres in order to better inform organisational policies and practices on diversity and equality both in call centres and in wider contexts. This is complex in terms of the identification of the issues and their solution and fits with the interpretive approach of exploring reality in a social context (Hossain, 2011). Cavana et al, (2001, cited in Khan, 2014) also point out that the interpretive approach also emphasises the importance of analysing the interaction between the researcher and the respondents. The interpretivist tradition is adopted for this research as it is important to study gender inequality regimes in their natural environment to make sense of and to understand employees' views and involvement in management. Using this philosophy, the researcher will acquire a broader understanding of gender inequality regimes in call centre management in Scotland. Interpretive philosophy aligns well with this research. Using interpretivism, the researcher can emphasise understanding multiple relationships and individual interpretations. Having established the research philosophy, the next section will explain the research methodology.

3.3 Research Methodology

Qualitative methodology is firmly located in the interpretivist paradigm and as such, is a logical choice for the research methodology. Denzin and Lincoln

(2003, p.3) state that qualitative research “involves an interpretive, naturalistic approach to the world”. Denzin and Lincoln (2003, p3) define qualitative research as “a situated activity that locates the observer to the world. It consists of a set of interpretive material practices that make the world visible and then transforms it”. Accordingly, qualitative researchers display a wide range of interconnected interpretive practices (Denzin and Lincoln, 2011), always striving to better understand the subject matter at hand (Saunders et al., 2009). For them, each practice makes the world visible in a different way. Hence, they use multiple interpretive practices in any study (Schurink, 2003). According to Patton (2002), qualitative research attempts to understand the unique interactions in a situation. The purpose of understanding is not necessarily to predict what might occur but rather to understand in depth the characteristics of the situation and the meaning brought by participants, and what is happening to them at that moment (Bendassolli, 2013). This is important for this thesis which examines the characteristics of the gender inequality regimes in call centres and their meanings as seen by their women in management.

Miles and Huberman (1994, p10) argue that qualitative research is “fundamentally well-suited for locating the meanings people place on the events, processes and structures of their lives”. Qualitative research also has “unique strengths...for research that is exploratory or descriptive, that assumes the value of context and setting, and that searches for a deeper understanding of the participants’ lived experiences of the phenomenon” (Marshall and Wood, 1995). This, again, is particularly important as this research focuses on

women's perceptions of organisational factors that constitute gender inequality in call centres.

The advantages of qualitative research, as mentioned by Creswell (2015), are that qualitative research gives a detailed viewpoint, seizes the voice of the participants, permits the researcher to ask about experiences, is participant-centric, and appeals to the satisfaction of the participant. Creswell (2015) also adds that the disadvantages of qualitative research are that it cannot be generalised, generates soft data, can be used for many participants, and it reduces research expertise given that it majorly relies on the participants. In order to overcome the issue of generalisation, Darlington and Scott (2003, p. 18) highlighted that "If one considers the unit of attention as the phenomenon under investigation, rather than the number of individuals, then the sample is often much larger than first appears." Therefore, in this research, the number of contacts or interactions was definitely larger than the number of interviews conducted, which were seventeen.

3.4 Research Setting

The literature review demonstrated that call centres are a new business sector, and as such, they are also an essential part of economic activity in Scotland, although this sector of the Scottish economy has not received much attention (Taylor, 2020). Therefore, Scotland's call centres have been chosen as the research setting.

According to the UK government's survey of call centres (DTI, 2004), Scotland, the Northwest of England, and Yorkshire had the largest concentrations of call

centre employment in the UK. It is important to point out that locational decisions are taken at the corporate level of organisations, and most call centres choose outer regions of the UK to locate call centres. They became important for so many reasons, including the relatively lower cost of labour and the availability of customer service (Richardson and Marshall, 1996; Bristow et al., 2000). It is also important to note that a key factor in Scotland's favour was the level of education of its population.

Scotland has emerged as a global leader in the contact centre industry. Mirroring trends observed at the global and UK levels, the Scottish contact centre sector, which was established in the early 1990s, has experienced sustained growth since 1997. This expansion has been driven by the influx of numerous multinational companies and global outsourcing service providers (e.g., Sykes, Capita, CGI, Capgemini, IBM, Teleperformance, Serco, Webhelp) from around the world, who have chosen to set up their customer service operations in Scotland (SDI, 2013a, 2013b).

The Scottish contact centre industry has developed a robust infrastructure to support its operations. The Contact Centre Association (CCA), the UK's preeminent professional body for contact centres, is headquartered in Glasgow. The CCA sets industry best practices and quality standards, and provides support to its members, who employ one-third of the UK's contact centre workforce. In collaboration with UK service providers, the CCA organises training courses and workshop programmes. For instance, the CCA Training Accreditation is the standard in-house training scheme for employees

working in CCA-affiliated contact centres across the United Kingdom (CCA, 2024).

Call centres are present across the whole of Scotland but mainly in the Central Belt, where the majority of the population lives. Some of them are concentrated around certain areas of the Central Belt. For example, in 2012 in Glasgow, 12.2 per cent of Glasgow's working population was employed in call centres, or it is associate activities; subsequently, in West Lothian, it was 7.7 per cent, and in Greenock, it was 7.2 per cent in 2012. The report found that call centres are a major form of employment in many urban and rural areas in Scotland. It provides an essential form of new jobs to the community (Taylor, 2020).

3.5 Data Collection using interviews

Easterby-Smith et al. (2010b) believe that the main method to collect information from company managers or employees can be achieved through in-depth interviews. Through this, research can gain insight into the organisational and social realities of an organisation. In an in-depth interview, the researcher uncovers the perception, views and opinions of individuals or groups through the language they use.

The aim of using the qualitative interview is to gain an understanding of the issue from the interviewee's perspective, which includes not only their view but also why they have this viewpoint (Easterby-Smith et al., 2010). Qualitative interviews can be semi-structured or unstructured (Bryman, 2004) and both

semi-structured and unstructured are also referred to as in-depth interviews (Mason, 2002). This research uses a semi-structured interview method.

According to Easterby-Smith et al., (2010), the semi-structured interview method is beneficial when:

- It is important to understand the construct the interviewee uses as a basis for his or her belief about a situation or matter. In terms of this research, it will be helpful to understand managers' view of gender under-representation in management.
- The subject matter is commercially sensitive or highly confidential. In a semi-structured interview setting, the interviewee will feel comfortable to discuss and be truthful about the issue. Gender is a sensitive topic, and the semi-structured interview setting fits well with it.

Data collection consisted of semi-structured in-depth interviews, a method that fits with the interpretative nature of research (Qu and Dumay, 2011). An interview guide was used and is set out in Appendix 3. It was constructed initially from themes that were generated from the literature and later from the analysis of each of the interviews as they took place. Finally, secondary data on call centres was taken from reports, organisational documents and government department statistics and reports.

All contact and personal information used was kept confidential, as set out in Section 3.8 below. Interviews were audio recorded with the consent of participants for subsequent transcription.

3.5.1 Sampling

Sampling methods can be divided into two categories: probability and non-probability sampling (Saunders *et al.*, 2016). In probability sampling, which is used primarily in quantitative research, the chance of each case being selected from the target population is known. However, in non-probability sampling, which is used primarily in qualitative research, the probability of a subject being selected is unknown (Saunders *et al.*, 2016). This research adopts non-probability sampling for data gathering (Saunders *et al.*, 2016).

3.5.2 Non-probability sampling

Non-probability sampling tends to focus on small samples and looks to examine the real-life social context instead of making statistical inferences regarding the size of the population or sample (Wilson, 2014). It is a strategy that includes participants, settings, persons, or events deliberately chosen to obtain information that cannot be provided by other participants (Patton, 1990; Wilson, 2014). Non-probability sampling is based on judgement (Sharma, 2017) and provides rich data (Saunders *et al.*, 2016).

There are various non-probability sampling methods. The most common ones are purposive, quota, snowball, and convenience sampling (Saunders *et al.*, 2016). They are explained in Table 3.1 below:

Table 3.1 *Non-probability sampling methods*

Types of sampling	Selection strategy
Snowball sampling	The initial respondent is chosen from non-probability sampling, and additional respondents are recruited by information provided by the initial respondent (Silverman, 2022).
Purposive sampling	In this strategy, a case is chosen because it represents some feature or process in which the researcher is interested (Silverman, 2022).
Convenience sampling	In this strategy, each case is selected based on only including individuals that are available to participate in the research (Riveria, 2019).
Quota sampling	The researcher selects a proportionate sample with certain characteristics of the sample population based on easily identifiable variables (Riveria, 2019).

Purposive sampling was used to identify potential interviewees, which is usual in qualitative research (Holloway, 1997). This sampling process allows the researcher to choose a case because it illustrates “some feature or process in which the researcher is interested” (Silverman, 2022, p294). In this thesis, the researcher is interested in exploring the ways in which gender inequality regimes influence the context of women in management in call centres, focusing on managerial and senior managerial positions in call centres.

The researcher has worked in a number of call centres, so direct professional contacts and personal contacts were initially accessed. Additional participants were recruited via snowball sampling, which is often the case for qualitative research. At the end of each interview, the interviewee was asked if they could identify colleagues or contacts who might agree to take part in the research. The researcher was mindful of Silverman’s (2022) exhortation that researchers need to be really careful about the parameters of the population and choose

the sample case based on that. The researcher also took into advice the reminder of Saunders et al. (2012) that the strategy for selecting an interviewee for a purposive sample depends on the research questions and objectives.

It is necessary to provide a description of the terminology used in call centres regarding the hierarchical structure of management and the titles used for managers to avoid confusion. Usually, there are four levels of management in call centres. At the first level, there are team leaders who manage teams of customer service advisors, which are comprised of up to fifteen people. At this level, there are also Accredited Trainers, who not only train the Customer Service Advisors but also deputise as necessary for the Team Leaders. Four Team Leaders were interviewed. Team Leaders and Accredited Trainers are, in turn, managed by the second level of Operation Managers or Call Centre Managers. They are responsible for managing groups of Team Leaders. Each Operation Manager usually manages around four to five Team Leaders. Their responsibilities include meeting with the team leaders and communicating the objectives of the day to the Team Leaders. In this study, seven Operation Managers were interviewed. In a call centre of about 1200 employees, there are around four Operation Managers. Their contact with the Customer Service Advisors is different from site to site. The next level of managers interviewed was the Head of the Call Centre. They are responsible for leading call centre operations and improving customer service operations. Two interviewees held this role. Finally, the fourth level is Director and Executive, and four interviews were conducted with Directors and Executives.

Figure 3.2 Interviewee's Role in the Call Centre

Source: Author

Figure 3.2 details the level of each of the interviewees in the sample. The same themes were used in the interviews for all Manager respondents and for the Key Informants' interviews.

The study included interviews with two key informants - a male call centre manager and a female human resources expert in the call centre industry. The male manager's perspective provided an alternative viewpoint on gender dynamics and organisational culture, which helped to contextualise the challenges faced by women managers. This triangulation of findings from the primary participant interviews enhanced the nuanced understanding of the research topic (Maxwell and Ogden, 2006).

The female HR expert was selected for her specialised knowledge of the Scottish contact centre sector. Informants like her can offer valuable contextual

and background information, including insights into the industry's history, current trends, regulatory frameworks, and economic significance. This contextual data enriched the analysis of the women managers' lived experiences. The interviewee's name was coded as CM1 to CM15, and the Key Informants as K1 and K2 to protect their anonymity. Figures 3.3 and 3.4 provide examples of the usual job structure of an in-house and outsourced call centre.

Figure 3.3 Hierarchical Structure of In-House Call Centre

Figure 3.4 Hierarchical Structure of an Outsource Call Centre

Source: The Author

The purposive sampling strategy adopted was homogeneous sampling and focused on a particular subgroup, in the case of this research, women call centre team leaders, operations managers, operations directors and above. The homogeneous sampling method allows the researcher to explore minor differences in their views in greater depth (Saunders et al., 2012). The interviewees were all women managers at various levels within call centres. However, as call centre job titles do vary, it was important to discuss job characteristics with the participants to ensure they were of similar levels for each category.

When choosing the sample size, it is usually recommended to continue collecting the data until, by conducting additional interviews, no new data emerges or until the 'data saturation' is reached. Initially, the researcher

intended to conduct thirty interviews; however, saturation was achieved after conducting seventeen interviews, including two key informant interviews, with no new themes emerging at this point. Saunders et al. (2012) suggest a guideline for the sample size, which is set out in Table 3.2 below, and state that when conducting semi-structured/in-depth interviews, the minimum sample size should be between 5-25 interviewees; therefore, seventeen interviews are deemed sufficient.

Table 3.2 Minimum non-probability sample size

Nature of study	Minimum sample size
Semi-structured/in-depth interviews	5-25
Ethnographic	35-36
Grounded theory	20-35
Considering a homogenous population	4-12
Considering a heterogeneous population	12-30

Source: Developed by Saunders (2012)

It is important to point out that this research's data collection was conducted in December 2019 and February 2021 during the Coronavirus (COVID-19) pandemic lockdown. This posed a number of problems, as many of the interviewees were working from home during this time, and sometimes, arranging both the interviews and their timing was difficult.

The study adapted its data collection methods in response to the unprecedented context of the COVID-19 lockdown in Scotland. Originally

planned face-to-face interviews were transitioned to online video conferencing platforms. While this shift presented practical challenges, such as ensuring participant familiarity with the technology and maintaining interpersonal rapport in a virtual setting, it also offered benefits, such as enhanced accessibility for participants located across different geographical areas. Additionally, the research design acknowledged the pandemic's impact on the Scottish call centre industry, including changes to working practices and increased reliance on remote work. This facilitated an exploration of how these transformations specifically affected the experiences of women managers. The limitations of conducting research during a global health crisis, such as potential participant stress and the inability to undertake in-person observations, are also recognised.

Another consequence of COVID-19 was that no face-to-face interviews could take place, and all interviews were conducted using Zoom. According to Boland et al. (2022), COVID-19 created challenges for conducting qualitative research. The UK, like many other countries, went into lockdown, which in turn restricted face-to-face contact in order to control infections. Qualitative researchers showed an increased interest in using video conferencing as an alternative to face-to-face interviews (Tuttas, 2015; Archibald et al., 2019), and this researcher was no different. During the pandemic, the number of hardware and programmes increased. Zoom is a global video conferencing program that is widely used by firms and also by individuals for interpersonal communication (Zoom, 2022). The video element of video conference interaction is specifically important as it enables the researcher to respond and

see the non-verbal cues, as these are an important aspect of qualitative data gathering (Boland *et al.*, 2022). The researcher is comfortable using technology, and the interviewees were already familiar with the platform as all interviewees were using Zoom for their work. Zoom was also used in the key informant interviews.

One advantage of using Zoom as a tool for the interview is that it is cost-effective (Krouwel, Jolly and Greenfield, 2019). Zoom is also useful if the population is disparate and difficult to reach (Tuttas, 2015). Boland *et al.* (2022) highlight five areas that must be addressed in order to benefit from using video conferencing. Firstly, rapport must be established. This was done in a number of ways. As stated earlier, the researcher had known some of the interviewees through working in the call centre industry and here, it was easier to re-establish rapport. For all interviewees, the researcher was careful to start all Zoom calls at the agreed time and began each interview by introducing herself and explaining the purpose of the interview. The researcher also used appropriate verbal and non-verbal approaches to ensure the interviewee was comfortable.

Secondly, the researcher must be aware of possible technological issues that can arise. As a result, Zoom Premium was purchased by the researcher for a number of reasons, one of which was to ensure that interviews could last longer than one hour if the interviewee so wished, which was the case in all interviews. In addition, a laptop was used, instead of a phone, to ensure greater battery and general reliability. It is important to point out that all

interviewees were very comfortable using Zoom as this was the main platform they were using for work during the lockdown. Thirdly planning was important. The information sheet and consent form were sent in advance to the interviewees and if they required more information, that was discussed with them prior to the interview. Fourthly, ensuring the privacy of the interviewee is vital when using Zoom. Each interviewee had to give consent to the recording, and Zoom also uses a facility for consent to be given before any recording of the interview can begin. As is normal practice in qualitative interviewing, the interviewee was advised that they could withdraw consent at any time during the interview or afterwards. No interviewee withdrew consent at any stage. Each interviewee was notified by the researcher and by Zoom when the recording began. For the Zoom account, the researcher used her student email address to build trust in the interviewer and to give greater confidence to the interviewees. Finally, in terms of equity, all interviewees already had access to Zoom, to the internet and to computers and so the researcher was not required to provide any technology.

3.5.3 Information about the interviewees

This section provides information about the interviewees in terms of their type of call centre. It also provides information about their characteristics.

The respondent's job sector was coded under Outsourcer, In-house, In-house bank, and In-house travel. The respondent's job titles have been added to differentiate the findings in terms of each respondent and to present their quotes.

The data was collected from seventeen interviews; ten respondents worked in in-house call centres, and seven worked in outsourced call centres. The details of the respondents who worked in in-house call centres are explained below in Table 3.3 and for outsourced call centres in Table 3.4. The number of call centres is higher than the number of respondents as some managers have worked in more than one call centre in their careers. Therefore, a code is generated for each call centre a respondent has worked in.

Table 3.3 Information about the In-House Call Centres

Name of the call centre	Information about the In-house call centre
In-House1	A global bank call centre. Has call centres in the UK, India, and the Philippines.
In-House2	This in-house company is global, with more than 10,000 employees in a range of industries. It has call centres all over the UK and abroad.
In-House3	A UK bank, which is part of the HM Treasury Women in Finance organisation.
In-House4	This company is one of the world's largest utility companies.
In-House5	This is an international communications company and has 9.5 million customers. It has call centres in the UK as well as India.
In-House6	It is a major commercial and retail bank. It has a call centre in Glasgow.
In-House7	One of the world-leading communication companies. It provides TV, phone, broadband and IT services.
In-House8	This is an insurance company. It sells a range of insurance products and provides more services online and over the phone.
In-House9	This is a retail and commercial bank in the UK. It has branches in Scotland, England and Wales

In-HouseTravel1	This is an American car rental company, which operates corporate and franchise locations internationally.
In-HouseTravel2	This company is worldwide travel group. It is a mass-market tour operator.

Source: The author (2021)

Table 3.4 Information about the Outsource Call Centres

Name of CC	Information about the outsource call centre
Outsourcer1	This company provides digital, consulting, back office and software services.
Outsourcer2	This outsourcer call centre works in the communication industry.
Outsourcer3	This outsourcer has its main office in Scotland, though the majority of its business was in IT and communications in India.
Outsourcer4	This outsourcing company is based in Scotland. They provide software services in addition to their call centre; the company do both inbound and outbound calls.
Outsourcer5	This company is based in Scotland, with its Head Office in France. This is a technical consultancy, business outsourcing and customer experience company.
Outsourcer6	This company is based in Scotland, with its headquarters in France. The company provides customer care, technical, social media and other campaigns.
Outsourcer7	A telecommunication call centre based in Scotland.
Outsourcer8	This is a privately owned call centre. The company provide outsourced sales, customer service and other services for large companies.
Outsourcer9	This outsourcer is a British company. The company has over 500 contracts worldwide.
Outsourcer10	This is a Scotland-based company. They provide outsourced call centre and software services; the company do both inbound and outbound calls.

Outsourcer11	This company offers a real-time online assistance service, as well as an outsourced call centre.
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Source: The author (2021)

3.5.4 Demographic data of interviewees

In seeking to investigate and analyse women in call centre management, it is useful to consider looking at the demographic details regarding the managers and their call centres (see Appendix five). The conceptual framework and the literature chapter informed the demographic data. This section will discuss information regarding respondents, their role in the call centre, marital status, children, education and the number of people they manage. The data were collected from the seventeen interviews.

The sampling technique used in this research to interview managers was purposive sampling. A homogeneous purposive sampling approach was employed to select participants for this study. This strategy was deemed most appropriate given that the research focused on the experiences of women in call centre management within the specific context of Scotland. Selecting participants based on their shared characteristic of holding managerial positions in Scottish contact centres ensured that the sample possessed direct lived experience of the phenomenon under investigation, enabling them to provide rich and detailed data relevant to the research questions topic and questions based on their knowledge and expertise (Miles and Huberman, 1994; Creswell and Poth, 2016). This approach aligns with the qualitative nature of the study, which prioritises in-depth understanding over

generalisability (Creswell and Poth, 2016). The sample consisted of participants who hold managerial positions, such as team leaders and operational managers, in call centres located in Scotland.

Maxwell (2012) highlighted that purposeful sampling is a valuable technique that serves multiple important purposes. First, it can facilitate a representative or typical selection of settings, individuals, or activities. A purposefully chosen sample that is systematically sampled for typicality and relative homogeneity can provide greater confidence that the conclusions adequately reflect the average members of the population compared to a sample of the same size that incorporates substantial random or accidental variation. Second, purposeful sampling can be employed to adequately capture the population's heterogeneity. The aim here is to ensure the conclusions suitably represent the entire range of variation rather than only the typical members or a subset of this range. Third, a purposefully selected sample can enable the examination of cases that are critical for the theories underpinning the study or that have subsequently emerged. Finally, purposeful sampling can be utilised to establish particular comparisons that illuminate the reasons for differences between settings or individuals, a common approach in multi-case qualitative studies.

The marital status of interviewees has been highlighted in the table as it was important to find out about interviewees' views regarding work and family conflict. The number of children included was to discuss if it was conflicting with work pressure for some of the interviewees. Therefore, the marital status

and the number of children to be included were very important for family and work responsibilities. Among the interviewees, eight were married, five were single, three were in a relationship, and one was a widow. Nine of the interviewees had children.

The education component was added as the interviewee discussed the importance of both human and social capital. Human capital is important in terms of training and education, and social capital is in terms of networking. Both are added to the table to discuss how both assisted in their career advancement. The number of interviewees who were educated to postgraduate level was one, undergraduate was seven, diploma level was four, and high school educated were five.

Therefore, it can be concluded from Appendix Five that all respondents interviewed were team leaders and above in call centres. The type of call centres that the respondents were working in were in-house and outsourced, and they were inshore call centres. The number of respondents working in-house and outsourcing is evenly split. Most of the respondents were either married or in a relationship and had children. In terms of age, 47% were between 30 and 40. The rest were over 40. Most of the research respondents were educated to a degree level; however, a few were educated up to a diploma level. Additionally, the number of employees the respondents managed was from 5 to 2,500. Finally, all respondents were working full-time.

3.6 Data Analysis

Galetto (2016) states that actionable insights and decisions can be derived from different sources of data and solutions in organisations. Beck (1995) added that data analysis helps with answering the questions of the research, and if the analysis is executed well, the conclusions will be strong. Some of the popular qualitative approaches available to the researcher were grounded theory, thematic analysis, IPA, narrative analysis and discourse analysis (Braun and Clarke, 2020).

Grounded theory was introduced by Barney G. Glaser and Anselm L. Strauss (1967) in their book *The Discovery of Grounded Theory* (Glaser and Strauss, 1967), and since then, the approach has been used among different professions and disciplines. Its framework for analysing qualitative data is one of the most used by researchers (Bryman and Bell, 2011). The most important advantage of using grounded theory is that it is processed based, inductive and contextual in nature, and this useful characteristic of this method fits well with this interpretive study (Strauss and Corbin, 1990; Orlikowski, 1993; Charmaz, 2006).

Grounded theory fits with the qualitative research methodology (Charmaz, 2008). The features of grounded theory that differentiate it from others are that it focusses on theory building and also that the data collected during the research process are not collected before starting the research. In addition, data collection and analysis happen concurrently. The concepts that arise from the analysis are then used in the following interviews (Corbin and Strauss,

2015). Charmaz (2008) summarizes some guidelines for analysing data using grounded theory techniques, which were adopted in this research and are set out in Table 3.5 below:

Table 3.5 Charmaz guidelines

Comparing data with data
Labelling data with active, specific codes
Selecting focused codes
Comparing and sorting data with focused codes
Raising telling focused codes to tentative analytic categories
Comparing data and codes with analytic categories

Source: The Author

The grounded approach provides a more 'open' approach to analysing data (Easterby-Smith et al., 2008). This approach systematically analyses the data and offers a more flexible approach to collecting qualitative data (Charmaz, 2006). Using this approach to collecting data, the researcher can examine themes related to the topic. It will also allow further analysis related to women's perceptions of gender inequality in call centres from different angles and will, therefore, provide a detailed explanation (Corbin and Strauss, 2015). The interviews are analysed concurrently in a typical qualitative research case (Charmaz, 2006).

While the grounded theory is a powerful method for data analysis, it might not have been the ideal fit for this research on gender inequality regimes in call centres, as grounded theory is best suited for exploring under-theorised areas where a new theory needs to emerge from the data (Strauss and Corbin,

1990). However, gender inequality is already a well-established field of study with a robust theoretical framework as Acker's theory of gendered organisations (Benschop and van den Brink, 2019) (Nkomo and Rodriguez, 2019). Applying these existing frameworks to the context of call centres likely offered a more suitable approach than building a new theory from the ground up.

In contrast, thematic analysis allows you to engage directly with these established theories and concepts, using them to guide and inform your qualitative data analysis (Braun and Clarke, 2006a). This theory-driven approach can generate valuable insights into how the broader gender inequality frameworks manifest in the call centre environment without constructing an entirely new theory.

In conclusion, while both thematic analysis and grounded theory are valuable qualitative research methods, the thematic analysis offers several distinct advantages that make it a more suitable choice for this research on gender inequality in call centres. Therefore, this research used thematic data analysis, which will be discussed in the next section.

3.6.1 Interview data analysis (Thematic data analysis)

Thematic analysis is believed to be a common approach to analysing qualitative research data. According to Braun and Clarke (2006), thematic analysis is a method for analysing qualitative data that requires searching across a data set to categorise, analyse, and report repeated patterns. It is not only a method for unfolding the qualitative data, but it also involves

interpretation in the processes of selecting codes and constructing themes. A distinctive characteristic of thematic analysis is its flexibility, as it does not rely on any specific philosophy (Saunders et al., 2012). Rather, it can be used within a wide range of theoretical and epistemological frameworks and can be effectively applied to a wide range of study questions, designs, and sample sizes. Though some intellectuals have categorised thematic analysis as falling within the realm of ethnography (Aronson 1995) or as specifically suited to phenomenology (Joffe 2011), Braun and Clarke (2006) contend that thematic analysis can stand alone as an analytic method and be seen as the basis for other qualitative research methods.

Keeping in view the effectiveness of the thematic approach in data analysis, the researcher analysed the interview data through a thematic analysis approach and further broke down the data to identify the main themes emerging from the responses. Thematic analysis was applied to the interviews and supported by NVivo. The themes from the data analysis have been linked to the theoretical framework in Chapter two.

Thematic data analysis, as has been suggested by Kiger and Varpio (2020) is an appropriate method of analysis when a researcher is looking to understand experiences, behaviours and thoughts across data sets, as is the case with this study. It has been pointed out by Braun and Clarke (2006a) that thematic analysis provides the researcher with a valuable core skill for various forms of qualitative analysis. The researcher can use both inductive and deductive approaches to the identification of the themes (Braun and Clarke, 2006a). An

inductive approach derives themes from the data as it is used in grounded theory (Varpio *et al.*, 2019). Braun and Clarke (2006a) argued that data in the inductive approach drive themes. On the contrary, the deductive approach uses a framework or pre-existing theories or other researchers' driven focus to identify themes that the researcher is interested in (Braun and Clarke, 2006a, 2012). An inductive approach focuses on a particular aspect of the data that could be best shown or understood in the context of a pre-existing theory or framework (Braun and Clarke, 2006a).

Coding was carried out using NVivo. According to Fries (2019), CAQDS has changed the way data is analysed and gathered in qualitative research. Friese (2019) supports the use of CAQDS. Using this software enabled the researcher to gain insights, and it was quicker to analyse the data. The coding was started from the first interview and was done line by line, as stated by (Charmaz, 2006), as it keeps the researcher actively involved in the analysis. While coding, the researcher looks for themes and patterns, which are then analysed using thematic coding (Charmaz, 2008).

The interviews were analysed using NVivo. This software was used based on the large scale of data to manage. Using NVivo software, the researcher was able to prepare and educate herself about the data by reading it two times before coding it. The software is useful in analysing and gathering all evidence and grouping them into similar themes and ideas. It has also been found that using the software improves the rigour of the analytical steps for validating (Ibrahim, 2012). According to Braun and Clarke (2006), thematic analysis is

used widely in research, and they suggest a step-by-step guide to doing thematic analysis. This is explained in Figure 3.5

Figure 3.5 Stages of thematic analysis, the differences between the 2006 and 2020 articles

Source: (Braun and Clarke, 2006b, 2020)

The researcher followed Braun, and Clarke's (2006, 2020) suggested analysis guide. Braun and Clark's later published another journal in which the stages were updated in 2020 to remove some misconceptions and confusion about the use of thematic analysis (Braun and Clarke, 2020). For this research, the 2020 journal was mainly used. The stages for the thematic analysis are explained below.

Stage one is familiarisation. It started by reading and re-reading the transcribed interview, which was transcribed in Otter.ai. Braun and Clarke (2006) highlighted there is no one way to do thematic analyses, the same as

there is no set of guidelines to produce the transcript. Initially, the interviews were recorded through ZOOM and Microsoft Teams, and then the verbal data was transferred to Otter transcription software, where it was transcribed and checked for missing information by listening to the audio several times and comparing it to transcripts. Then, it was saved into a Word document. Braun and Clarke (2006) suggest that researchers need to transcribe the data before performing thematic analysis. This process was time-consuming and frustrating but was useful for familiarising myself with the data.

Stage two is systematic data coding through familiarisation with the data and having an idea of what is interesting and important. At this stage, the researcher produces codes from the data of all interviews. To start this stage, the researcher created a Node structure in NVivo since the researcher knew some key broad topics in the research, which were included in the interview guide. For example, the career pathway was a main node, or parent node as it is called in NVivo, which had two sub-nodes, or child nodes in NVivo, with one as an enabler and another as a barrier. It is important to explain what code is; therefore, it is described as 'an analytic unit or tool, used by researchers to develop initial themes (Braun and Clarke, 2020). Code can be explained as a label that captures something interesting in the data. It usually represents just one facet. This phase allows the researcher to produce initial codes from the data. It is a theorising activity in which the researcher must visit the data repeatedly. It is a process of reflection, communicating with the data analysis (Savage, 2000). The interview transcript in Word documents was imported to NVivo. King (2004) suggests that researchers can use software to organise

and sort the data. It is essential to highlight that although computer programmes help organise and sort data, they are incapable intellectually or do not have the capability to judge or have any conceptual process to transform data. The software facilitates the coding of the data for easy identification and critical thinking. The transcript was coded, and the key section of the text was identified and related to a theme or issue. Extracts from the interview data were coded in as many themes as they fitted. There were memos created if the code had an important aspect or expression. The codes were cross-checked with the conceptual framework for the first three interviews and found that they answered the research question. The researcher was satisfied that the codes generated were aligned with the research questions. However, as new interviews took place and new data emerged, the researcher continued to check this at regular intervals. The researcher continued to code the rest of the interviews. This was done systematically and covered the entire data. The researcher gave full attention to each data item, which would create the basis for the themes as suggested by Braun and Clarke (2006). It was an organic process, and the codes changed over time. Some of the codes had two or three levels and were divided into more codes.

The third stage was about generating initial themes from coded and collected data. Code clusters together to build and generate themes (Braun and Clarke, 2006b). A theme is described by DeSantis and Ugarriza (2000, p.362) as "...an abstract entity that brings meaning and identity to a recurrent experience and its variant manifestations. As such, a theme captures and unifies the

nature or basis of the experience into a meaningful whole". The researcher gathered the codes and identified the themes to present the overall picture of gender inequality regimes in the call centre industry. In this stage, the coded nodes in NVivo were checked to find out if there was a pattern or themes. The Screenshot of NVivo is presented in the Appendix 7. The prevalent themes are listed in the table below.

Table 3.6 Themes from the NVivo

Themes	No. of Interviewees who discussed the issue	No. of coding references
Inhouse and outsourced call centres	14	93
Career progress and career history	17	186
Barriers to women's progress	17	89
Motherhood, family and caring responsibilities	13	76
Recruitment and selection	15	62
Networking, career support, and it is important, mentoring	14	36
Management style and call centre management	13	47
Pay gap	16	73
Percentage of women in management	17	128
Working hours and workload	16	53
Sexual Harassment and sex discrimination	15	80
Organisation culture	13	48

Source: Author

Later the themes were generated from the codes. Codes were clustered together and made a theme. The researcher reviewed the themes and asked herself the following questions. Is there a central organising concept? Is the quality of the themes good? What are the boundaries of the theme? Is there enough data to support the theme? Are the data too diverse? And finally, the researcher finalised the thematic map and used labels from the research questions.

The fourth data analysis stage was developing and reviewing themes and making the links between the themes. Initially, there were 15 categories. It was reduced to 11 categories. The fifth stage was to redefine, define and name themes. In this stage, the themes' names were decided, and explanations were sought as to why the theme was important to the broader study questions. The names were the themes that reflected the central idea of the research, and an example is given in Table 3.7.

Table 3.7 Examples of coding and themes

Nodes (Parent)	Excerpts	Coding (Child Nodes)	Themes
Pay Gap	No. And we never ever found that myself, but three actually published their pay disparity, their gender, the gender gap report, you can get that from the website. It shows you there. It's not that different. Actually, they were making inroads to close that gap between both. So, we are actually paid really well, which makes it a really good company to work for in that sense.CM8	Bonuses Rewards and benefits	Is there pay gap in your organisation?
Career	I started off while I was doing my degree, hmm, just on the phone as a sales advisor. CM8	Barriers Enablers Motherhood Caring responsibilities	Career progress and career history

Source: The author

The final stage was writing up the results and producing the written material presented in Chapter Four. Some of the vivid and important examples of data for each theme were presented in related analysis to the research and the literature. The conceptual framework and the literature chapter informed the demographic data.

Details of the interviewees. The Nominal data in this Appendix has been labelled under, for example, gender and education without providing any quantitative measure. It is common in qualitative data to be presented in nominal form. The data is analysed using the grouping method manually. The variables were grouped into categories, and the percentage was calculated for

each category. The seniority characteristics were presented in Figure 3.1 in order to present the relative proportion of the seniority of the participants (CFI, 2022).

3.7 Reflexivity

Cassell and Symon (2004, p. 20) explained the term reflexivity as “the recognition that the involvement of the researcher as an active participant in the research process shapes the nature of the process and the knowledge produced through it”.

Reflexivity is important as it is argued that “researchers are always part of the social world they study. [and so, should] ...reflect on their role in the research process and on the wider context in which it occurs” (Hammersley, 2004, p. 934). The researcher is aware of the issue of reflexivity and adopted the suggestions of Cassell and Symon (2004) to facilitate researcher reflection. At the start of the research, the researcher wrote down the assumptions she had about the interviewee and referred to it at each stage of the research process. The researcher also kept a diary to record her feelings during the process. Later, the researcher listened to the interviews and also focused on her performance as an interviewer (Cassell and Symon, 2004).

3.8 Access and ethical issues

Four key aspects of ethics are explained by Diener and Grandall (1978, cited in Bryman and Bell, 2011) and were adopted in this research in order to research in an ethical and responsible way. Firstly, they argue that the

researcher should give attention to the issue of harm to the participant. This research doesn't involve any physical harm to the participants. Secondly is the issue of lack of informed consent. Informed consent is an essential part of conducting research (Laerd, 2016). To remove any concern regarding ethical practices, a consent form (See Appendix 1) was sent to the interviewees. Each participant signed the consent form. Besides, the researcher submitted the required formal Research ethical approval form to UWS on the 17th of June 2020 and was approved by the School Ethics Committee on the 6th of July 2020.

Thirdly in terms of invasion of privacy, it is argued that in the research process, the issue of privacy and anonymity is always related (Bryman and Bell, 2011). Personal information regarding the participants has been kept confidential. Participants were informed of their rights if they wanted to withdraw at any point(Laerd, 2016). Where appropriate, the call centre's HR team were contacted, and consent was obtained from the organisation before conducting the study. While conducting the interviews, managers were informed of anonymity and confidentiality (Laerd, 2016).

The last issue concerns the involvement of any deception. While conducting the interviews, the researcher ensured the interviewees were provided with important information regarding the aim of the study. Before the interview, the interviewee was informed of the recording of the interview. All participants were emailed information sheets, which contained details of the research. The information sheet explained to the participant that participation in the research

was entirely voluntary and that they had the right to withdraw at any time before, during, or within a calendar year of the date of giving their consent without giving any reason. Details about their agreement to participate, what the study entails, what their participation entails, e.g. a one-hour interview via the Internet or phone that will be audio recorded, and their right to confidentiality and protection from distress/harm were also included in that.

The researcher has paid attention to all these aspects of research ethics regarding the rights and obligations of both the researcher and the participants while conducting the interviews (Ticehurst and Veal, 2000). The interview was recorded on my phone and then transcribed on my home computer. All these contributions were made anonymous and kept confidential. Pseudonyms were used to refer to all participants and other generalised substitutes for their place of employment (e.g., call-centre A) as well as any other identifying information in transcriptions and the final research as well.

Other ethical issues also considered while conducting this research was that digital material was stored in the secured systems of the University of the West of Scotland using OneDrive and password protected. Only the main researcher had access to any personal information and raw data folder which were secured via password protection. All data collected was anonymised, and no identifying information was collected. The device used to record interviews was protected via passcode. No digital transfer of data from the phone has been conducted via mobile data or wireless connections; only via cable data transfer has been done to ensure data security.

Due to the Covid-19 crisis, my home computer was the main device used to process transcripts and recordings. To keep my home computer secure, McAfee antivirus software was downloaded and kept up to date. My laptop was secured with password protection and was kept in the home with an appropriate security system. Any printed documents that might contain any personal information of participants were kept under secure conditions and stored in a secure building in a secure cabinet. In addition, also due to the COVID-19 pandemic, interviews were conducted via Zoom rather than face-to-face. The researcher also paid attention to the essential and important ethical principles of honesty, plagiarism, informed consent, permission to publish and so on (Myers, 2019).

3.9 Chapter Summary

This chapter aimed to evaluate the methodological aspects of the research. The research was interpretive in nature. To understand women's views and experiences in the management in the call centre. This chapter also discussed the interview method to gather qualitative data. The researcher would like to point out that the researcher used Online Zoom

Chapter 4 - Results and Discussion

4.1 Introduction

As stated in Chapter 1, the aim of this research is to explore how gender inequality regimes influence the experiences of women in call centre management in order to inform organisational policies and practices on diversity and equality, both in call centres and more broadly. This chapter presents the research findings from interviews with women managers and key informants employed in Scottish call centres and discusses these in detail. As set out in Chapter 3, the qualitative nature of the research topic and study objectives necessitated using interviews as the primary method of data collection. And as Ryan et al (2010) contend, interviewing is an appropriate approach for gathering data on respondents' beliefs, behaviours, and experiences. As also set out in Chapter 3, the interview data was then analysed using thematic analysis, with the Nodes method employed in NVivo software to generate the emergent themes. Drawing on the conceptual framework developed from the literature review and presented in Section 2.10 and also the research questions set out in Section 2.11, and again below, this chapter presents the findings related to the conceptual framework and discusses each in turn. The findings are structured around four key themes that correspond to the research questions presented below:

Research question one (RQ1): What is the level of women's representation in managerial positions within call centres in Scotland?

Research question two (RQ2): What do managers think about factors that constitute gender inequality in their call centres.

Research question three (RQ3): What barriers do women face while progressing in call centre management, and how do they successfully navigate them?

Research question four (RQ4): What effective policies and strategies are available for call centres to reduce gender inequality?

This chapter addresses the research questions by drawing upon the themes that emerged from the literature review and discussing them in detail. There is a strong link between the themes in this chapter and the conceptual framework presented in Chapter 2. The key emerging themes are set out in Table 4.1, demonstrating how they answer the research questions. Each research question is linked to a theme from the findings, with the corresponding section number from Chapter 4 provided in brackets. This table also shows how the themes connect to the conceptual framework. The conceptual framework outlines the key elements that constitute gender inequality in organisations.

The first research question explores the level of women's representation in managerial positions within call centres in Scotland. This includes an overview of the Scottish call centre industry, highlighting the reasons why call centres are located in Scotland, including both in-house and outsourced call centres. It then proceeds to discuss the first theme, which investigates the views of women managers regarding the representation and experiences of women in call centres management.

This is followed by the findings on women's participation in call centre management. This includes examining the visible aspects of gender inequality, as detailed in the conceptual framework, which are referred to as the shape and degree of inequality. It also explores the structure of call centres and discusses women's representation in management roles. In addition, the discussion will address occupational segregation, which Acker (2012) and Connell (2006) have identified as an indicator of and part of the shape and degree of inequality.

The second research question examines what managers think about the factors that constitute gender inequality in their call centres. Additionally, this chapter presents the findings and discussion regarding the call centres' sub-structures and explains the associated processes and practices. These are explored by investigating the work organisation in the call centres and the factors that positively or negatively impact managers' career progression. Furthermore, it examines inequality in terms of occupational segregation, pay gaps, the impact of motherhood, and the challenges posed by family and caring responsibilities.

The third research question explores barriers to women's progression in call centre management and how women navigate these challenges. This question examines and discusses sex discrimination, stereotyping, career support, networking, management styles, performance standards, and organisational culture that impact gender equality in call centre management.

Finally, in terms of research question four, this chapter also examines effective policies and strategies that call centres can implement to reduce gender inequality. It outlines the interviewees' proposed solutions to address gender inequality in call centres. These solutions, combined with key aspects of the conceptual framework, are discussed in relation to this issue question.

Table 4.1 Themes answering the research questions

Research Questions	Themes and Sections	Framework
Research Question one (RQ1): What is the level of women's representation in managerial positions within call centres in Scotland?	Occupational segregation	Occupational segregation
Research Question Two (RQ2): What do managers think about factors that constitute gender inequality in their call centres.	Occupational segregation Pay gap Organizational Processes (Ideal Worker) Motherhood, family and caring responsibilities, marital status Legitimacy and degree of awareness of gender inequality	Occupational segregation Pay gap Marital status Motherhood Degree of awareness of gender inequality Legitimacy of inequality Organisational processes (Ideal worker)
Research Question Three (RQ3): What barriers do women face while progressing in call centre management, and how do they successfully navigate them?	Interactions in the call centres Barriers and facilitators to women's career progress to management Culture of the call centre	Stereotyping Organisational culture Organisational interactions

	Workplace behaviour and interaction	
Research Question Four (RQ4): What are available effective policies and strategies for call centres to reduce gender inequality?	Potential solutions to reduce inequality	Key elements of the conceptual framework, listed above, are reviewed.

Source: Author

4.2 Characteristics and structure of the call centres

This section examines the hierarchical structure of call centres, the extent to which inequality is externalised in outsourced call centres, and how gender inequality regimes vary between in-house and outsourced call centres. The focus will be on the results from the call centre industry in Scotland, particularly concerning the women employed in this sector. This section also classifies the different types of call centres, specifically in-house and outsourced centres, also known as Business Process Outsourcing (BPOs). This study will address outsourcing, in-house solutions, and public sector call centres. Additionally, there is an exploration of the international call centre industry, review the sector's reputation, and discuss the implications of the call centre's flat structure for women.

Call centres in Scotland have grown over the past thirty years, although it is unclear which company started the first call centre in Scotland (Scotjobsnet, 2014). The interviewees explained several reasons for the rise of the call

centre industry, and the first of these focused on the fact that the Scottish people are thought and found to be friendly, as is the 'Scottish Voice':

"... being really friendly and chatty." CM14

As compared to people in London, she said:

"if you get in a tube in London, no one speaks to you." CM14

One manager added that the people are friendly

"They are normally quite upbeat; they catch on really quickly as well. And I think there's also a hunger for that as well. So there's been success in the country, so people want to do that job." CM12

Managers also discussed the Scottish voice, saying that

"So, there's a piece on that we're looking at how customers react. And quite a lot of the research that businesses will do as, like, look. How do they react to a Scottish voice? How did they react to, you know, what, you know, what is that they buy into?" CM15

The view expressed by the CM15 is parallel to the view of Matinee Multilingual (2020), which elaborated that even though the Scottish accent is difficult to imitate and sometimes to understand, the accent is found to be friendly. However, as CM14 pointed out, an educated and qualified workforce is also available.

The second reason was that the government provides incentives to locate call centres in Scotland. The Scottish Development International (SDI), the government's trade and inward investment agency, stated that companies have immense confidence in Scotland's highly skilled workforce and infrastructure and that Scotland is an appealing destination for expanding business (SDI, 2021). SDI also said that Scotland is a strategic location for growth and innovation, with skills, a low-cost base, a business infrastructure, and a global business network (SDI, 2021).

CM2 said the reason is that:

"The various Scottish Governments they would have given state grants or tax breaks etc., to the firm, which is attractive." CM2

CM6 stated:

"Call centres really started Scotland because that's definitely a thing they're quite proud of, in the call centre industry, that it was a Scottish industry."

In addition, CM15 stated:

"Some contact centres they've set up right in the very beginning, and that's not going to happen in Glasgow now, but probably at the time, there were huge grants associated with high unemployment and things like that. And that's why they picked the areas that are probably picked because the government is supporting some sort of building cost that in setting out most of the contact centres." CM15

CM15 showed concern regarding independence for Scotland if that happened.

She suggested

“If we moved to like an independent Scotland, would that still be the same? Would those companies still want to be here? And that’s the thing that people need to think about do not mean because at the end of the day, it’s a whole company director for whoever decided they wanted to go Scotland decided to be independent out with the UK, especially in financial.” CM15

She further emphasised that call centres were mainly based in Scotland’s Central Belt.

“There’s a little kind of Central belt of ...So, it’s why there are, you know, there’s this kind of concentration kind of the central belt of call centres.” CM15

CM 15, who had been working in call centres in Scotland for twenty-five years, explained that in her first job, “it had quite a small headcount...it was less than 200 people”. In the beginning, she said the work was very simple. Calls were “like hi, Mrs Jones, I’m just calling to see how you’re offering free friends and family discounts”. However, she pointed out that call centres have become more complicated, and customers call for all different sorts of inquiries.

CM11, with thirty years of experience in Inhouse1(Bank), explained the attraction of early call centre work. She said that at that time, home computers were not widely available. She found the job

“Amazing because we didn’t have computers at home, so it was a brand new way of working and not filing cabinets... just brilliant.” CM11

Appendix Six shows the concentration of call centres in the Central Belt.

The price point for the call centres in Scotland was confirmed by respondent CM2, who said there are four reasons why Scotland is popular, as has been outlined in this section:

“The Scottish accent is accepted within the English-speaking world. The Scottish accent is well-received, and that is very important if you want to keep your customer happy.”

She went on to point out that, secondly, the employment costs are lower in Scotland:

“ ...it is the price point. Scotland is considerably cheaper from a labour point of view than England or Ireland, for that matter, at this point.” CM2

Thirdly, she stated that location and cost are important aspects when organisations consider locating their call centre.

“... in certain areas in Scotland, is high unemployment. Again, if I come in and open a contact centre in an area with high unemployment, the state will be ever so grateful. Yeah. And that attracts a company an outsourcer to open a contact centre.” CM2

Fourthly, she noted that:

“Scotland has its own legal system, and CM6 highlights an interesting point that some call centres were initially based in Scotland due to Scottish law. She added that call centres began in Scotland because of a legal loophole. “The first call centres started in Scotland in Glasgow because there was a legal loophole, because [in] Scots law, you can agree to a contract verbally [while in] English law, it had to be written.”CM2

She pointed out that legally you could have a verbal contract over the phone with the customer as compared to England, where it had to be on paper.

“It’s good. So, you could sign up your contract in Scotland when the call centre was based in Scotland.”CM2

Even when the English law changed, she stated that this legal loophole boosted the call centre industry in Scotland. CM6 also pointed out that one of the early Scottish call centres, now an independent outsourcer, initially began by selling tickets for a Scottish football club:

“ I think it was selling tickets...and then it kind of went on from there.”

The call centre industry is a growing source of employment, and organisations are being funded to locate their call centres in Scotland. Most call centres are located in the Central Belt. Employees are well educated, and unemployment is high, so call centres can attract employees, as turnover is high. The growth of the call centre sector is impressive and challenging. The industry, in a short space of time, has transformed customer service, the nature of the service

sector and the location where they operate (Burgess and Connell, 2017). This industrial revolution is threefold. Firstly, the means of service provided is through ICT, and its capabilities have increased over time. The second feature of the industry is the re-restructuring of the organisational management, and the workforce is reconfigured, producing leaner organisations to save costs and overheads. That resulted in outsourcing and subcontracting their services to other call centres. Labour contracts replace previous commercial agreements, resulting in a flat organisational structure. The third factor is related to the previously discussed two. The integration of ICT and the separation of production has facilitated the restructuring of the customer service work. There is now the physical separation of the employee from the actual workplace and the customer (Burgess and Connell, 2017). In the following section, we will analyse and compare the different types of call centres in Scotland.

4.2.1 Comparing the types of call centres

There are different ways that customers are connected to call centres. The first kind is inbound call centres, where the customer calls the call centre if they have any issue or question regarding their product. The second is outbound call centres, where the call centre agents phone customers regarding their products, such as telemarketing calls. The third kind of call centre has both outbound and inbound activities (Zapf *et al.*, 2003). So, do gender inequality regimes differ between in-house and outsourced call centres?

All respondents in this research were dealing with inbound call centres. The interviews with respondents were evenly split between in-house and outsourced call centres.

Managers views on Inhouse call centres are listed below:

Respondent CM1 stated:

“In-house companies tend to have more resources, whether that be money, people, whatever it needs to do to get the job done.”

In-house Banks by CM4 and CM14. CM4 said that Inhouse operations are:

“Cost-effective, consistency of customer experience. I think it helps refine practices, coaching, management practices, communication improves. There’s a whole host of reasons why having everybody in a central place, makes it better for colleagues and better for the customers.”

“I was proud to work for Inhouse2. I was proud to work for Inhouse6, but I think I was proud to work for Outsource5? Probably no. I didn’t feel that you had an attachment to them as a company” CM14

“That has to do with the fact usually big firms like at the time In-house Travel 1 or In-house travel 2 was another firm. I worked in-house in the contact centre, there was a lot of finances available for employee engagement, for your wellbeing. With In-house travel 1 and with In-house travel 2, we had a gym on-site we had we had a bar in the house the whole lot; you will not get that right now with an outsourcer. So, you need to find a different way of creating this feeling of, shall we say, belonging.” CM15

This section focuses on the call centre industry, which is generally divided into two primary forms: in-house and outsourced. In-house call centres are located within the same organisation (Chicu *et al.*, 2019), for example, in banking and insurance. Outsourcing call centres are explained by Chicu *et al.*, (2019) as offering their services to other companies who wish to outsource, such as their ticket booking or HR function.

CM15 pointed out that in in-house call centres, companies tend to spend a lot of money on engagement, coaching and supporting the junior team members, which really assists with employees buying into the call centre's culture.

4.2.2 Outsourcing call centres

It is believed that companies are using outsourcing as a key strategy to improve costs, productivity, profitability and competitiveness, ((Moschuris, 2008) or in the case of public sector companies, they use it to improve efficiency (Farneti and Young, 2008). These types of call centres are divided into inbound and outbound.

Outsourced call centres are when the company decides to move some of its internal and decision making responsibility to an outside provider (Gray *et al.*, 2013). When comparing in-house call centres to outsource call centres, outsource call centres are more likely to focus on sales and outbound calls Holman *et al.*, (2007). Overall, the research found that there are three types of Outsourcing. First is “offshore outsourcing” that is when you hire a company in another country to do customer service for you; India is one of the best examples of this (Nextprocess, 2021).

The second is “nearshoring”, which happens when you contract a neighbouring country, for example, a country in Europe such as Ireland. The third is “onshoring”, which occurs when you outsource certain work to another outsourcing company in the UK. This thesis examines onshoring call centres, and these are set out in Table 4.4 below.

Respondent CM1 explained the difference between working in an inhouse bank call centre to an outsources call centre as:

“[the] bank [In-house] is very different, it takes a bit to get used to [and said] I think outsource is a very, very different beast to inhouse. Outsourcer1 was a typical outsource provider and trying to cut corners, trying to do so many different things.” CM1

Another manager agreed with CM1, saying that:

“Outsourcing is very different to work in directly for an employer, I think. They’re just a lot more focused on numbers. And not as focused on people.” CM14

When asked about what part of the business company will outsource?

CM1 replied,

“There are quite often, if I am honest, “scuff work”. So the work that people didn’t want to do, the work where there is high volume, the work where you could have a tedious work perhaps you could end up high absence and not service your customers that’s why call centre work is so commonly outsourced because they can keep the more complex stuff in house and will send out the high volumes for somebody else to manage it for them.”

Respondent CM1 further explained that the type of work usually outsourced:

“That could be retentions, sales, customer service, so I think at Outsourcer10, we would deal with meter issues and any kind of customer service meter readings, billing queries, cash collection. With Outsourcer5, we deal with customer services, upgrades and downgrades and retention is so if somebody wanted to leave, for example, trying to keep their business.”

Some of the reasons that the respondents highlighted for outsourcing was to save money, for example, CM1 from (Outsourcer10) and CM10 (Outsourcer 1)

“They would decide on which parts of their business they were going to pay somebody else to manage for them. Ultimately, it was cheaper for that business to be able to do that.” CM1

CM10 pointed out that the main reason for contracts going to different companies is price, but recently technology has played an important role. She also said that technology played an important factor and pointed out they lost a contract due to that recently.

“So, it’s where that the companies get the best price.” CM10

And:

“...most recently, a contract that we sadly lost after a long time that they and the company that procured that deal weren’t on technology. The client preferred the technology that was on offer by another company than from what we could offer.” CM10

CM2 also added that there are

“Firms they never outsourced their contact centre.”

However, she also said

“There are firms that outsource anything that is customer service related. Because it’s a cost centre to the firm, not a profit centre, and because it’s a cost centre, they want that cost as cheap, as low as possible. Yeah. So therefore, they go and find an outsourcer. Very often, Outsourcing is initially driven by pricing.” CM2

Once the decision to outsource is taken, the control and internal management are decided by the type of contract between the call centre and the client company (Ren and Zhou, 2008). This includes—the type of service and managerial strategies, the contract design, and the payment system agreed upon by the outsourcing centre. There are different forms of contracts. Firstly, there is pay per call resolved- in these contracts, the host company pay for the call resolution. Secondly, there is a piecemeal or partnership contract - in this form of contract, the parent company pays for every call attended. Thirdly, there is pay for call resolved plus share cost- where the call centre earns for every call resolution and, in addition, shares the cost with the main company. The third one is suggested to be the best one to gain coordination and optimal level of staff and effort in a call centre (Ren and Zhou, 2008).

The length of the contract varies. As CM5 pointed out,

“They can be one-year contracts. There can be three-year contracts. They can be five-year contracts or longer, but in general, the most common contract is three years long.”

K2 pointed out that the outsourcer has a partnership relationship with the client, and he explained that:

“... it’s certainly more and modern, this is what I would say, I think historically, outsourcers have worked as service providers like that traditional way. This way is more overlapping and probably more ingraining each other and then the way that we work. So, I guess from [the Client’s (Inhouse 2) point of view. They like their operations to run in a particular way with a particular style. And they bring things in all things from Inhouse 2 to the operation. So, we actually have like employees who reside and work within our building as [Outsourcer 5]. So that gives you an idea of what we call the partnership.”

When a client decides to introduce a new policy, process or change, it is introduced from the client. But she pointed out that the outsourcing company can suggest policy, and she said that it should be encouraged as

“At the end of the day, your guys on the phones, or the way that I see it as your guys on the phone, that should be your primary source of information and on one exchange, because they are the ones talking to the customer day in and day out nothing from people sitting in an office to write down a new policy on a new process is very easy.” CM13

However, eventually, the change always comes from the main office

“But the changes will always come from in-house from your head office teams.” CM13

A further development in outsourcing is business processing outsourcing (BPO). There are two BPO categories in Outsourcing; the first is back-office Outsourcing, which deals mainly with the business's in-house requirements,

for example, billing, payroll, HR, etc. However, the second form of BPO is outsourcing front office services like customer service, marketing, and technical support (Nextprocess, 2021). CM1 gives an example of back-office

Outsourcing:

“They would decide what parts they were going to keep for themselves. Typically, it would be call centre work that people outsource, but sometimes it would be back-office work.”

In outsourcing, there is one model that is called an in-house solution, where the outsourcer and in-house are located in the same building, as explained by

CM2:

“...that initial setup came into play also a couple of years ago, maybe ten years ago, 12 years ago, where is this kind of model started to pop up. That was never the case. But was the case very often when you worked for an outsourcer. That very, very often, the buildings were absolute rubbish. And you still find them, they are like cowsheds, they are cold, there is nothing around that is, you know and from real estate point of view.”

Employee engagement is an issue with outsourcing. However, respondent CM2 pointed out that this can be improved if the parent company effectively managed the relationship with the client:

“There are a handful of parents[companies] who do the engagement piece very well. And but that comes down to how the client relationship is managed between the Outsourcer and the vendor manager of the firm.”

She also pointed out that

“There was a time in Outsourcing ten, fifteen years ago.... where it was not common to have to be fully open and fully transparent how things were going. When that started to change, and contact centres allowed vendor managers to come into their site whenever they wanted to be on site.” CM2

Respondent CM2 gave an example of her experience about an improved relationship with a client:

“I had a relationship manager sitting in my contact centre every day all day. But what that did, it made it very transparent. So, there was nowhere to hide, and the relationship was very close. That means that your employees, they feel much more part of this of the Outsourcer community and delivering service on behalf of somebody else.”

Therefore, investments from the leading company are more related to the parent company managing the relationship with their outsourcer and vice-versa. In addition to their main brand, often a leading brand, the parent company will introduce a sub-brand, which is usually a basic and cheaper brand. They usually do that to save the cost and present the product with fewer features but at a cheaper price, mostly digital-only brands.

“And [Inhouse 5] is the main company, but they have a sub-brand like a sister brand. And it’s basically liked a no-frills [brand]. It’s just cheap [products]. The overhead of having all that stock, so you’re able to sell cheaper. So, it’s just like when the companies want to diversify their brand and play in different segments of the market, and that’s why [it] was born.” CM8

Speaking about the cheaper brand, CM8 explained that there was no telephone contact. It was all done digitally:

“I’ve got to say it’s not a call centre. It’s a contact centre, but it’s not called [that]; we’re all digital. So, I’ve got a team in Mumbai in India who do web chat, and then I’ve got a team that sits in. They are all working from home just now, but I’ve got advisors that sit in the UK as well that do complaints and social media.” CM8

This section will examine the data to understand how inequality regimes manifest across in-house, outsourced, and international call centres. The findings indicate that outsourced call centres exhibit more pronounced "ideal worker" regimes, characterised by expectations of long hours and uninterrupted work. These requirements tend to disadvantage women with caregiving responsibilities. In contrast, in-house call centres were found to have more rigid organisational structures, which offer greater flexibility but perpetuate gender-based segregation within different functional areas. The findings suggest that the degree and nature of gendered dynamics varied across different call centre settings. In-house call centres were observed to have more resources available to develop and implement gender equality policies. In contrast, outsourced call centres were found to rely extensively on monitoring and control mechanisms, which contributed to more deeply entrenched gender inequalities. The increased resources available to in-house call centres enabled them to allocate budgets for diversity and inclusion initiatives and maintain more robust human resources departments. These in-house call centres were better equipped to address discrimination complaints and enact family-friendly workplace policies. Offshoring and nearshoring are

beyond the scope of this research, although it is worth pointing out that from Table 4.4, it can be observed that most of the call centres have outsourced parts of their business to other countries or nearshored them. Moreover, about 80 per cent of call centres internationally perform their operations in-house, meaning that companies' operations are based on their premises. In this environment, employees provide better customer service as they have a greater knowledge of the product. The in-house call centre provides employees with training to achieve better quality. However, multiple organisations use outsourced call centres, and they provide more flexibility and innovative technologies (Consulting, 2019). Most of the call centres in the research had call centres abroad. It is also important to point out that only 14 per cent of the call centres will be in an offshore location, which is relatively low compared to onshore call centres. As Holman et al. (2007, p. 9) point out. "Call centres typically serve national rather than international markets. Eighty-six per cent do their local, regional, or national market". It can be observed, as Holman et al. (2007) stated, that both onshoring and offshoring are growing at the same time.

4.3 Level of women's representation in managerial positions in call centres

Acker (2006c) (Acker, 2006c). argues that organisational structures are not neutral; they embody power relations and can perpetuate inequalities. In the context of call centres, we can examine how different structural elements might contribute to gender inequality regimes. Acker (2006c) contends that traditional organisations with career ladders still exist, and relatively new

companies also have hierarchical structures. She also points out that in some organisations, certain inequalities are externalised in new segmented organisational forms as both services and production are carried out in other low-wage countries, and often those organisations are legally separate entities (Acker, 2006c).

In her explanation, Acker, (2012b) highlighted the presence of invisible processes within organisations, which she called the 'gendered substructure'. These processes embed and perpetuate assumptions about women, men, femininity, and masculinity, ultimately leading to gender inequalities, occupational segregation, and pay gaps. This section will address occupational segregation and how organisations create and maintain gendered job segregation, pay gaps, and limited opportunities for promotion. Gendered processes, such as recruitment and selection, are significant in HR practices. Training and promotion opportunities are often limited in female-dominated occupations, like call centres, about occupations of worth'. England, P. (1999 p. 743). This research identifies the critical features of gendered divisions. It will discuss occupational segregation, both vertical and horizontal, promotion opportunities, hiring practices, and training.

4.3.1 Occupational segregation

Acker (2006) highlighted that sex is one of the bases of inequality in organisations, and this can be seen in occupational segregation in work organisations, both vertically and horizontally. Gender occupation segregation highlights the inequality in the distribution of women and men in different

occupational categories and job types. In this section, data on women in management are discussed. The data was gathered from the respondents' interviews and represented their views. The researcher asked each interviewee about the number of women and men at each level of their respective call centres. The data was manually calculated, and a percentage has been presented in Table 4.1. Through this, occupational segregation in the call centre will be presented. In this section, both horizontal and vertical segregation will be discussed.

Table 4.2 Percentage of Women Employed in Call Centre Management

Roles in the call centre	Women	Men	Call Centre Type	Interviewee
Board level				
Executive/Chief executive	45%	55%	Inhouse Bank3	CM4
Executive level	0%	100%	Outsource1	CM10
Board level	10%	90%	Outsource1	CM1
Board level	20%	80%	Outsourcer6	CM9
Board level	20%	80%	Outsource4	CM1
Director for customer channel	100%	0%	Inhouse Bank3	CM4
CEO	0%	100%	Inhouse5	CM8
CEO level	0%	100%	Outsourcer1	CM10
Executive/Chief executive	45%	55%	Inhouse Bank3	CM4
Total Average	22 %	73 %		
Operation managers				
Head of the customer service	100%	0%	Inhouse Bank3	CM4

Roles in the call centre	Women	Men	Call Centre Type	Intervi ewee
Head of sales operation	0%	100%	Inhouse2	CM6
Head of the sales operation	0%	100%	Inhouse2(location 1)	CM3
Customer service leader (CSL)	70%	30%	Inhouse Bank3(CM4
Sales centre manager	50%	50%	Inhouse2	CM6
Sales centre manager	50%	50%	Inhouse2	CM3
Operation manager	0%	100%	Outsource5	CM7, K1
Operations manger	60%	40%	Outsourcer1	CM10
Snr operation manager	100%	0%	Inhouse5	CM8
Total average	47 %	53 %		
Team leader				
Team leader	60%	40%	Inhouse2	CM6
Team leader	50%	50%	Inhouse Bank3	CM5
Team leader	30%	70%	Outsource5	CM7, K1
Team leader	40%	60%	Inhouse2	CM3
Team leader	50%	50%	Inhouse public1	CM11
Team leader	70%	30%	Inhouse5	CM8
Team leader	50%	50%	Outsourcer1	CM10
Total average	50 %	50 %		
Customer service level				
Colleague level	65%	35%	Inhouse Bank3	CM5
Customer service representative	60%	40%	Outsource5	CM7, K1

Roles in the call centre	Women	Men	Call Centre Type	Interviewee
Sales advisor	60%	40%	Inhouse2	CM6
Sales advisor	40%	60%	Inhouse2	CM3
Sales advisor	40%	60%	Inhouse public1	CM11
Customer Service	70%	30%	Inhouse5	CN8
Customer service	50%	50%	Outsourcer1	CM10
Total average	55%	45 %		

Source: Author

It can be observed from the data in Table 4.2 that call centres' hierarchical structures are strongly gendered, particularly at the executive level. According to the table above, an average of 55% of customer service level jobs are held by women. At team leader level the figure is 50%. At the level of operations manager and senior operations manager 47 per cent are women, and at the CEO level, women account for only 22 per cent. This shows that women lack representation in these senior levels, and numerically, women dominate the lower ones, as well as call centres overall. It can be argued that this representation of women at the customer service level is yet another part of the pattern of feminized jobs, which is discussed in the literature chapter, Section 2.2.5.

Inhouse5 has a sub-brand of the main company, and it has been recently introduced. CM8 said that companies are diversifying, and a lot of companies have diversification charts where they say that they want to have a certain percentage of women in their management. In Inhouse5, the element of the

occupation or other divisions persist on a small scale, as she highlighted below:

“But in terms of how Inhouse5 operate, they’re very, very diverse, and they’re all up for equal opportunity. So, I’ve never actually in my career at Inhouse5. I’ve never had the experience of actually a man who has got a job over me just because he’s a man.” CM8

CM1 pointed out that in the In-houseBank1, “there’s a decent split’. However, CM4 said that in InhouseBank3:

“When you look at the colleague population, it tends to be more heavily biased towards women. I think that’s, but I think that’s more because that’s the type of job a woman wants, depending on where they are in their personal circumstances. So, it’s a good job if you want to balance it with looking after the family, etc. So, you do tend to have quite a few women.” CM4

She also pointed out that men do not tend to remain at the customer service level:

“So, they come, and they might do 12, 18 months if you’re lucky, but they’re all already itching for the next thing.” CM4

CM4 stressed that it is important to have gender balance in an organisation.

“So, we’ve done a lot of work over the past few years to create a better gender balance...because I think you get different perspectives, and women definitely bring a different, different way of approaching activities that often are calmer, more thoughtful, more curious.” CM4

Respondents CM1, CM2 and CM4 all agreed that gender balance at the CEO level even in the Inhouse Bank is not still 50/50

Respondent CM4 did point out that

“From CSL to then head off, that often is a challenge to get there. And often, they bring non-contact centre people in to do that well, which I find more frustrating than anything else. Because I think you really need to understand call centres to manage hierarchy because you’ve got to understand the nuances; otherwise, you’re driven by numbers that can be manipulated in so many different ways. So But yeah, I think I’ve worked in quite heavily female-biased regimes since I’ve been in contact centres since certainly since I’ve been sort of CSL level and above.”

Respondent CM2 agreed and said that

“I think it’s safe to say that the majority on top-level are still men.”

Respondent K1 pointed out that women

“I think there were more female managers than there were men in Outsourcer5”

CM9 agreed with K1 that there are more women team managers and that she always had women managers in her career in the call centre. However, there were men at the regional managers and director levels. She thought it might be due to the company’s culture.

However, respondent K1 said

“With your managers there I think there were about two women.
And quite a few men, but not that top level.” K1

That means that there were more women at the team leader level, but higher than that were men.

Respondent CM5 pointed out the same point that the client directors are men.

“There are very few client director’s women. Yeah. So, as I said, the higher you go, the less women representation.” CM5

In an in-house call center², both respondents CM6 and CM3 said that:

“It’s probably quite an equal male and female, and probably slightly more male.”

Respondent CM3 also said that In-house² has some improvement at the director level to bring gender equality.

“...We certainly feel there’s been a vast improvement in bringing females into that area of the business into contact centres”

Respondent CM6 said regarding improving gender equality that, the company had a big push on how inclusive there were after the METOO movement. The company had inclusivity days

“Teachings about the difference between diversity and inclusion and that sort of thing”

Respondent CM4 pointed out:

“I think it’s that next step, what makes the next level, which you know, from CSL to then head off, that often is a challenge to get there. And often bring non-contact centre people in to do that well, which I find more frustrating than anything else. Because I think you really need to understand call centres to manage hierarchy because you’ve got to understand the nuances; otherwise, you’re driven by numbers that can be manipulated in so many different ways.”

The ratio of men and women in every industry is different. CM2 point out that

“I would recommend you distinguish a little bit on the industry.”

She said about the Banking sector

“In a banking environment, you can have a good ratio of balanced ratio, men, women.” CM2

In the Hospitality industry

“You really can if you’re going into the hospitality industry. So, airlines, hotels, tour operators, the majority of people delivering the service are female. And I will probably say up to probably 70%. Okay, the men there, they would take the job because they love to travel and they want the freebies, and 20 years ago, we got them. So, at the time when I read a race, I only paid taxes to fly to the beach is fine. So, nowadays, that’s not the case anymore. And it’s a low-paid job.” CM2

The managers have pointed out that technology is a predominantly male-dominated area. An example of this is presented by CM7, who said that in the IT industry...

“At the technical account, so for example, I recently just finished a piece of work in Germany with a client who is a technical solutions provider. The front-line people 80 per cent, I will say comfortably 80% men. Subsequently, the leadership, that management structure in that particular firm, and it’s a big multi-global proposition in that site in Romania, is one woman.” CM7

The reason that Respondent CM7 and K1 said the women couldn’t be promoted to senior positions was due to the structure of the call centre.

“It was top-heavy with men. Most of the managers were men. Most of the team leaders were men, and off the top of my head, I remember three team leaders that were women that whole place. and one of them were..... That was that’s only three women that I remember that we’re team leaders. For the kind of ops managers, it was basically when obviously it was just ... the two men managers.” CM7

Respondent CM7 gave an example of a flat structure in Outsource5 as

“It just felt to me like.... And....., were ending with the bricks, and they were not going anywhere fast. That was to me it was like, you know, the dead man’s shoes, but where you need to be until they went before them, nobody else will get an opportunity to actually become ops managers in there. And I know that CM1 left to become a manager. I’m sure an ops manager with the Inhouse4 because I don’t think she saw a future or stepping up even higher.”

Respondent K1 agreed to CM7 and explained:

“ The positions were not there for people to be pushed to the furthest that people could be pushed to as a team leader, maybe

because then they could create teams and then get a team leader to sort of take over the team. But then that was it. There was nothing else to be created above the team leader because all the managers were still there. Nobody had left, and today they couldn't create a post for them." K1

Most women are in favour of more women in executive positions. However, CM2 and CM9 expressed their disagreement with the quotas system.

"I think if you put a quota in front of a man, they do it resentfully. Right. And you don't want them to do it resentfully. You want them to do it. Because you know what the right reason, I read some really good stats, and some really good articles, women and companies with female CEOs are more profitable globally. Full stop. There are fewer of them. But the ones that there are more profitable." CM9

CM9 highlighted that their company is trying to bring more women into the IT field as they want to present their company as gender equal and present a good image of the company in order to get more contracts. The company is trying to achieve gender balance in the company.

"No women will apply to universities. And we're like got any women on your course. And they're like, dude, and because everyone's trying to hire women, you have to compete with Facebook, and Google and every other tech company that wants these women, and you're like, oh, and so that's one reason why. And then the other thing with the company I work for is that there is some inherent, definitely some inherent biases, and biases, inherent bias. And sometimes in the hiring of men, we hire people for who they know, often not what then also, because we are a company that's about ten years old, and we have some really big clients. But we've still got a few more to land. And we will hire people who have previously worked for these other big

businesses, banks, these other big telcos. And quite often, the people that are in those positions are middle-aged white men. Because we hired that person because they worked for that company for ten years, so we're like, well, we'll hire them because they'll help us get into that company. We're hiring more middle-aged white men. And it's become a huge focus for the company over the past two years to make sure that like we are hiring a lot more women.” CM9

Some of the reasons behind the higher or lower number of women in senior management as are presented by managers. Firstly, about the technical team, CM8 said that men have always dominated it. She thought maybe the reason behind that could be that many women might not be getting college or university qualifications in IT. CM9 said that she is working with an IT company she agreed with CM8. She said her company was trying to hire a data engineer in the UK, and there were very few women who applied for the job. She said that women are not encouraged enough to study maths, engineering, or computing as there is a cultural issue in the UK. This study refutes the claim that inequality disappears in the new economy as the IT sector is strongly segregated and predominantly staffed by men; however, customer service is predominantly staffed by women, yet at senior levels men prevail.

4.3.2 Horizontal segregation

It is important to establish the reasons inequality or equality exists in call centres and in the call centre industry. This section will discuss the structure of the call centre. It presents the organisation's hierarchical structure and, as pointed out in the literature chapter, call centres have a flat structure, and this will be discussed as well.

Within the call centre, there are different teams that deal with the day-to-day business, and the managers may interact on occasion with other support functions of the business. All managers pointed out the flat structure of the call centres. Women are present throughout the call centre management though the majority at the senior director level are men.

The interviewees all commented on the flat structure of call centres, as exemplified by this quote from CM5 about a medium-sized outsource company:

“You would have your advisor, team manager, operations manager, senior operations manager, and then you would go into, maybe, department heads or directors.”

However, CM1 highlighted that a bigger outsource company structure would be

“Advisor, team manager, operations manager, senior operations manager, account director and site director.” (CM1)

Outsource companies work on several projects at the same time; they call every project a campaign. CM1 said that in one campaign,

“You will have team managers, operations managers potentially a Senior Operations Manager depending on the size of the campaign, leading up to a director.”

She also said that in a larger outsourced company, there would be

“10 or 12 layers of people removed from the top of the campaign” (CM1)

In explaining the management career steps, CM2 said:

“You become a Team manager. Yeah. From there, your next step, if you are going the operational path would become you become an operations manager. Yeah. An operations manager usually manages between five and maybe 10 Team managers [and they manage] roughly between 50 and maybe 100 people. Yeah. This is where a lot of women stop.... you then become an ops director.... when I was ops director, I had between 1000 and 2500 people working in my group.”

Besides the main call centre operation, there are many other functions of the call centre, for example, training. CM8 initially started as a customer advisor. Then she became a trainer, training the new people coming to the call centre to become advisors. Another role she did was customer experience manager, in which she tried to improve the customer experience, for example, by looking at NPS scores and complaints through different methods.

“Customer experience, and that is just basically looking at [Inhouse 5]’s customers and like, are they having a good experience with they give us surveys, why are they leaving as bad service? What are the projects that we need to do to make our customer experiences better?” CM8

After that, she became a quality manager. She was responsible for online webchat for both call centres in Glasgow and India, outsourced the call centre and did an evaluation and audits. This role covered a lot of people, as she points out about 5000 people

“You’ve also got loads of teams that support your contact centre. You’ll have people like quality teams who look after making sure that you’re compliant. And you’re looking after your customers. You’ll have maybe

reporting teams who look after all the reporting of the operation will also have, you'll have like resource planning teams." CM12

Another function within the call centre is the time management team CM13 explained it as:

"So, the team that looks after you know, how many calls are coming in, how many are being answered, you know, are the advisors on hold are they on Rab monitoring that kind of live performance of the contact centre to make sure because most of the contact centres especially the outsource ones will have within their contract with their main company." CM13

"Usually very clear specifications of how many calls you are expected to answer as a contact centre. You know, queue times, all that kind of stuff. So, you will always have a real-time team looking after that life running of the operation, making sure that the contact centre is being compliant. And the calls have been answered, you are not getting dropped calls, people have known slugging off, and they've been on hold or going on personnel for 20 minutes." CM13

Another manager added:

"Resource will be look at, do we have enough people to service our customers essentially, and, and you can have multiple, you then have other areas of the business that support that area" CM1

CM13 stated that there will always be a compliance team:

"looking after a quality side of things. I think each contact centre will work differently because again, that will depend on what was stipulated on the contract. So, from an [in house] perspective, for example, we own the Quality Framework and the compliance framework. So that comes from us. So, in regard to [outsource company E], which is our

partner in India, we give them the quality structure that we want them to follow.”

The other section is IT. Call centres have relied heavily on IT, as CM9 explained:

“You will have your standard IT people who are reporting to IT team managers who report into somebody who’s responsible for one system, somebody who’s responsible for that. And then like a Chief Technology Officer, so there’s like, a whole different world for different sections of the business because it’s not just people sitting and taking the phones, which is the area I was in, but there’s the technology that sits behind it.”
CM9

“There are sales, and they need to go out and get new clients.” CM9

An example of a skillset is when a call comes through to the call centre, whether it is complaints, customer service, sales, or retention, so each one is called a skill set, so the support staff are not that many, as mentioned earlier CM13 said that number that is looking after every skillset as follows:

“One person per skillset, so I used to look after the first and second line, then you would have someone else looking after complaints, someone looking after social media and chance and two people looking after commercial, so it was like five of us. So, you would have one person per skillset except me that I was I had two skill sets.” CM13

HR support each area of the business CM12

“You’ll also have, like our go-to-market teams or go to market teams, look at what you’re going to put out to your customers and how that will impact the contact centre if we advertise a new product, for example,

do we expect X amount of customers to call us if we do we need more people at this time.” CM12

All these functions in the call centre will report to the head of the call centre

The Call centre Advisor generally deals with the customers on the phone as CM2 points out:

“We’ve got the colleagues on the phones.”

Advisors work in teams, and in between the Team manager and the advisor, there is the role of Deputy Team Leader (Dcel). As with agents, these titles can vary, and Dcels are often called Associate Leaders. In this role, the person is still an Advisor but has more experience, so they assist the other Advisors as explained by CM2:

“We’ve got a roll called Associate Leader....and they’re really happy to help with the general queries of the day and more of the instant support required for colleagues.”

CM2 also said that they have a similar role in their company as well, called Floor Walker:

“You can become what we would call a subject matter expert or a Floor Walker..... and you have more time off the phone.”

Then there is the Team Leader role, who is responsible for managing a team of call centre advisors.

“Then you’ve got the Team Leader role. In my company, we’re looking for them really to create some of the transformation activities. So really understanding the voice of the customer, the

voice of the colleagues, what are our complaints telling us, how are we handling complaints? How are we making the most of that really? They're responsible for around 15 colleagues." (CM2)

The number of agents a Team Leader manages is different in every call centre, as seen between CM4 and CM2. Respondent CM4 said that in the call centre, a team leader manages "15 people". While CM2 said in her call centre a Team Leader manages "let's say 10 or 12 Agents".

For an In-house (bank), the structure is presented as there is a role called operations manager. This role is about managing Team Leaders. Each Operations Manager will have between 6 to 12 Team Leaders reporting to them, as explained by CM4. CM4 points out that next, there is the role of the Operations Director. Subsequently, there is a role called Customer service leader (CSL). It is also called customer service director. This role is about strategy for the customer service operation and delivering that strategy. Up to ten operation managers report to CSL. They also have three associates.

"Then you have the CSL sort of customer service leader? And they're responsible for around Well; they have 10, direct reports of seven leaders, three associates, and the responsible for about 120 colleagues, full-time colleagues." CM4

The Head of customer contact service is responsible for supporting over 800 service advisors.

"Then above, that is me. So, the head of customer services. And then I report into the director for customer channels. And then the other person then is the exec. So, the chief exec above that." CM4

CM4 and CM14 give very similar in-house structures, even though one was in a bank and another was in the communication sector.

An outsourced call centre management structure can be different from an in-house one. At the first two levels, for example, the structure of customer service advisor and manager level in both in-house and outsourcing are the same up to the operations manager level. In addition, the responsibilities of the operation manager include people management as well as managing their performance other responsibilities include:

“You’re also responsible to a large extent to the client. So, I didn’t just manage the people... I would have to you have to present the client, right, I would have to go in and do quarterly business reviews, with the client, explaining why my operation performed that the way that they did, and what their results were. And so, there’s still a lot of client management. I contacted the client, especially in the last post, because we were based on the client site. I sat three desks away from the client. So, there’s a lot of client management as well as people management, as well as KPI (Key Performance Indicator) management.” CM9

CM9 added that after the operations manager, there is a call centre manager or site manager. The site manager usually has different clients within their building. Then she said about the Glasgow site-building. She said it has four floors, and for different clients, you have a call centre manager, and each call centre manager has four operation managers for each client. They also have senior operation managers, whose job is explained as follows:

“they trust to oversee and only come to them when they need them. You just create a slightly bigger hierarchy. But again, it depends on the site,

the location, the number of clients, the headcount, as well, so you're not going to give a call centre manager one account if that isn't the case of 100 people." CM9

This particular outsourcer was an international call centre. It has an office in many locations in the UK and other countries, so she added that the site director in this call centre would report to an area or regional manager, meaning whoever was responsible for Scotland. The regional manager reports to the area director, the directors from the north, the director for the southwest etc. They will all report to a more centralised function.

"So, for, like the UK, you will still have a C suite, you'll still have a chief operating officer to the UK, you'll have, you know, a chief customer officer, and maybe a chief financial officer, you'll still have them for each country or continent. There still be there will still be senior people, really senior people that they all kind of roles up into for like the UK." CM9

The structure of the government call centre presented by CM11

"So, the top of the tree is the Chief Inspector... And then below that, there are senior civil servants, and they're all directors. So, I was one of the senior civil servants, and I was divisional director for customer services, but in customer services, that included all support functions, which were the HR, the IT and, and then all the call centres as well. So that was like its own little bubble in, and then in the other divisional directors, there were the divisional directors for school inspection, that that was split into north and south of things. So, there were two for them. There was an IT director as well because there's IT going on elsewhere outside of the call centre. And then there's HR director, so, you kind of

have that because of the size of the customer service and the call centre bit I had accountability for parts of the IT parts of the HR, but I joined into the main IT direct to the main HR director, and there is like matrix management from of the IT and the HR. Ultimately, day to day it was mine, but then, For bigger funding projects, it went into the main IT director. And then below that was the usual line manager. So, you got an ops manager, a Team Leader and a frontline member of staff.” CM11

However, what is noticeable is that there is not much difference between an in-house and an outsource call centre except in an in-house structure. There are more management levels at the top of the hierarchy. Overall, the structure of the call centre is similar to that all respondents explained.

One outsourced call centre has different clients; for example, given by CM9, the operation manager has to depend on the client or accounts. She also pointed out that if you are an operation manager, you are usually dedicated to one client

“Because you need to understand the different things that people are measured against the quality aspects and the intricacies of the clients. And that’s almost impossible to do both well.” CM9

Even though call centres have a reputation for having a flat structure, and it is argued that there are limited opportunities for promotion, it can be observed that there are at least six or seven levels of management. However, while the call centre might have more layers in its organisational hierarchy, there are large numbers of employees concentrated at the lowest level of Customer Service Advisor level where a larger number of women are working. Much

fewer are working at the management level, and they are performing similar jobs. The finding in this study in terms of the structure of the call centre is similar to that of Belt (2002). In this research, we mainly focus on the manager role and above; however, there are other support roles in contact centres, too, as you can see from Figure 3.3 and Figure

4.4 Conclusion

Sections 4.3.1 and 4.3.2 answer the first research question: what is the level of women's representation in managerial positions within call centres in Scotland? In order to answer this question, the researcher focussed on the gender composition of women and men in call centres. The researcher also analysed the number of women in horizontal and vertical occupational levels of the call centres. This was done in order to identify if there was occupational segregation in call centres and, if so, whether this was vertical and/or horizontal. Occupational segregation is a key element in the shape and degree of inequality and can highlight areas that organisations should address.

Data was taken from the ONS Labour Force Survey that showed that, overall, more women than men are employed in outsourced call centres and in customer services generally. When the interviews were conducted, it was confirmed that this was also the case in all the respondents' workplaces.

However, research also showed that there is little, or no data collected or published on the number of women in management in call centres. Nevertheless, the data obtained from the respondents provided interesting information about occupational segregation in management in their call centre

workplaces. At the level of first-line manager (Team Leader), each respondent advised that the percentages of men and women were roughly equal or there were slightly more women than men. This fits with research by Belt et al. (2010), in which they pointed out that half of the call centre first-line managers were women and pointed out that above this level, there are not many management positions available due to the flat organisational structure. This was confirmed by the respondents, who stated that Team Leaders and Operation Managers had to resign if they wished to progress their careers. Often this involved moving to another call centre.

The research respondents also confirmed that the percentages of men and women at the level of Operation Manager were also approximately equal. However, they confirmed that there were fewer women above the Operation Manager level, with the numbers being worse in outsourced call centres. They also pointed out that most senior management positions were filled by men, regardless of their place in the hierarchy, maintaining the feel of a “boys club”. Therefore, this thesis provides clear evidence, albeit limited, of vertical occupational segregation at senior levels in call centres.

The flat organisation structure is not the only reason that staff in the Customer Advisor role do not seek promotion. The reasons presented by the interviewees were that the customer service role is the type of job employees want due to their personal circumstances, which is similar to the view of Belt (2002 p.43), who suggested that a large proportion of the employees working in the call centres never move from “bottom rung” of the call centre and added

that these employees fell into two categories. Firstly, it consists of employees who made a decision that they are going to stay at the customer service level due to their caring commitments and secondly, some of the employees who are working part-time wish to remain working part-time, which the research shows is not an option at the level of Team Leader and above. However, unsurprisingly most of the interviewees had looked for promotion, and many still were looking for a promotion. This view is similar to that of Hakim (1996), who contends that women employees have to make a choice to be “career women,” and these are women who are committed to their work and give priority to their work commitments. Seventy per cent of the respondents in the research were in this category and were really looking to be promoted. However, in line with the criticisms of Hakim’s theory, for some women, a career was not a choice. For example, some of the respondents were single women with children to support. It is worth pointing out that in most call centres, all managers have to work full time and usually long hours, and therefore in working as Team Leaders, they will have already shown commitment, which will help them to be promoted. Only one manager said she wished to stay at her current level, and she had worked in the call centre for a long period and was waiting for retirement.

As previously stated, data from this research suggests that within call centres, women are hugely concentrated in customer service and first-line team leader and operation manager roles. Still, at the lower levels of management, the numbers of Scotland’s call centre managers are greater compared to the representation of women in the EU, where only one out of three managers are

a woman, while in the call centre, it is about fifty per cent. However, this equality does not seem to transfer to more senior positions, which is in line with the findings by Eurostat (2020).

The respondents also stated that company culture plays a crucial role in having fewer women at the top level of management. This supports the findings of the International Labor Office (2019), which suggested that globally women are over-represented in support functions like administration, with men inclined to be working in operations, research and development, and profit and loss. These professions performed by men are viewed as critical experiences for Board level positions and to become a CEO.

The research has also shown that more men than women are more likely to be found in IT in call centres. The lack of education in IT, cultural norms and no role models were pointed out by the managers as the reasons behind the lack of women in IT, which were similar to the finding from OECD (2018), which pointed out reasons such as the difficulty of access, affordability, lack of technological literacy or education, together with other factors including inherent biases and socio-cultural norms which lead to lack of women in the IT. It is worth pointing out that some companies in the 'tech' industry are trying to push for more women within the industry. A study in 2017 by PwC shows that only 5 per cent of the leadership position in the tech industry are held by women in the UK (Rafi, 2020). This was also emphasised by the managers who worked in the tech side of the call centre, stating that overall, the representation of women in this sector is very much less, both generally and

in management. They pointed out that it could be due to culture in the UK or that there might not be many girls studying it at university.

Occupational gender segregation has been part of the debate about gender inequality. A high level of segregation has been related to the pay gap and constrains women's career progress (HIE, 2017). The concentration of women, both vertically at lower management levels and horizontally, indicates inequality (Blackburn and Jarman, 1997). Finally, it can be said that vertical and horizontal occupational segregation was present in call centres. In terms of vertical segregation, the percentage of women in management in call centres decreased as the level of jobs in the hierarchy increased. Consequently directors, CEOs and senior officials tended to be male and were highly paid. This shows that there is a glass ceiling, and it is harder for women to progress to senior positions. This is in line with the existing research and statistics on the representation of women in management outlined in the literature review.

4.4 Factors that manager think constitute gender inequality in call centres

4.4.1 Pay Gap

This section presents the wage gap element and shows the wage difference in the call centres and the data regarding the wage gap in the call centres. Acker (2006) pointed out that the wage gap varies with the height of the hierarchy in an organisation. Acker highlighted that women are usually at the end of the wage hierarchy. In the research, the respondents were asked about

the pay gap and their views on the pay system in call centres, and they were also asked about the new rule regarding the gender pay gap that the government introduced, namely that all organisations with more than 250 employees need to publish their gender pay gaps (Vinnicombe et al., 2019). All respondents were aware of the gender pay gap.

CM1 said:

“I don’t think we’ve ever closed that gap fully.”

Respondent CM1 further added that

“It is difficult to quantify because... you’ll find when you start to move up is that you are promoted from within. And you’re given a smaller pay rise for, the fact that you’re learning if you like.”

She pointed out that most managers don’t know what their fellow managers are earning.

However, CM1 gave an example of a situation when salaries were discovered when she was working with Outsource4,

“There was a big cull of team leaders. And they recruited loads of external team leaders. I think I was on seventeen and a half thousand which was not great pay for, a team leader, even at that time. And then we had a restructuring programme. Everybody had to re-interviewed for their own team manager jobs. There was maybe about five or six that were successful keeping your job and so to reward me for that I think I got a 300 pounds pay rise which barely covered the cost of the suit I bought for the interview process. So, by that point, I’m still not even on £18,000. They then went and recruited externally and recruited heavily on

men and brought those men on £23,000 a year so a huge amount more than I was earning and by that point, I was an experienced manager. So, it felt desperately unfair to me at that point in time.”

CM1

All of the senior managers and top executives interviewed didn't know about the salaries of their peers, and those are being paid above them. The respondents also added that they put a lot of trust in the organisation regarding pay. A noteworthy point highlighted by CM4 was that:

“ I think we tend to go softer on that, and just be grateful for what we get. Rather, rather than actually being quite bold and brash, and saying, No, this is what I think, to that role. Yeah. And I think that again, I think it's just a bit more of a male trait.” CM4

She also added:

“But I think the other thing we struggle with, as women actually [is to] know what we're worth and what to say we want to get paid.”

CM4

The same point of being aware of the pay of others was also made by CM4:

“And if I'm doing a job worthy of a certain salary, that I should be paid, if you're going to pay a bloke that amount. You know, I mean, and, and there's a lot of governance surrounding now. But unless, unless I see somebody else's salary, I'm never going to know whether or not I've got parity in my pay.” CM4

CM3 pointed out that in terms of lower-level employees and managers, salaries are also not disclosed:

“So, when we recruit, we always put the starting salary for advisors and team leaders. We always advertise that internally and externally. However, once they’re all recruited, we don’t disclose what their salaries are.” CM3

CM3 and CM 8 also said that their organisation is aware of the pay gap, as there was a big debate about the company’s pay gap.

“Because those that have come internally have had years of pay increases, and then when they are an advisor, and then go to Team Leader, they feel that they’ve got probably a better salary. But then what some of them found out was the external guys were coming in higher, or the external team leaders because they were saying, you know, we’re used to this kind of salary with our company, I’m not going to come to you for anything less. So, we had to do a review last year where we had to close the gap between internal and external pay. And so, there was a difference of £11,000 difference between the team leaders. The review wasn’t just done in one site. it was done across all the contact centres, and they’ve closed that gap now” (CM3)

Respondent CM2 gives an example of the pay gap in a big Outsourcer1.

“ I left my job at Outsourcer1 at a salary level that was just around the 100,000-pound mark, which I thought was a really good salary. I saw after I had left, yeah. And I researched and started my consulting practice. I learned, oh, shit, my male colleagues made 150,000 pounds per year. So, the pay gap is certainly still there. But we are not the only industry.” CM2

However, at the agent level, CM7 and K1 said that there is no pay gap.

Respondent CM7

“Will get paid equally, and that was it.”CM7

When it comes to paying between an in-house call centre and outsourcing, CM6 said that

“Outsource call centres are not well paid.” CM6

Comparing the pay system in the call centres. Both in-house and outsourced call centres' pay system is similar.

“And I think, you know, negotiating your salary still plays a part in it. But we've got a grading system. So each role has a grade attached to it. Each grade has a salary bracket on it, usually between seven and 9000 pounds from the lowest to the end. So, you know, a particular grade, so a grad D would be, you know, starting salary would be 32,000 pounds to 40,000 pounds, within that. You know, when you get a role on when you get a promotion, it's definitely when you get an internal promotion because depending on what you're getting paid. So, you may be at the top of your salary bracket for that grade. And then when you move to a grade higher, you know, it works differently, but you always offer to negotiate your salary. Okay. It's not encouraged. And I think for a woman. It's a lot harder to negotiate salary.” CM13

Since 2017, organisations with 250 employees or more must submit a Gender Pay Gap report under the Equality Act 2010 (Gender Pay Gap Information) Regulations. The report must be submitted to the UK government's Gender Pay Gap Service and must also be published on the organisation's own web site. The data that organisations have to submit includes the mean and median gender hourly pay gap, the percentage of men and women receiving bonus pay and the mean and median gender pay gap for bonus pay. In

addition, organisations must report the numbers of men and women in each of the organisation's four pay quartiles (Government Equalities Office, 2021).

The Gender Pay Gap Service allows access to each organisation's information and also has a facility to allow a comparison to be done by downloading the data for all organisations in each Standard Industrial Classification of Economic Activities (SIC) code to an Excel spreadsheet. The code for call centres is 82200, and an analysis of this comparison is set out in Table 4.2. It shows that for mean hourly earnings, the pay gap is 9.7%, while the median is 4.21%. For bonus pay, the mean is 12.88%, and the median is 9.2%. The range of the mean hourly pay gap is from -4%, indicating a gap in favour of women, to 37.3%. The range of the median hourly pay gap is from -2.6%, again indicating a gap in favour of women to 31.4%. As can be seen, the range of the mean gap for bonus pay is -277.8 to 87.3 (Government Equalities Office, 2021).

Table 4.3 Comparison of Gender Pay Gap reporting for call centres SIC 82200

	% Mean hourly pay gap	% Median hourly pay gap	% Mean gap for bonus pay	% Median gap for bonus pay
Average	9.47	4.21	12.88	9.20
Range	-4 to 37.3	-2.6 to 31.4	-277.8 to 87.3	-95 to 75

Source: (Government Equalities Office, 2021)

As stated above the SIC code for call centres was used for this comparison. However, only 47 organisations were listed under this code, of which five were in Scotland and only one in Glasgow. Clearly, not all call centres with 250 or more employees were listing themselves under this code. Further research revealed that a variety of administrative related and head office SIC codes were used by organisations. However, despite this, there is clearly an average pay gap for all companies listed. It is also useful to point out that only four companies had a pay gap where women earned more in hourly earnings than men.

Overall, it can be summarised that a pay gap exists in call centres. However, it was interesting to discover that in senior management, managers, firstly, don't know how much their peer colleagues are paid and, secondly, don't know if there is any pay gap at their call centre.

It is also important to note that managers said when they joined as a Customer Service Advisor, they knew how much their salary, and that of their contemporaries, was because not only was it advertised in the job description, but also it is customary for call centres to pay Customer Service Advisors at minimum wage or just above it. However, they pointed out that later when they were promoted, which is usually internally, they didn't know the salaries of their peer group. In addition, some of the call centres will offer incentives, in addition to a basic salary, if staff meet their targets.

In addition, the managers also said that every company tries to have a 'don't ask, don't tell' policy on pay. Therefore, it is difficult and unlikely for them to discover if they are paid more or less than their male colleagues. About four call centre managers mentioned that their organisation publishes gender pay gap reports, and these companies are trying to close the gap.

The gender pay gap is an indicator of inequality. The data presented in Section 4.4, from an analysis of call centres' Gender Pay Gap Reports to the Gender Pay Gap Service, shows that in the UK there is a mean and median pay gap in terms of hourly pay, together with a mean and median pay gap in terms of bonuses. However, as pointed out in Section 4.4. not all call centres publish their data under the same SIC code. However, data from the ASHE also shows a pay gap in call centres, though this is only for outsource call centres in the UK, and there is no data for Scotland. It is clear that much more data needs to be collected, particularly in terms of the issues this research has uncovered in terms of Gender Pay Gap reporting. McDonald (2015) points out

in her research that more detailed information on occupational segregation and the organisational pay gap can be uncovered from the data published by local government in Scotland. If this type of data collection was to be required by the private sector and so by call centres, it would provide a fuller and clearer picture of these aspects of the gendered substructure.

A particular feature of the call centre industry, pointed out by the respondents, is that wages are not commonly discussed between employees. In the UK, women managers overall working full-time experience a gender pay gap of 15.9% (ONS, 2019b), while for all women working full-time, the pay gap is 8.9% (ONS, 2019b). Some of the managers were not aware if there was a gender pay gap in their organisation, which is similar to the findings by Blackaby et al. (2005) and Lang (2008). In this research, one of the managers only found out about the huge pay gap she had experienced for her job in the organisation at a later date when she became a consultant for the same company.

Some of the managers discussed the culture of the 'don't ask don't tell' policy in call centres. Managers stated that in the senior levels of management, they don't discuss their pay with colleagues. This is in line with research by Duncan (2022) who stated that in the United Kingdom, companies could direct their staff not to disclose their pay, and this is known as 'pay secrecy'. These kinds of practices are usually observed in industries where they give discretionary incentives and bonuses, which could be the reason it operates at the senior level in call centres where the pay is higher, and bonuses are offered as well.

However, the Equality Act 2010 prohibits companies from enforcing this pay secrecy if the employee is discussing their pay or if their aim is to find out if they are paid differently from a colleague on the basis that they are experiencing discrimination. Duncan (2022) further added that keeping pay secret can lead to decreased motivation and can impact employee culture as employees want to be recognised, respected and appreciated, and this is mostly associated with pay and incentives.

Another important point made was that women tend to be softer in negotiating pay raises. They believe in the organisation and think that the organisation will pay them the right amount. This is supported by the finding of Kauppinen (2005), who pointed out that employees' need to negotiate and bargain for pay with the employer is important in general, and through that, equal pay for everyone will be promoted as well.

The managers did point out that at the customer service level, the wages are the same. When recruiting the advisors, they advised that there is no difference between men's and women's wages. Managers also suggested that the wage gap doesn't exist when women enter as customer service advisors, but later, the gap widens when women progress to a higher level.

4.4.2 Organisational processes (Ideal worker)

This section presents an overview of the working time and life balance of managers in call centres. Firstly, work for an organisation in the call centres is discussed in terms of part-time working, presenteeism and workload in Section

4.5.1, while motherhood, marital status and family caring responsibilities are presented in Section 4.5.3.

4.4.3 Part-time working

As set out in Section 2.2, call centres provide access to customers often 24/7, and as a result they have to organise the work in shifts. As a result, call centres have a reputation for offering part-time work. However, this study found that this was really only available at the level of the Customer Service Advisor. Respondent CM1 pointed out that in her call centre few managers worked part-time, as did Respondent CM5. It is important to note that all managers in this study were full-time.

“A few part-time managers. And mostly the bulk of managers would always be full time in outsource. Yeah, there was a few Part-time [managers] one male member and a couple of females. The females were always to do with childcare and the one male that was part-time it was to do with the university. He was studying.”CM5

Respondent CM5 confirm the above point. And added that there is not much for the managers. They need to work full-time.

“ It really depends at a certain level; there is flexibility. I was a team manager, and depending on the project you’re on, you know, they may not have that flexibility.” CM5

However, at the advisor level, it was different across different call centres. She explained that there were a number of reasons. Firstly, there are

“Probably more females that are working part-time and mothers who have come back from maternity, they’re on reduced hours.”

CM5

Secondly, she added that

“Some may be... studying as well.” CM5

It is generally accepted that call centres can provide students with job opportunities as they offer some flexibility that enables students to work around their studies.

Finally, she stated that

“Some might have reduced again because of the community and the cultural expectations. Some females have said that they need to reduce their hours to care for their mother-in-law or their mum or someone they care for as well.” CM5

It is important to note, therefore, that there is little opportunity for the women wishing to build a career in a call centre to work part-time.

It is suggested that outsourcing companies are making great use of temporary workers and part-time workers. It is also suggested by Holman et al., (2007) that outsourcing call centres offer lower discretion; the jobs are less likely to be covered by union contracts, pay lower wages, and have higher levels of performance monitoring. Holman, Batt and Holtgrewe (2007) indicated that outsourced call centres are making great use of these. CM7 added that they are loosely abused.

“A lot of call centre staff are students. And I think that is partly the reason why. And I’ll use the term loosely they are abused.” CM7

It is observed that women tend to do part-time work, and the majority are women with children that have children in nursery and primary school. The second category is people from colleges and universities that do evening and weekend jobs. Some of these part-time workers stay in the call centre and make it their career.

A few managers said that it doesn't bother them to do a few hours of extra work. But one crucial point is that if you are an operation manager or centre manager, CM15 said that she thinks that

“I used to have a girl who used to worked for me, and she was part-time. And she used to come in at half nine every day and finish at the half, two. And she was a centre manager. So, she was managing 200 heads. But the bottom line is, it just didn't work”. CM15

She said that the manager was really frustrated with her career. She thought:

“Her career wasn't what she wanted to be. And I was like, I hear you but the bottom line is, if you've made, you've made some of these decisions yourself do you know what I mean it's just frustrating I think people get frustrated because at the end of the day, you know that you're not doing the best in the parent front, you know, you're not doing the best in the job front, and you are sort of as a woman, you're stuck in the middle of that thinking how do I manoeuvre through this.” CM15

4.4.4 Presenteeism and Workload

Overall, this section will present the findings on assessing presenteeism and workload. Though call centres create more employment opportunities, several factors are causing stress in the workplace, including presenteeism and overwhelming workloads. Long working hours were indicated by most of the Respondents.

As an example, respondent CM5 said that she

“Was paid for 40 hours a week. But sometimes I would do 60 hours a week. But see, the other 20 hours I wouldn’t get paid for them is just that I had so much work to do so much admin to do that, I couldn’t finish. So I was there, the agents would come in, and they would go, and I was still there all the time, every single day, every single day, for all those years that I worked in call centres, it was all the time the same, the same.” CM5

CM1 agreed with that and said that the company:

“Would expect you to do more hours than you would actually be contractually paid.” CM1

Usually, the operation managers contract for 40 hours:

“ I could work fifty, fifty-five hours a week in that role.” CM1

She said that she was not recognised for those long hours working:

“There are people like me contributed to that from the opposite side. Because we, people like me, would do the extra work, but you’re not getting paid or recognised for it.” CM1

The research found that managers at the Team Leader level and above tended to have long working hours. This was due, in great part, to the highly target-focussed nature of the job. The managers were responsible for their subordinates meeting targets, and, for example, sometime agents would have a longer call, and until every agent was off the phone the manager would have to stay. It is also important to point out that this overtime was usually unpaid and only occasionally paid.

The same issue of more responsibility when you are in the senior position is expressed by CM11, saying that sometimes she had to be working till late 11 or 12 at night as there would be some nights that you are dealing with some serious situation, and I had to stay at work till two at night she added that with the senior-level job you take on more accountability, and you can't just leave your work.

“When I walked out the building, so that's the other thing about being in a more senior position is you can't just walk out the door, whatever anybody says, if something is going on, like systems that crashed, or, you know, we were short of staff or anything like that, then the hours are different the hours and more than you would be working on a frontline role.” CM11

Some managers had to work night shifts as that was the only available way to get the experience they were looking for to progress. Usually, they would do that for six months or a year, and then they would rotate to a shift during the day. CM9 said that if you were working the night shift, she would have been

paid slightly more, but she did say that shift did negatively affect her relationship at the time.

However, CM8 stated that she does work long hours, but that is through choice. She does not have childcare responsibilities. She pointed out that this might adversely affect women with children.

K2 said his company offers flexible working hours, reduced hours, and part-time work. And that the company has supportive policies, but these require understanding managers to implement them. Some other companies, too, are changing. CM12 highlighted that her In-house call centre is introducing more flexible working hours where they can offer it or where it doesn't impact the business—some wellness and mindfulness for the employees. However, she did say that in her company, it is still not common practice. Overall, it can be said that most of those working part-time or flexibly are at the customer service level, and most of the team leaders and above believe that they work long hours.

This section discusses the process and practices in the call centre and how the work is organised. Acker (2006) contends that work is usually organised in the image of a white man having no other responsibilities outside work, that is, a person who has no responsibility for childcare or family demands and works long hours. Because women have more responsibility outside work than this work, the organisation of the work is, therefore, an important factor in maintaining gender inequality in the organisation.

This section discussed the organisational process in a call centre and shows that the ways in which the work is organised disadvantages women. It demonstrates that how the work is organised affects women who have responsibilities outside of work. It also examined working hours, part-time working, presenteeism, and household responsibilities, again focusing on the ways in which these adversely affect women.

Acker (2006) contends that work is organised in the image of an 'unencumbered white man', who has no responsibilities outside work that affects his ability to do his job. This was found to be the case in Scotland's call centres. The shifts were about ten hours long, and some senior managers had to travel. Many women in the research have children, and some of them find it difficult to combine their work and childcare responsibilities, especially those who are single mothers. These difficulties are noticed by women climbing the career ladder, so some of the women decide that they are not having any children until they are in a stable position in their careers.

As stated in Sections 4.5 and 4.8, call centre culture plays a crucial role, particularly in terms of presenteeism and the need to travel. Long working hours were also discussed, and some pointed out that the different shift patterns and night shifts were how their work was organised. Some would say that is not a requirement of the job, but they must do it. As CM11 pointed out that you can't just leave your work when you are in that position. Women could work part-time at the customer service level. However, when they are promoted to team leader or above, managers stated that they could not get part-time work.

4.4.5. Motherhood, family and caring responsibilities, and marital status

Organisations have different processes and practices that they use to achieve their goals. According to Acker (2006), these processes and practices contribute to the production of gender inequality. The development of these processes and practices are usually guided by textual material, for example, books studied on post-graduate courses such as MBAs, by employees themselves, or they're developed by managers that are influenced by outside information from, for example, the EHRC and CIPD (Acker, 2006).

One of the key policy and practice areas relating to equality is how organisations deal with motherhood and caring responsibilities. This is also linked to Acker's (2006) degree of awareness and legitimacy of inequality.

All respondents were probed about parenting and housework responsibilities, and it can be noted in Appendix Five that about half of the women in the research are mothers. A few had younger children. The rest had grown-up children but shared their experiences of managing childcare and work.

Half of the respondents that didn't have children pointed out that it would have been difficult to progress if they had children:

“I don't have children, which makes it probably a wee bit easier for me.”

CM1

CM 12 agreed with CM1 on the above comment, and CM12 added that my husband and I are both career-focused, so she decided to focus on her career

and be in a secure role. She thought that was a little selfish, and she wouldn't give up her career for anything. She thought, however, it might change over the next few years. She was not sure. She didn't have children as she thought it would affect her career progress. She had to change companies to get experience and knowledge, and she said that you don't have a maternity leave package when you change jobs. She had to work for a year to get a maternity leave package. She said:

“Women always consider all these things when deciding to have children and their impact on their careers.”CM12

Most managers without children pointed out that if they had children, it would have been a barrier to progression to the job they wanted; therefore, they had to decide between a career and having children. For example, CM9 said

“I have always had a career goal... I can't have kids because I need to get to that next stage. And then once I do that, then I think about kids. And then once I do that, and then and I'm not with that partner anymore, but I have been in a relationship since long term. And we are again. I put it off and said, you know, we'll do it after this. And I don't know if you know, everyone says if you wait for the right time to have kids, you'll never have them. And here I am. You know, I'm single again, and I have no kids. I'm 35. So, I may have made a great mistake.” CM9

A few women who prioritised having a career instead of having children thought that they might have made a mistake, and a couple of women who have children blame themselves for not giving much attention to them. CM8 thought that if she had children, she wouldn't be able to progress. She provides an example of her sister:

“She had a daughter and took a year gap, and then when she went back to work, she went back to part-time because she wanted a part-time nursery, which stalled her career.” CM8

CM13 and CM11 also pointed out the consequences to career progression, of having children:

“Do I want to have kids and understand the impact like? I think it is naive as a woman not to have that conversation with yourself. Because the reality is having kids will impact your career, and it will impact your career progression.” CM13

CM 11 added

“Barriers to progress are childcare and home life. So, I'm getting home at six, seven o'clock at night cooking tea, or trying to look after the house because, you know, I feel like I want to be giving up all the things I feel I should be doing. So, it's, it's, it's just doing all that as well. That's, that's the thing you either need to be able to take on or not.” CM11

Working hours also stop some women from progressing to managerial jobs and beyond, and one manager said that that had been a big issue in that particular call centre. It is the working hours. The manager asked two of the customer service advisors why they did not apply to the manager role in that company. They replied it was not due to confidence; it is due to working hours. Managers need to work full-time, and that is difficult for women with children and caring responsibilities.

“They'll say no. I'm confident, but I don't have the time. Unless you can give me only 25 hours to do the job, that's fine. I can do it. But they're like, you know, I can't run a team and do my home life on 25 hours a

lot. I can't give you the results you're after. So I'd rather just stay as I am as a sales advisor." CM3

In terms of women with children CM14 also mentioned the invisible barrier; she was unsure if she was ever assessed in the background for being a parent and had not gotten the job:

"And people think she's got a young baby. Maybe she's not the best person for the job." CM14

CM14 added that being a single mom did affect her career progress. She thought that she could not offer so much to the job as she had caring and house responsibilities. She didn't want to race ahead, try to get promoted, and not cope with all that at once.

Respondent CM5 was divorced, currently with her boyfriend. She said:

"We don't live together, so he's helping just as much as a boyfriend would help." CM5

And regarding her son, she added that if she had to travel for work, she would find a friend through an online moms' platform, so her kid would stay with her.

"So, I actually met a couple of mothers who have their kids the same age as my son. And I actually already asked around, like, I particularly became very good friends with this girl. And I actually asked her Listen, if there's any travelling in the future, with my work, can I leave my son with you, you know, overnight for one or two days or whatever? And, of course, I would be paying for it or whatever. And she said, Yeah, no worries." CM5

CM5 and CM13 also added that it is really difficult for women with caring responsibilities to travel. She told a story about her colleague as part of her job. She has to travel abroad. That was the requirement of her job to travel, so she agreed at first

“We were very close. And personally, it was an exhausting time because her husband works full time. Yes, her husband's mom helps them with the kids because they've got two kids. One that is about eight, and her daughter is about five, I think, but it just brought up an entire conversation of her saying, like, what do I do? Like, my husband works full time. I can't just leave my house for two weeks.” CM13

However subsequently because it would have been so tough for her, she had to ask the company to send someone else. Regarding managing career and motherhood, respondent CM4 said that she had her daughter when she was 29 years old, and she was clerical level at the bank. She went back to work full-time as she didn't want to be labelled as a part-time mom.

“I made a very conscious decision to go back to full-time work when I had my daughter at 29. and I did it because I was still clerical at the time. I hadn't even got a leadership role. But I was very conscious of that, and I think it's down to those...conversations or the things you hear, but I didn't want to be labelled as a mom and part-time mom. I knew if I went back part-time, I'd still do the same hours. I would do this full-time because you just end up doing more. And I didn't want to be paid less. So, I made a conscious decision to go back full-time.” CM4

She added that her husband was doing a 9-5 job and he's "never been a career person."

So, he "did the dropping off in nurseries and then picking up", and when the child became school-age, her parents would help.

"My mom and my dad had to come and take some of the pressures of taking the kids to school when they got school-age. So, taking on picking them up. And if they were ever sick and touchwood, I've been very lucky [her daughter] has been an extremely healthy child. And then my mom would go and do it [look after her]. CM4

One manager, CM8, pointed out that she doesn't have children, but it shouldn't affect her career progress, and women shouldn't be judged on this in the interview process. She thought that the only thing that holds back women in their careers would be experience. However, she pointed out that women usually miss out on opportunities when they are on maternity leave.

"For example, you know, a couple of my friends have missed out on a promotion because they've been off on maternity leave. And they didn't know that that rule had become available or something like that, whereas I have never really had an extended period off work. So, I've always been abreast of what opportunities are there." CM8

Explaining her childcare arrangement, CM2 said that she is from Switzerland, and there, if a woman manager, it is common to have an au pair. She added:

"I always have an au pair; otherwise, I would not have been able to do what I did. By that, I mean an 18-year-old girl that was

coming into my household stayed in my house looked after my children.”

Among all the respondents, respondent CM2 has the most children.

“I had three children... they’re all grown-ups now. They’re all out of the house. But I always needed somebody to help me look after them. And I didn’t have my family because I left Switzerland with the children. So, it was always an au pair.” CM2

She also said:

“It was always cheaper to have an au pair. She was living in my house rather than bringing the children to a creche or nursery. It was cheaper to have that girl living with me. And what we always did, we offered the girl, you know, the room, the food, whatever else. And we paid for her language studies, which normally, people come to learn the language if they do au pair. Yeah, but it worked.” CM2

Regarding the house responsibilities respondent, CM4 said that she that cleaning is not in her priorities, and she has a cleaner who comes once a week to clean.

“I have to admit I’m not I’m, so I am not a very good housewife. And cleaning does not come to the top of my list. And so, the cleaner comes in once a week and just does a couple of hours. And she just makes sure the place is spick and span. And it wouldn’t be to my mother’s liking in terms of the deep cleaning, but it is what it is, and then I have a girl who comes and cuts the grass once every three weeks. that allows me to and then be quite lazy on the home front so normally it would be the weekend would be for me to chill, cover off a few things that I might have to do for

work. So, I do tend to be able to switch off now from work at the weekend.” CM4

For those in relationships, they spoke of their partner’s role. Regarding her husband’s role in the house, CM1 said that he still has a traditional role.

“We probably have quite a traditional role in the house. But it’s very amicable. I don’t think either of us iron. I don’t buy clothes that need ironing anymore. But I typically do to things like, you know, the washing and we both clean bathrooms.” CM1

She also added that her husband doesn’t favour cooking; however, he will empty bins.

“I tend to cook because [he] doesn’t enjoy it, but he’ll empty bins, which I didn’t do, and I didn’t touch the dishwasher. You know, so some of the housework roles we have are probably quite traditional. But there are other ones with it’s just that this is what works for us, you know.” CM1

In the research, there was only a male respondent, K2. He had two children, and he and his wife were working full-time. He said that he needed to think about getting his work-life balance right as an issue. Other than that, he didn’t see any other problem regarding his career progress. He said the grandparents help with the children. They have that support available. Sometimes he had to work over the weekend, but usually, he works 9-5 Monday through Friday. He said, as far as housework is concerned. They split it among each other.

“I mean, there are things that that are I maybe not so good at, like the actual washing and stuff like that. Sometimes I made mistakes there,

and other things like, you know, doing the dishwasher and floors and you know the laundry and all that kind of stuff, I can do that, so I would say it's probably 50/50 we have jobs that will allow you to do like the washing and My wife doesn't do the bin or anything like that, so you know dog walking and stuff is my job.” K2

When I asked CM14 about her childcare arrangement, she said she was fortunate when her daughter was young, she was working in a bank, and they were flexible in terms of changing working hours to suit when she was a baby. She was doing training, so the call centre was flexible in terms of starting and finishing work, and that helped her a lot during that time; however, on domestic work, she said she had to do most of the housework

“I think it is a bit of both. I think you know, when you speak to the majority of girls on my team, I would say girls, they are all women. I would say the majority of them do most of it as well. There's no do I do even split there? Yeah, I think that that is quite cultural because I think men think they work harder.” CM14

When explaining her childcare arrangement, CM15 said that she started part-time as an agent, and then she got an opportunity to go to a contact centre down in England to become a secondment manager. At that time, her daughter was at school. Her parents looked after her Monday to Friday in Glasgow, and she visited at weekends. During the summer holidays, she thought she couldn't manage and needed to come home to Glasgow. When she spoke to her manager, she advised her to bring her daughter to where she was working. She didn't have any childcare arrangements. Still, luckily, she had her friend moved there, and she was on maternity leave. She made an arrangement with her that she would leave her with her friend. She got promoted there to the

manager role later than she arranged to have somebody to look after her daughter. She could only afford that as she got a bonus. Her basic salary was 18,000. She said she found it really hard being a single mother and working full time. Later the bonuses were reduced, and she had to come back to Glasgow. She told about an incident that:

“Things like an example would be one day that my childminder was getting a divorce. And she said to me, remember, you need to pick up your daughter from school, she is at a lawyer. I forgot because I was at work, and I was so busy. And I forgot and then like my boss came in at a meeting because I said look where is (your daughter) the childminder phoned, and I forgot about that it was like five o'clock at this time and was it and eventually what happened [her daughter] had walked home realise that wasn't the walk to childminders and all this stuff has went on. But it really was a wake-up call. Because I was like child needs to be my sole focus. so, I came back to Glasgow. And stayed probably. I stayed with [that job] till my daughter was 16. The day before my daughter's 16th birthday, So about another seven years.” CM15

In summary, it is clear from the research that women managers without children believed that it was difficult for those with children to take the same approach to career progression that they had. Those women managers with children took a number of approaches to their careers. Some decided to halt their career progression due to childcare responsibilities. Others continued but had to do so with support from their families or childcare organisations such as au pairs, childminders and nurseries. They pointed out working hours are not in favour of women who have children. Most of the married women said that they were responsible for doing most of the housework, for example,

looking after the children, shopping, ironing and washing. Therefore, the above factors, do influence women's career goals due to the difficulties of combining childcare, domestic life and work life. As noted in Section 4.5., at the managerial levels there is not much flexibility in terms of part time or flexible working so for the women who were planning to have family it was really problematic. These findings suggest that working and other responsibilities like household and caring responsibilities are one of the greatest barriers to the career progression of women in management. Eagly and Carli (2007b) emphasised that women are usually the ones who take the pressure of family responsibility more than men. They still continue to be the ones who interrupt their career due to these responsibilities. They also take more time off, and if they can't balance it, they will change to part-time work. Part-time work is common in the UK. Lyonette et al. (2011) said that women use part-time work to balance care and work responsibilities. When women change to part-time work, it negatively impacts their career progress. Part-time workers are usually penalised in terms of low pay and fewer training and development opportunities.

Marital status and motherhood are also part of the shape and degree of inequality. Half of the women in the interviews had children, while the other half did not. Those who did have children had developed individual childcare arrangements, while those without children believed it would be difficult to combine motherhood and their career. The childcare provided in the UK is provided privately (Menon, 2023). It is very costly, as is pointed out by the managers; therefore, they had to find alternative ways of seeking help from

parents or friends, which was challenging for women. A childcare survey in the UK by Coleman and Cottell (2019) stated that the average cost for a child under two years for 25 hours is £127. In Scotland, 50 hours of childcare for three- and four-year-olds is £242 for 50 hours a week, which is £12,6000 a year. That is, in some cases, expensive for the managers in the call centres as they are paid £28,000-£32,000 a year. Therefore, managers said without the support of family and friends, it wasn't easy to manage. It is important to point out that it is the Scottish government's policy to provide 30 hours per week of free state-run nursery school places for all children aged 3 and 4. However, state-run nurseries only operate in term-time, so many managers have to use private nurseries (Scottish Government, 2020).

One of the managers who found it challenging to manage childcare and long working hours had to reduce her working hours. She changed the working hours to 10-3. When her daughter was in school, she would be at work. Her career was halted during that period until her daughter became sixteen years old and then changed to full-time. That is consistent with previous research. Managers discussed the work and family conflict, especially one of the managers who has a daughter. She said that she couldn't balance work and family since their call centre management job was more demanding (Buckalew *et al.*, 2012).

It is also important to point out that women with children who work often have feelings of guilt, and this was the case with several of the respondents in senior positions with children. They had this feeling of guilt, and they thought that they could not give their children a lot of time.

Connell (Durbin, 2017) stated that the gender division of labour in the home should also be considered when discussing gender inequality. Interestingly, all the women said that they do most of the housework even if they work full-time. This is similar to the findings presented by Eagly and Carli (2007b), who examined a time-diary study that records what people are doing during the day in 24 hours. In 2005, in the United States, women spent 19 hours on average per week on housework compared to married men, who spent 11 hours. Even though this has improved, the situation gets worse when childcare responsibility is added. The same was the case with managers in the call centres, who highlighted that while men do share housework and look after the children, they still do most of the housework and childcare. Research published by the Scottish government (2020) showed that women spent 127 minutes per day on housework and cooking, while men spent only 75 minutes per day on these tasks. The research did not specify the housework and cooking duties or how this was divided up.

New section To summarise, call centre culture plays a crucial role, and managers pointed out that they are working long hours and need to be available at all times, which can affect and conflict with their other responsibilities at home. Some pointed out that they had to travel and needed to go to different call centres, and some women couldn't do that. The next section will explore the degree of awareness of gender inequality by organisations and their view of its legitimacy or otherwise.

Acker (2012) posits that the factors that constitute gender inequality are part of the organisational substructure. She pointed out the invisible process and

practices in the ordinary life of an organisation and what assumptions there are about women and men. The key features of gender inequality were discussed in the conceptual framework, with the most common inequalities being occupational segregation, the pay gap, motherhood, family and caring responsibilities, marital status, workplace behaviour and interaction (Sex Discrimination and sexual harassment). These inequalities will also be discussed in the following sections, beginning with the pay gap. Occupational segregation was discussed in Section 2.5.2.

4.5 Barriers women face and navigate while progressing in management

4.5.1 Recruitment, selection and training

Both internal and external recruitment was discussed with the interviewees and training was an issue highlighted by the managers. Overall, call centres have a high employee turnover, so they are constantly recruiting people. CM10 explained that her call centre, Outsourcer1, would recruit at least 15 people every week. In terms of training these people, it was pointed out that at the Customer Advisor level, staff had an induction and roughly about two weeks to four weeks of training. The training in the financial industry was more intense, lasting about six weeks at the customer advisor level.

Sometimes, Customer Advisors are recruited for a specific project, and the length of training depends on the complexity of the project. It can be from one week to two months. The best example one was given by CM13

“Outsource2 were amazing in terms of the training that they give their staff; correctly was two months of training, which is unheard of really. For contact centre environments, it was two full months. And the detail that they gave me and was able to learn during those two months was amazing, super valuable.” CM13

It was clear that call centres do internal recruitment for promoted posts. CM4 explained the reason:

“We're really big on internal promotion just because you want to develop and nurture your talents and bring them through and give them the opportunities and the roles. Higher up, as I said, are less frequent.” CM4

However, the majority of the call centres provide very little or no training when staff then move to the Team Leader level. The respondents stated that they had to learn on the job as part of their everyday work. However, the research found that usually, there is a role in between called secondment or subject matter expert when it is possible to learn other parts of the business.

Occasionally, call centres will recruit externally for Team Leaders, as explained by CM4, who stated that these recruits usually find it really difficult as companies don't have any training for that.

“We had a few years; we'll create about three or four external team leaders. But what we found was, there was no training, no induction training for team leaders. So I had to also train us to put something together for them. But even what they put together doesn't set them up for success. So, unfortunately, what we found was...one left. They said it's not the place for me, the other three worked so hard, and they put in extra time. And even down to like sitting with the advisors and watching them work to understand what advisors do, and how our

systems work because there's no training around it. So externally, they have the hardest process when they come in. They've got to be so resilient because there's no real support for them.” CM4

There were also concerns raised about internal recruitment. Respondent CM6 pointed out, what she termed, the sneaky way of advertising and filling internal jobs based on personal relationships and links to management.

“It was two girls... with the role models getting promoted. They were both females. They were both in relationships with other managers.”
CM6

An incident by CM9 was also discussed where she was looking for an Operation Manager job, and she couldn't get it in that call centre as the job was not being advertised. Instead, the managers were cherry picked from different operations and got promoted. So, her manager had to speak to HR to investigate that, and she was told that eventually, she would get the job when more clients were available.

CM10 said up to the Operation Manager level, recruitment would be internal, but at the executive level, it is external. She said the preference, though, is usually internal. The reason that they want to hire internally is that they know about the business. She explained that in her organisation, the company has recently brought one woman in at executive level

“She had loads of skills, and that she brought to the table and has done really, really well and done really well in the change in culture and approach. And there is still a way to go, but, um, yeah, she was brought in externally, and at the same time that we were looking at gender and that gender was an issue.” CM10

In summary, most call centres' common practice was to promote internally. Only if they can't fill it internally, then they hire externally. Still, for senior positions, they do external recruitment as well.

4.5.2 Promotion opportunities for women

It has been highlighted in an earlier section that Advisor and Team Leader roles are dominated by women in most of the call centres. There are different progression routes to senior management level, through managers turn over creating an opportunity for the promotion. If you can't be promoted, you can go sideways to support other parts of the call centre. There is call monitoring and HR. Some managers, if they couldn't get an opportunity within the outsource company, would apply to the parent company.

During the Christmas period, some people usually get an opportunity to do a secondment and later try to get a permanent job. To get promoted, most managers had to take extra responsibilities to learn more skills without any monetary reward solely to get a promotion. Networking also provided opportunities. Some outsource call centres were huge and had branches all over the UK. If a manager couldn't get an opportunity within their call centre, they would try to get a job in a different location; however, a flat organisational structure seems to be a barrier within a call centre. The reason presented for women working at the Team Leader and Advisor level was that they have the required soft skills. So, it is important to find out if these skills held women back.

The standard route for promotion was stated by the respondent CM1:

“I worked as an Advisor for in Outsource4 as a customer service at that time. And I was an advisor for maybe about 10 months and then applied for a promotion and was successfully got back shift team manager, then moved on to..... moved on to a day shift. And I think it was a team manager there for a couple of years...applied for an operations manager role and were successful with that one.” CM1

Having reached the Operations Manager level, CM1 then moved to another outsource call centre, which is expected due to the flat organisation structure

“Operations in Outsourcer11. I moved into their continuous improvement programme. I eventually left there, I think in 2014, to go back to Outsourcer4 and into Outsourcer4 which became Outsourcer10 a senior operations manager of the Inhouse4 campaign and ran a campaign in there for. a ran a few campaigns in there for Inhouse4 for a few years. I then moved over to Outsourcer1,..., and I was there up until 2019. And I’m now working for an In-housebank1.” CM1

Respondent CM3 explained her career history as

“I’ve been working at Inhouse2 for coming up to 15 years. And I started off as a sales advisor...did that for six years.” CM3

Then the next stage of her career was

“Then I saw an opportunity to become a team leader, I did that for seven months, and then I progressed forward to then become a cell centre manager [Operations Manager]. And so, more than half of my career at Inhouse2 has been as a sales centre manager. However, during that time, I have taken opportunities to step away and do a secondment.” CM3

She than progressed to

“There’s a position for sale centre manager coming up with you want to try that. So, I did a secondment, and then I went permanent. So, while sales centre manager, I started looking at running the budgets and running the site commercially as well. And the improvements I’ve made, thus Why then I got offered the job for operations Services Manager for 14 months.”CM3

All the managers interviewed have worked their way up in the call centre. For example, CM8 started working part-time in a call centre when she was at university. When she graduated, the jobs in her own field were not paid well, therefore, she stayed in the call centre. Now she has been working for about 14 years and is head of the customer experience. Subsequently, another manager, CM11 pointed out that:

“You get motivated if you are ambitious and want to work up the career ladder. I don’t think you will get the operation manager or CEO role if you are not motivated because you have more accountability, more involved and are knowledgeable about the issues. It will then become fun for you however she mentioned that you have to ‘Park your family life’ because if you start thinking, oh my God, I’ve got to get home because I’ve got to do this, this or this, then you can’t focus on the work and that becomes stressful.” CM11

The ideal worker norm often disadvantages women, especially those with caregiving responsibility, as it prioritises long hours, constant availability, and single-minded focus on work (Acker, 2006c). The findings shows that most of the manager's progress in the call centre has been done internally, and they went from being an advisor and worked their way up to higher management

levels. However, the interviews have pointed out there are a number of obstacles in the call centre career above the Team Leader role. For many, this is due to the flat structure, which limits the available management positions in the call centres. There are few positions and a large talent pool of people applying for them. They try to get promoted, and when this is frustrating, they apply to other call centres, which is why every manager has worked in many call centres. Some managers also pointed out that to get a promotion, they have to relocate to a faraway location, and they would find this difficult if they had caring responsibilities.

The reason behind joining the call centre job was not a career move for most of the respondents. They entered the industry if they couldn't find a job somewhere else. They joined the call centre as a Customer Service Advisor and were promoted to Team Leaders.

When managers were asked about the reason for joining the call centre, the interviews highlighted that they joined the call centre not because they were interested but because they couldn't get a job elsewhere. They joined the industry at a young age and stayed there. A few joined the industry when they were students working part-time while studying, and they stayed. Some found it easy to join and noted that you can get into this industry due to the high turnover:

As an easy, fairly easy job to get at the time, call centre job can be useful if you are at the beginning of your career and want a job." CM7

"You can always get a job in a call centre." CM7

A couple of managers started part-time jobs while they were studying:

"I started off while I was doing my degree .. just on the phone as a sales advisor (part-time." CM8, CM6

For others it was the prospect of a better salary:

"I needed money to pay the bills. That was kind of the whole thing that it was. So, I started working for Outsourcer1 as a contact centre agent.

"CM10

"I was about 25. And I saw a call centre job as an agent, a temporary call centre agent job for the Christmas period. In my previous. I was managing a couple of gyms. I wasn't enjoying it. It was a lot of hours for little reward" CM9

"Not due to interest. I fell into it like so many other people." CM2

Progression in their current job was also a reason for joining a call centre:

"I left the bank because I didn't feel I was progressing. And I worked there from I was 17 until I was 24. And I thought I'm not I'm not moving, but I wanted to, and I read about a job in Inhouse8. And I thought that was just a call centre for a very new one then. So is how I moved in to call centre." CM14

Two of the managers started at a very young age, at sixteen or seventeen, out of school and college; they started it during the summer break and stayed. Two of the managers started part-time when their daughters were young and later

changed to full-time jobs. Some of the managers who worked in call centres for many years said that they didn't think they would be working for ten or fifteen years in the call centre. There is a further pattern that emerged and related to managers in outsourcing call centres. Primarily, managers were working on projects and once the projects were finished the call centre was then taken over by another company, and the manager was TUPE'd into another outsourcer. Thus, they had to change companies quite a lot, or they would have to go to different companies if they wanted a senior position.

When asked about changing jobs, Respondent CM2 replied

“I wanted to move into the next level of management. The position I wanted was held by a woman that was not moving. She was not moving up, she's not moving sideways, and I found I had nowhere to go. So, I left and then yeah, I got hired by Outsourcer8.” CM2

Thus, it can be said that while call centres provides job opportunities for many women, for most of the respondents joining a call centre was not a positive choice, they tended to fall into it. There were a number of reasons for this. Some took up call centre employment, because it provided student employment, or because they could not find another type of job. However, others joined for a better salary or for progression. There was also the finding that outsource project work meant that staff could be TUPE'd to other call centre employers.

4.5.3 Flat structure (women's career progress to management)

Team managers were asked if they have experienced any barriers in their career progression in the call centre. Many views emerged. Some obvious

ones were lack of promotion opportunities, again associated with the flat structure, lack of support from their manager and family commitments. This is in line with the findings of Belt (2002, 2004) on barriers to women's advancement in call centres.

CM1 said that the only barrier she faced during her career was with Outsourcer1

“There was very much a cliché feel, around it where it became hard to, to manage, because directors would have certain people that they trusted and what was said became the truth, not the results became the truth. And I think that incredibly difficult in Outsourcer1. And to the point I didn't want to work There I took voluntary redundancy from Outsourcer1.” CM1

She said that during that time, she felt that she was feeling like somebody was trying to stop her from being successful. They would put blockers in her way,

“And which impacted my people. Because anything that I would be trying to get would be to improve life for my people which always goes on to improve life for your customers. Always, always, and not always with a cost attached to it, and those would be blocked and that for me was exceptionally difficult.” CM1

It can be said from this case that trust in women was an issue in that company.

It is also linked to stereotyping, which will be discussed in Section 4.

In addition, CM5 explained. That she had to change jobs three times in three years, and she had to take voluntary redundancy.

“Voluntary redundancies from a project.” CM5

Either the project was given to another company or, or she had to go to another company. This finding also relates to the TUPE experience set out in Section 4.7.2.

CM10 pointed out the issues with the flat organisation structure when she was trying to get an operation managerial role. She found it difficult to climb the ladder even though she had a really supportive manager. It wasn't easy to get to the operation manager role because the job was not being advertised, and they would be offered to people known by other operations managers. She added that at the operations manager level, there are not that many jobs available. She said:

“You need to wait for one operation manager to leave to replace them or get promoted.” CM10

She described the process of getting a permanent operations job which involved her:

“Old boss, and my new boss, campaigning for me because they really liked me and they liked how I worked so. Emm, they went out to all the different heads of sites and business managers and area managers. They said, I've got somebody who's really good, who needs a permanent operations manager role. It would be a waste for her to move back down, who's got a job.” CM10.

CM13 pointed out that there are a huge number of women in the call centre industry and said that some of the companies that are quite progressive want to publicly show that they have 50 per cent women on the board. She also stated that she believed that there is a glass ceiling for women, and it is harder

for women to progress. She pointed out that manager support and interest in your development is essential for career progress:

“If you don't have your manager behind you, it's going to be very, very, very difficult.” CM13.

However, not all bosses were as supportive, and she had a manager that was a barrier for her to progress to the next level. She said that he was not good at his job, so he was not letting her be promoted as she was making his job easier, and for most of the work that she was doing, he would get the credit for.

“Reality is in most cases, in many cases, that means that you're going to get stuck, especially if you're carrying someone else.” CM13

This also links to mentoring, which will be discussed further in Section 4.7.4

The respondents were asked about the strategies for women wishing to move to an operations Manager role. CM4 explained that:

“To get a role like mine, you know, until I move on, then I am then the blocker for anybody else coming up. So, it has the opportunity within the company to keep moving out, learning new things to come back to the roles when the roles are available, or going and looking elsewhere to other companies.” CM4

Managers from the In-house call centres pointed out the opportunities for women to progress in outsource call centres are very limited and in addition there is little room for development. However, they stated that this is not always the case in In-house call centres. CM8 said:

“Whereas if you work for the actual company like head office, there's loads of opportunity.” CM8

CM4 also pointed out that overall, her career progress was steady and slow, and she said that if she was more ambitious and wanted it more quickly, then I might have faced more barriers. She added that one of the most significant barriers for women is their confidence, and she thought that might have been one of the reasons for her slower career progress. She said she wouldn't apply for a job until she was confident that she could do it. However, this is not the case with men. She said that in her opinion:

“They are pretty happy to wing it an interview whether they have done it at all or not.” CM4

CM15 agreed with CM4 that confidence helps in career progress. She said that

“I think people identified things in me that I didn't identify.” CM4

The respondents also stated that there were salary implications for those wishing to become a Team Leader. They said that overall, there is not much difference between the salary of an advisor and a team leader. In addition, occasionally, the advisor would take home more salary than the team leader due to bonuses, and so the advisor then begins to question the point of getting a promotion:

“The problem is where we're going and in management, as sometimes the difference between the management salary and the agent salary isn't that much different.” CM15

On the contrary, CM10 has worked in the customer service level for seven years. when asked about the reason for not getting promoted for so long, she said that:

“I've never been career-driven. To be honest, a lot of the opportunities that I've had have really, I suppose I can try to be natural, just natural progression. And I've never, I never set out to think I want to move up or that I wanted to do it long term and definitely didn't think I'd be still in the same company 19 years later.” CM10

It is worth noting that this was only the case with one of the respondents.

Managers were asked about their future career plans. Those interviewees who were in their 50s were thinking about their retirement and were happy where they were CM4 said that:

“I think I found my forte. So, my forte is operational management dealing with people.” CM4

CM15 agreed and said:

“I don't intend to do anything after this, so I probably plan to work maybe another four or five years. And I would plan to retire and have a bit of relaxing time.”CM15

Two of the managers who worked for over thirty years are now consultants and have their own firms. One of the managers has worked for twenty years. She started a master's degree part-time but wanted to stay in a call centre after that.

In terms of education, while half of the interviewees had degrees, interestingly, all respondents agreed that education to degree level hadn't benefited them with their career progress in the call centre. Most of the managers started their career as an agent. However, they said that their degrees did help with confidence. Commenting on education, one manager said

“Call centres are more with the experience, I think... it's very much work your way up.” CM14

A few respondents had only graduated from school or college when they began their career in a call centre. Those who only had school-level qualifications had to take some management or other courses. It was pointed out that there is an investment in training and development in Scotland. Colleges offer accredited training for call centre employees. Training and development are essential as technology changes and the industry moves toward the web, knowledge management, and email. Scotland also has a highly skilled and flexible workforce that helped Scotland expand and succeed with BPO (Scotjobsnet, 2016).

Interestingly, after working ten years in the call centre industry, one interviewee decided to do a part-time master's degree.

A person's human capital is often an important factor in career progress; therefore the level of the interviewee's education has been added to the list of characteristics.

In summary therefore, it can be observed that women do face barriers in their careers. These included trust in women and lack of available managerial jobs. Having children, family, and caring responsibility came up as a prominent barrier for so many women. It is clear from this section and Section 4.7.1 that call centres do provide managers with career progression opportunities and in all call centres, there were career pathways, both horizontally and vertically. However, it is clearly easier to be promoted to the Team Leader role, but much more difficult to be promoted to Operation Manager roles, due to lack of available positions and a flat organisation structure. It is also important to note that the Team Leader and Operation Managers roles are still people management roles. The decision-making roles are still filled by men. Similar views were expressed by Stanworth (2000) that men continue to guard areas of power in organisations and dominate powerful high-status job occupations. It could therefore be said that the glass ceiling has been cracked by some women, but it has not been broken.

The structural and situational factors within the organisation that result in the lack of women in management are set out in the literature review in Section 2.7.2. The interviewees pointed out that mentoring, organisation support, networking, education, recruitment and selection assist in women's

management progression. The data on these themes will be discussed in the next sections.

4.5.4 Mentoring

Acker (2006c) argues that interactions in organisations, which are seemingly casual, can reproduce inequalities. Mentoring and networking often happen through informal interactions. The following section will discuss mentoring, networking, and interactions in call centres.

All the interviewees said that their companies have different ways of mentoring. The respondents were highly supportive of mentoring in the call centre. Primarily, it indicates that mentoring remained one of the best ways to inspire and retain employees.

CM3 said that she'd "always had a mentor" and added that:

"[my mentor is] a director for our strategy area. And I'll because I've done a lot of work with her, I want to learn something different. So I've got a new director, who's my mentor...[she is] from the service area." CM3

CM3 also stated that mentoring was useful in a way:

"So we got to understand her area of the business and how all those contact centres work. And so that's why she's my direct. They're my mentors now." CM3

CM3 explained that another reason that she has a mentor is for promotion:

"The aim is to get to director level. But right now, for me to be in that position, I need to be getting across various different parts of

the business. So, I'm trying to get much experience as I can, work in various areas, whether commercial, working on budgets, or working with partners sites."CM3

She pointed out that there were no restrictions in terms of mentoring from Inhouse2.

"In fact, they have heavily promoted me to go get a mentor and support and so that I can then network with various other people to see what more is out their opportunity wise." CM3

CM 14 agreed she has a working group at her company, and she thought it was beneficial. Some of the companies were offering a shadowing activity as stated by CM4, who pointed out that:

"So we have shadowing activities that go on, you know, where they can go to different roles and shadow, and actually see if that's the role that one." CM4.

However, it varies from business to business; CM4 stated that:

"It's easy for me to support colleagues to go and try different things. And then the biggest challenge, I think, for people going up through the ranks, I think there's two: their own personal belief and desire, and preparedness to put the effort in together and not just have it handed to them." CM4

Mentoring was emphasised by the respondents, who believe it assists with overall career progression. This is supported by research by Gayle, Baugh and Sullivan, (2005). Furthermore, Jyoti and Sharma (2015) found that mentoring is closely related to career development. Through mentoring, employees can try new ideas without fear of any punishment. Mentoring tended to be confined

to in-house organisations, where there was more support compared to outsourcing companies, and one reason behind that was the cost of mentoring. In terms of human capital, all of the managers interviewed progressed in their careers based on their experience in the company. They pointed out that education does not have much effect on their career. However, they insisted that in order to get a promotion, it was important for the managers that they had to work in other areas of the business, and for this, they would need to spend more time at work, and usually performing this extra activity wouldn't increase their salary, though they would have to do it to get the experience.

The way mentoring works within call centres is that managers have their senior managers as their mentors. Regarding support for the Customer Service Advisor, there was no proper training for the employees to become Team Leaders. They had to learn on the job, and Team leaders find it difficult to perform the job as well as learn. The same process applied to Operation Managers. They had to get experience in different departments, and usually, that would mean more work without any extra pay. A few in-house call centres had leadership programmes, especially banks, like 'associate leaders' and 'flex to lead', which were pre- leadership programmes.

4.5.5 Networking

In the working environment, networking helps with personal advancement. Networking is beneficial not only for information gathering but also for the sense of collaboration or helpfulness created in the company (Alex-Nmecha, Chinedu and Bassey, Mfon Bassey, 2017).

Some of the call centres understand the value of networking. CM4 stated that Inhousebank3 had a group that provided you with an opportunity to network in the bank.

“We have a group called the SLG, which is like the senior leadership group, which is really you saw execs, go plus one.”

CM4

She also warned that:

“It can hinder you as well, because then if you, if you don’t participate or get involved, then clearly, you’re not giving yourself the best opportunity to be thought of and selected.” CM4

Networking was also supported in Inhouse2 in various ways. She pointed out that the company promote these networks:

“Inhouse2 promotes that brilliantly. I mean, we’ve had, from celebrity speakers to your, you know, local doctors doing guest speaking, you know, talking to people, you’ve got so many different people from different backgrounds, talking about so many different things around whether it’s female-male ratios, or, you know, career progression, inequality, all of that stuff, even differences in salary.” CM4

To CM3 this networking means that:

“They’ve actually unlocked a door around topics that I didn’t even feel were an issue in this business. [They said] No, it is an issue. You might not have felt it...but it is an issue in other parts of the business because it’s a vast business.” CM3

In the same company respondent CM6 said that:

“There were social events that we would do kind of. There was at the end of the first year, we had a first birthday party, and it was kind of everyone went to that. There’s also. they do the So teams, agents, technical advisors who have done very well hit certain targets, and you will get tickets to this event... they’re a big deal to get invited to because it is a big networking option because it’s people from all over the UK.”
CM6

Networking is vital to CM6 because:

“You get to meet very senior managers; if you want to, you get to kind of meet those connections. So those are, those events are big things.”
CM6

On the managers at operational levels, she said that

“They would tend to be training days where they would go off together, and they tend to train them all at once. So, you would meet managers from other sites and senior managers from other sites. It did seem to be there was definitely a new feeling to it.” CM6

Respondent CM2 pointed out

“I mean, how do you create a transparent career path, for example, within your centre, okay. And, you know, if decisions are made, let’s say, on the golf course, and I’m not saying that lightly because I play golf, and I love playing golf, and I learned to play

golf because my male colleagues play golf. So, therefore, for me to fit in, I needed to learn the game.” CM2

She said that it would be difficult for some of the women who have family and need to go home on time:

“This is a cliché, and it’s still portrayed as a cliché that you have to go home. It is not everyone, like; not everyone has got a setup whereby the woman can come home when the work is done, or after the socialising. It is a fact that’s just the way it is. And I’m not saying it’s good, but it’s just a statement. But if I cannot go to these networking opportunities, because I have a family at home, I’m not interested in football; I do not play golf, then it is more difficult to break through that a lot. And a lot needs to still happen. And I’m not saying it’s still as bad as it was maybe 20 years ago.” CM2

CM8 said that the networking in Inhouse5 is more at the team level. Usually, a team will go to the pub after work together. However sometimes men and women separate. It will be a bunch of boys if they are friends. CM9 added that at the Team Leader level, there are few opportunities to network outside work and at the Operation Manager level, there are opportunities to network across different industries and accounts.

“People within different roles, there's probably a bit more training, where, you know, everybody could be called into one centralised site where you can meet people and get talks and things. And there was the odd occasion where I would be brought to, perhaps, a networking event. Ah but, I think until its performance, I think that probably happened to me twice where I went to one was a charity ball event that we bought a table at, and one was in client events because we provided us with an award for excellent customer service. So, they wanted to have an event

for us in our own kind of thing. And I was chosen on both occasions to get to go and represent, but it's not encouraged if the event happens, and you get chosen to go great, but they don't help you create those from happening.” CM9

Respondent CM7 said:

“It is improving at a very slow pace, and it is nowhere near good as it could be.” CM7

Respondent CM4 pointed out another aspect of networking, namely that relationships are built through work experiences:

“That naturally when you are trying to develop a high performing team around you. You are going to bring like-minded individuals and people who have worked well with you in the past.” CM4

CM15 added that you need other managers and people to support you to get a senior leadership role. This links with Section 4.7.3. She pointed out that most of the time, women don't have the time to build that relationship, as she has to invest that time at home and with her family. She added that some women might find it difficult to network with men due to their family situations; they might not be comfortable.

“So, if you're at all-boys group...someone [may] find that quite intimidating and also the partners may find that quite intimidating because like I used to go away and travel. Look, COVID is made me stay at home. But what 9 times out of 10 and an average month, I will be away at least twice a month where I will be with my peer group. They are all men and then me. So there will be things like, well, how would your partner feel if your husband feels if you've been away with three men, every other week going out to dinner forgetting to phone them

because you've just left the office at seven, you went for dinner and drinks with by the time you get back to your hotel room, it's half past 11 you know, he's probably in bed, you're not going to phone him. For lots of people, that's a no.” CM15

CM12 said there was an online forum in her call centre that all employees and senior management have access to. Employees from each department bring their ideas forward and what barriers they are facing in the business. They work as a team to figure out how to sort it, and then they come back with answers to everything that is raised. She thought that is useful in connecting people and sharing your problems and information. Half of the call centres have forums for specific issues such as disability, gender, LGBT, and parents for their employees that they can be part of it and get support if they need to.

Another form of networking is conferences, often yearly conferences that usually happen in some central location where they meet and talk about business performance for the following year. Managers emphasised that technology plays a vital role in networking. The senior managers in the call centres will have coffee morning catchups with executives. Covid19 had a significant impact on the way networking happened. Most networking at the time when these interviews were conducted was online through application Zoom, Teams and Skype. LinkedIn was also suggested to be really helpful in networking, and a few managers were contacted through this application and got jobs.

In terms of networking, one of the managers pointed out that to fit in, she had to learn golf, as she thought that networking is important in terms of knowing that is where decisions are being made, and usually, it would have been discussed by the managers while they were out playing. Eagly and Carli (2007b) also highlighted the issue that breaking through these male networks can be challenging for women, particularly if the network is centred around masculine activities. In order to counteract this, one of the call centres has introduced networking outside work which is more family-friendly, and managers could take their families.

These sorts of out-of-work leisure networking activities are difficult for women who have a family and need to go home. Eagly and Carli (2007b) pointed out that one of the most devastating results of the family and work-life balancing act is women leave very little time for networking and socialising with their colleagues and building professional relationships. Usually, networking is believed as a non-essential part of the work. It usually turns out to be an important element of work.

One manager discussed that when some women were married or had partners, and they were going away or travelling, in her case, she would usually travel with three or four men, which could cause problems in relationships. She always thought about how her partner would feel if she were out after work with a group of men. She said some women's partners would not be at all comfortable with this, so many women would refuse to travel for work in this way.

Fundamentally, all respondents agreed that networking does help your career. In addition, most of the respondents were using LinkedIn and growing their network through this. Therefore, it would appear that this is a useful and helpful platform for networking.

4.5.6 Gender discrimination and harassment (Workplace behaviours and interactions)

According to Acker (2012) and Connell (2006), workplace behaviours and interactions are part of an organisation's substructure, which is created and recreated between employees at different levels of the organisation. It can be between individuals or groups or formal and informal. The interaction may exclude women or include women, especially in male dominant environments. Sexuality can also complicate working relationships Acker (2012). This section will discuss the interactions between managers and behaviours in the call centre. It also discusses gender discrimination and harassment in the call centre.

A minority of the managers in the call centres had experienced sex discrimination. Two had faced race discrimination, while on the other hand, the majority said they hadn't faced sex discrimination at all. So, there were different views among managers about sex discrimination.

CM6 explained a couple of incidents of sex discrimination:

“There's a point where I essentially been sexually assaulted twice within the call centre. And it's one of this. And it's just not, it's just

kind of laughed at. One of them was a manager, and one of them was my manager. they were both parts of the boy's club." CM6

Secondly, she said:

"There was an email chain whilst I was working for Inhouse2, not for Outsource5 I was sitting a manager's desk asking to log me into whatever system I needed. And for that day, and I saw an email that was discussing what hair colour I, I changed my hair colour quite a lot. And there was a discussion as to whether I was hotter as a red-haired or blonde or brunette." CM6

She said he had also asked her "do you think I'm a sex pest?" She said that she did pointing out that: Agents go and have sex with you in the disabled toilet? How do you not think you're a sex pest?

She added:

"He was the person who I was I pushed I was trying to get past someone, and it was in there a few managers and everyone else stood back to let me past apart from him who pushed himself up against the wall and then as I had to force myself, you know, past them with my back to him he then thrust into me." CM6

Specifically, the point about managers was:

"And there were two other managers down there. And he made an exceptionally sexual noise." CM6

As already stated in Section 4.7.8, Respondent CM6 pointed out that having a relationship with a manager would help in promotion.

"It was two girls. So, when I was saying with the role models getting promoted, they were both females. They were both in relationships with other managers." CM6

She pointed out that it was due to the culture of the company.

“It was very reflective of Outsourcer5. But that dynamic definitely carried over to Inhouse2, even when we had, you know, a couple of years on when we’ve been with Inhouse2 long enough that this attitude shouldn’t have continued.” CM6

From the senior management perspective, she added:

“It was very much the pervasive attitude and was ignored by senior management; they were well aware of it.” CM6

CM9 mentioned an incident of sexual harassment when her boss, at a Christmas party, sexually harassed her. She said that sexual harassment should be taken seriously and reported. However, she didn’t report it at the time, as she thought that it would hurt her career. She thought it was just one stupid, drunken moment on the work night out. Then, she explained another incident she knew which was reported, and nothing was done about that. It was just swept under the carpet, and when the same man groped another woman in a far worse way. She reported it, and that person was instantly dismissed.

“I have been in a position with a man in power in the workplace where I’ve been looked at for more than where I’ve been looked at in a non-work way. I’ve been at a Christmas party and had a boss’s hand on my bottom. I’ve had that happen twice with two different men, you know, I’ve been so I, that’s something I’m very aware of. And I think that’s something that’s really shitty for a woman to have to deal with.” CM9

She said:

“On the one occasion where it was reported, the woman manager wasn’t given any support. The second time when it happened, and the manager was dismissed the management was trying to cover it up. It was very cloak and dagger. Why had this person left? And obviously, you've got to be very careful about what you tell people, probably for legal reasons...the company didn't take any learnings away from it. Now, it's never happened, again, to my knowledge, in that situation in that business. But I'm not convinced that anything would have been done differently if it were to happen again.” CM9

CM1 said that within the company she was working for, the higher management was putting blockers in her path. When she used to turn up to the directors meeting for presenting results, her results were excellent.

“And rather than trying to adapt or adopt some of the processes that I use, they will choose to run down your performance if you like, rather than adapt to the work to try and emulate. So, there was a bit of a boy’s club in that way. It was right let’s not all try and improve. Let’s just stick where we are and get ready and that was shocking.” CM1

CM4 that she felt that she had to

“Put in more in an interview or a presentation, then maybe my male colleagues, which, you know, ten, fifteen years later, you could say, well, actually, that’s probably a bit different. Tend to be biased there.” CM4

It seems sexual harassment is happening in the call centre. Another manager, CM10, also pointed out that one of her managers was dismissed for sexual harassment. She said he was ‘an awful guy’. She stated that he was promoted to the service director role and “just

changed because of the amount of power they have in their role". She said that some of the actions he was doing as

"The usual stuff that people talk about, like when you're talking, because I started, I started at 18. Yeah. And so I've kind of gone through from being 18 now to 37. And you still get the whole, you know, men calling you love and looking where they should be looking when they're talking to you or that skirt is not short enough or sometimes just would be verbally abusive, just rude." CM10

CM10 added that the manager was on one occasion quite physical.

"And it was one occasion that he and he backed to me to a meeting room. That was the worst time that was kind of the final straw. He once kicked a wheelie chair from one end of a room to another that just missed my desk by that but that much because he was too angry." CM10

So, she said that it was not only her who was treated like that. There was another woman who saw him behaving like that. She whistleblew his behaviour which started an investigation, and then, later on, he was dismissed. However, he was in that job for one year. She said with age, women become more confident. They would stand up against any sort of harassment and would say, don't call me that. Besides that, she said the location of the call centre, how far away it is from town make a lot of difference as the experiences are different. She added that she thought that it is common in every company. All of the managers who faced sexual misconduct didn't report it. Only one CM13 reported it. She reported her manager for sexual misconduct and sexual harassment. She said she was nearly fired from her job. She reported to the

team leader when he was spoken to that there is an allegation against him, and he was told who had made the allegation and who were the witnesses. He said to the operation the following things.

“That I was terrible at it at this point, I was doing kind of the grad bay, so I was helping people that were advisers that had just come on the phones, I was doing all that kind of training and support piece. He went to the operations and said that he had had complaints that I was rude. And that I was too direct, that was abrupt that I wasn't doing my job properly. That I was lying that I was coming in late, all kind of stuff, and the operation which was composed of one man and two women took his side, and I nearly got fired for it.” CM13

She explained the sexual harassment in work as

“ He was very uncomfortable. Like he started just by making wee comments about how did I look, or, you know, if I had a big bum, or if I did and or you know, those jeans, you look really good, and you and I'm like, this is unprofessional. And again, once again, as a woman, you learn you're not taught but through time, you've learned to just deal with this behaviour. Because if you bring it up nine out of ten times, it will just be detrimental to you. So, I did put up with it for a while. And then the end of it was there one that he actually physically touched my bum.”
CM13

At the point when she was trainer she complained, and he made the counter allegation. After that, she was sent back to another call centre, and she was told that she was not doing her job correctly.

“And then they took everything from me. So, at that point, I had been doing I had been off the phones for ages. I was doing like training. I was doing grad bay. They put me back on the phone. They put me on the

worst shift pattern that I have ever been. And I was working until 11 o'clock at night, most days. Em, I was getting quality marks like every day, like two and three calls, and they weren't making them all terrible. so it goes to the point. I raised the issue with the ops team because I didn't have anywhere else to go. So even though I knew these people had made the decision to punish me, I still had to raise it because I needed a paper trail." CM13

The company didn't do anything, and it affected her emotionally; she had panic attacks, and she was in a terrible place. She had to take time off from work and while she was off, she was contacted by another call centre and got a job there. When she was in another call centre, a friend of hers messaged her that he started harassing her and other girls in the team. She advised them to report, but they pointed out what had happened to her. The girls working there had to work due to their family situation. She stated that this kind of atmosphere harms women's confidence and takes a toll on women emotionally. She pointed out that girls in their early 20s usually find it challenging to deal with this situation. Adding to this, CM14 said that when she was younger, men thought that women weren't as capable as men, and she would see that from their behaviour and the way they treat women at work. However, CM13 said that it changed a lot over time.

Behaviour and interactions are part of the organisation's substructure. This section discussed both formal and informal interactions. The research found that sex discrimination is one of the key informal barriers to getting a senior position in call centres. Sex discrimination was widespread in call centres. It was surprising to find out that 41 per cent of women interviewed had been

sexually harassed during their career in call centres. All of these managers talked about the number of incidents that happened in the call centres and what managers experienced in their work. In addition, 29 per cent faced other forms of discrimination on the basis of age, race, or parenthood, and it is worth noting that these are visible aspects of employee discrimination; they couldn't state how they are judged invisibly.

Another issue regarding sex discrimination is the reporting of incidents. Most of the managers who faced the incident hadn't reported it except one manager, who had to deal with the counter allegation and faced negative consequences. This is similar to the findings by NWLC (2016) that few victims of sexual harassment make a complaint formally to the organisation or to the fair employment agencies. In the UK, according to a YouGov poll, more than four-fifths of young women in the UK have faced sexual harassment, which suggests that most of the women don't have faith that the abuse will be dealt with. (Topping, 2021). It can be summarised that the interviewee's description of sexual harassment is a consistent picture of the harassment in the call centres,

4.5.7 Organisational Career Support

Development opportunities were primarily in In-house call centres, although there were a few in outsourced ones as well. In terms of organisational support for development into leadership roles, beginning with team leadership, Respondent CM4 pointed out that:

“There’s a big leap, I think, from being a colleague into the leader. And unless you’ve got natural leadership tendencies, what we tend to do is promote people who are taskmasters.” CM4

So her company had developed the role of “associate leader” and in this role, responsibilities were:

“To support others and deliver through others and not because you’re ticking a box. And given a number they need to achieve; they need to understand the why. So, we’ve got that rolled [out], and we also have some roles that other companies will have, but it’s sort of developmental, so we call them ‘flex to coach’ that’s teaching them how to become good coaches.” CM4

CM4 said that there was another programme:

“‘Flex to lead’, that’s that pre leadership piece. And also ‘flex to change’. That was for people who didn’t want to really want to go down the people leadership journey but were interested in solving problems, getting curious about things. And so, we sort of put those developmental areas in place. But we have a really good job paging system. And we encourage our colleagues to really talk to us about the things that they want to achieve.” CM4

Inhouse5 has a personal development plan for the employees, where you can work in different business areas and gain experience, which would help you get a position advertised. All respondents pointed out that while training or completing it or doing a secondment, you were not paid for that. That was considered part of your development.

4.5.8 Stereotyping and management styles

Acker's (2006c) framework of inequality regimes (Acker, 2006c) revealed how deeply ingrained societal assumptions are about the gendered shape of workplace structure and practices. One prominent example of this is the persistence of gendered divisions of labour, where certain roles and responsibilities become associated with 'men's work' versus 'women's work'. Acker argues that these divisions are not neutral or based solely on objective differences in skills or abilities. Instead, they are often rooted in deeply held stereotypes about men's and women's inherent natures and capabilities (Acker, 2006c).

For instance, in the interviews, respondents were asked about the differences in management style between men and women. CM1 said that in terms of management style, the "management of the company plays an important role".

She also said that:

"It depends on the size of the call centre as well. A big business like Outsource1 had more of an old boy feel... if you like. [The Board] was far more top-heavy with males than with females, and they admitted they had an imbalance but continued to recruit men into those more senior positions." CM1

CM3 said that, in her experience, women approach activities differently than men

"Calmer, more thoughtful, more curious. And, but not necessarily any less dogmatic. You know, when the male testosterone, I think kicks in around the boardroom table, whether you're female or a man." CM3

On the issue of management style, respondents CM3 and CM8, pointed out that sometimes men can find it difficult to talk about 'female issues. CM8 said that women deal with the emotional side of the employees better and added that men are very process and task-driven

"They've been quite open about it; they find it uncomfortable sometimes to talk to females around sometimes stuff that they're medically going through in their team. And say, 'Can you speak to the lady in my team because I don't feel comfortable?' Now the female she's probably comfortable speaking to her male manager about stuff." CM3

She added:

"Because they're worried that they don't want to say something, and then they get a complaint or, you know, so they're very kind of like worried about these kinds of things. So, I think, because of that, I feel sometimes the male managers become very number and target orientated. And they kind of lose that engagement level at times with their teams." CM3

She said that female team leaders would listen to the employee issue and would give advice. On the other hand, men find it challenging to discuss stress and emotions. CM 15 has provided an example of the softer side of women in management. Women are often stereotyped as being more nurturing, empathetic and better suited for customer service roles or caregiving roles, electing the traditional expectation of femininity.

"At quite a high level, like you could be, I could be as a director and walk by somebody or what is wrong with you today. Because you can just see in the face that something's wrong. And you go, what is wrong? Or

the train broke down. I'm 15 minutes late. And you're like right, just calm down, go and get coffee, get yourself organised to be fine, do you know what I mean, but I think I think probably men are less likely to have that kind of soft side. But don't get me wrong, I have worked for some women who don't have that soft side like. They're just like whom... here it is. I definitely think either there's a difference, but on the whole, you could, you know, you can work for people who just no matter what sex they are, they're quite open-minded about things." CM15

CM7 said that women managers are

"Approachable and they would listen to you." CM7

Manager CM9 said that she finds it easier working with men than women. She expressed that she considers man-management easier. However, she also pointed out that women have always been nurturing, supportive, and keen to help my progression. About her male manager, she said that he took less responsibility for her development. She added that male managers are more laid back and don't micromanage as perhaps women managers do. She said her current male manager is not a control freak and is trusting. She pointed out that she had only one male manager and a few women managers.

CM10 and CM14 said that there is no difference between women's and men's management styles. It is more related to personality. CM14 added that some women, depending on their position, could be complicated and aggressive. CM 15 agreed with CM14, saying that women can be tougher but more organised than men. Men don't tend to say what they are thinking, and they are more reserved in their communication. when there is an issue, they won't be in touch on the softer side. CM10 pointed out that she worked with some

women that would listen to you. Others would pretend to listen to you, but she added that she worked with some fantastic women.

“Some of the women that I worked with was amazing. I've worked with some great men too.” CM10

“I've been managed by men that have been more understanding and better than women.” CM10

There are mixed views about women's and men's management styles. Some managers think that women are more approachable, emotional, and organised and find out that men are more straight to the point, and their management style is more relaxed.

One of the barriers to women's career progress is stereotyping Dipboye (1987). There were mixed views from the interviewees. CM2 associated being competitive with stereotyping. She, however, added that it is linked to the view that managerial positions are only for men.

CM2 stated that:

“I think, you know, when you get into that level, you get into that level because you want that level of responsibility and authority. And, you know, you are naturally competitive. And I think being naturally competitive brings out what you've probably classified as being male gender stereotypes, but I think that I think that they're in women as well.” CM2

CM4 stated:

“It’s just we just label them as being male stereotypes, just because that’s what we used to see more men in those positions. But I think it comes out from women as well.” CM4

Concerning stereotyping, CM5 said that women should work twice as hard and then they will get promoted. She said that in call centres and other industries.

“There are these professional bullshitters who are mostly men. I have never met a professional bullshitter who is a woman.” CM5

Her point of view about women was:

“Women do their homework; women work hard to get the responses or to get where the information they want to get, men just fling it. And they are just professional, professional bullshitters that other men believe. Yeah, this is how contracts get signed. However, a woman I’ve never as I said, I’ve never met a professional bullshitter who’s a woman. Oh, all women, they do their research. They work meticulously and this is why they work harder and longer than men” CM5

She added that women usually work on the lower level of the jobs, and they do all the hard work; however, the credit is taken by the men in higher position jobs. However, she also stated that working with women can be challenging if

“She feels she feels threatened by you. And she just gives you more work and more work and more work and more work. Like until you cannot do it anymore. Until you’re worked out.” CM5

In summary, there was evidence of the male management style being perceived as the dominant one in terms of career progression, as well as the view that women had to work harder than men. However, there were mixed views about stereotyping.

It was evident from the research that many women entered the call centre as a temporary job, and many of the managers stayed in that job for different reasons, which will be discussed. Due to the flat organisational structure of call centres, women find it difficult to progress above the Team Leader position as the number of available jobs is limited. In many cases, they had to stay in the same position until someone left, and they could apply for that job. Flat hierarchies, therefore, create job queuing. In addition, the research found that there are often no formal promotion procedures and that increases the chance of managerial stereotyping (Bielby, 2000).

Managers pointed out that women's and men's management styles is different. There are cultural stereotypes seeing men as a leader (Oakley, 2000). Some of the descriptions used by the respondents for male managers were professional bullshitters, task-driven, number oriented, and they described women's management styles as calmer, more thoughtful, and more curious, organised, but not necessarily any less dogmatic, approachable, and they would listen to you.

This is in line with the report by the CMI (2018), which pointed out that women leaders show greater intelligence and interpersonal skills. These qualities assist in creating a respectful and positive environment. It also added that women were key in promoting diversity at work. The interviewees also pointed out that they struggle if they are assertive. The findings from the same report agreed that only half of the assertive women could rise to senior positions compared to men, for whom assertiveness is seen as a positive trait.

Stereotyping has been pointed out by the interviewees as a barrier to career progress. They pointed out specifically the recruitment of men to more senior positions. When asked about the high number of men at the senior level, they pointed out it is embedded in the culture and that numeric positions, heroic male and problem-solving stereotypes are attached to men, and these are valued by the organisation. It is clear that one of the barriers to women's career progress is stereotyping (Dipboye, 1987). However, there were mixed views from the interviewees. Some associated being competitive with stereotyping, linking this to managerial positions being only for men.

4.5.9 Culture of the call centres

Organisation culture is one of the key concepts, or as termed by Sun, (2008) as “stable factors” in the everyday life of an organisation. An organisation's culture is explained by Acker (2012) as beliefs about gender differences and gender equality or inequality. These beliefs lead to organisations not questioning, for example, the pay gap and gender differences. Usually, an organisation's culture will be affected by the larger cultural environment of the society. This section will discuss the call centre culture.

When asked about the call centres' culture, respondent CM1 said that women's progress in a company is related to the company itself. She worked in different outsource call centres and said:

“In Outsourcer4 if I compare that to Outsourcer1, I believe in OutSourcer1 gender did matter.” CM1

She also pointed out that, in her experience, that is not the same everywhere

“In my experience, it’s not been across the board, I do believe it’s company dependent.” CM1

Respondent CM1 thought the reason for that could be that smaller companies respond to change quicker than the bigger and older companies.

“I believe the company has been around much, much longer. I think it was quicker for Outsourcer10 to change and respond. Where for Outsourcer1 it was quite easy perhaps for people to hide at the top and not be answerable to any of the those, questions? Whereas with Outsourcer10 being a smaller business, it’s very visible where things are in and what you would expect either. So that has been my experiences... bigger companies are slower to react and move with the times than in smaller businesses.” CM1

Emphasising the age of the company, CM10 elaborated that five years ago, Outsourcer1 was very male-heavy, though recently this was changing, and women could now be promoted to management. CM11 added the older the call centre is, the more likely it will be run by old-fashioned people who won't understand people’s needs. She explained a call centre story where people had to raise their hands to go to the toilets, especially when it was busy, but then that company couldn’t get any clients, and they had to change the call centre's culture. Adding to the age of the call centre, CM 12 said that the Inhouse7 culture was more male-heavy.

“ It was a wee bit different. I'd say it is probably more male-heavy, and particularly in the higher role. So, director level and senior level is a lot more male-heavy. Actually, Inhouse7 are very much a male orientated world.” CM12

Respondent CM5 explained that you don't get enough motivation at work in a call centre. The culture is that

"The tone is set from the top...a lot depends on that tone." CM5

She explained her motivation level at the call centre was very low that she finds it challenging to motivate her advisors.

"It's very, very hard. All you can do is try your best to be fair with them[advisors]. But at some point, I think towards the end of my years in call centres, I wasn't motivated at all anymore. And in the end, I was... don't even enjoy being you know, team Manager anymore. You don't even; you just wish you would go back as an as an agent." CM5

Respondent CM7 agreed with CM5 and added that she didn't like the fact that if your performance was not good you would be penalised for it.

"That doesn't sit with me, the punitive stuff." CM7

And she gives an example of her training the employee and expresses her feelings as

"I became a trainer for them. I did five weeks training with people. And I had to keep them motivated and enthused, and all the way, I'm thinking God help you." CM7

This finding is similar to the findings when CM7 talked about stress in call centres and said that the Team Manager role is the most demanding job, stating, "it is a stressful, hectic, very high-pressure job". Overall, managers thought that the culture of an organisation does affect

employee stress levels. Three managers explained the culture of their call centre was more male-heavy. The same call centres were older call centres and have been there for about over twenty years.

CM1 spoke about the reputation and strategy of Outsourcer1.

“There’s lots of things that Outsourcer1 do well and that there is a lot of things that Outsourcer1 have taken on, because what they’re prolific at is buying businesses.... whoever was the board at that time bought up hundreds and hundreds of businesses, ‘TUPE’d’ all those people into Outsourcer1. But in actual fact, there’s nobody in your leadership team as an expert in that field.”

CM1

The buying of a large number of businesses would clearly have implications for an organisation’s culture. CM1 pointed out another consequence of this:

“So, if you’ve not got a good leader, leading, you know, whoever, whatever...you start to, to lose some of this skill, you start to lose some of the integrity that was originally in the business, the thing that would have made it attractive to Outsourcer. And you then get a disgruntled workforce who walk off...” CM1

Furthermore, respondent CM1 added that

“ Over the last two years, they’ve been trying to shed a lot of the businesses they took over to only keep the core of what they’re actually good at... that is one of the problems that the Outsourcer1 has had. They became so big that they actually struggled.” CM1

One of the team leaders who left one company said she hated it so much at the end of her call centre career. She added usually the tone, and culture, is

set by the operation manager. If the operation manager micro-manages, you will need to micro-manage the agents. Usually, in training, you are told that you need to motivate the agents. She said that that is impossible to do that if your operations manager doesn't motivate you. That is why at the end of her career as team manager, she was not motivated, and she sometimes wished that she go back to become an advisor

“You don't even enjoy being, you know, Team Manager anymore. You don't even you just wish you would go back as an agent.” CM5.

CM8 indicated that the image of one of the Outsourcer4, saying

“Outsourcer4 are terrible... I've heard such horror stories from the Outsourcer4.... because, you know what, it's like a lot of uni students will end up in an outsource contact centre just to make more money.”

CM8

This would have implications for the organisation's culture if it were populated by students, who would have their own university culture.

The respondents tended to discuss culture as artefacts rather than values or basic assumptions. However, there were clear differences between in-house and outsourced call centres in terms of cultural artefacts such as training and development. Women's careers can be affected by the organisation's culture. Respondents pointed out the gendered culture in outsourcing call centres and also that the culture of the call centre varies from company to company. They emphasised that changing the culture in a smaller outsourced company is easier than in the bigger call centres. Management plays a crucial role in creating a good culture for the company. However, as Schein (1987) points

out, much culture change is initially at the level of artefacts and behaviour, not values.

One of the issues highlighted about the call centre's culture was its target focussed nature. Managers and employees need to achieve their targets, and they will be penalised for it at the customer service level if they don't. Managers were not happy with the approach. Gait (2010) highlighted that the culture in an organisation should be such that employees are proud to come to work and deal with the customers. If the culture is not good, they won't look forward to coming to work. It is easier for managers to identify what is not right with culture. If the culture is not good, it will impact the call centre's reputation, customer service, and customer service advisors. It is noted that developing such a culture can be a challenge for call centres. It is suggested that it can be achieved by setting achievable targets. It is pointed out that most of the decision-makers in the call centres generate unachievable targets. These unrealistic targets are unachievable no matter how hard the employees work, so it is important to get the target number right and have a plan and strategy to meet the team and communicate it to them (Michael, 2016).

It is also highlighted that if the call centre is older, it will be run by old-fashioned people, and the management won't understand people's needs. Some of the managers pointed out that in their call centre, the management is male.

It can be concluded that the call centre has a gendered culture and that the call centre management needs to influence it and be changed, which will result in improved performance and retention.

Certain factors affect women's career development and progress. Women's career progress is often different from men's, and various factors shape and limit women's progress (Misic-Andric, 2015). It has been highlighted by Acker(2006d) that the organisational substructure is understood by examining the gender substructure. And they can be examined by looking at the company's organising processes and practices, so this question will be answered by focusing on the organisation's sub-structure. Organisations have processes and procedures that affect women's progress in the call centre. This section answers this question by looking at the organising process in the call centres. There is research in the area shows that gender inequality is produced informally and formally (Acker, 2012a; Burawoy, 2021). Therefore, this section will examine these practices that produce gender equality, those highlighted by Acker, (2012a) and those found during the interviews with the managers.

4.5.10 Conclusion

Research question 3 asked: What barriers do women face while progressing in call centre management, and how do they successfully navigate them? This section sets out and discusses these key barriers: recruitment, selection and training; promotion opportunities; the flat organisation structure; mentoring; networking; gender discrimination and harassment; formal and informal interactions; stereotyping; management styles; and organisational culture. It demonstrates that all these barriers exist and women both overcome them and work within them. These all form part of the gendered organisational substructure and are influenced by the degree of awareness of the gendered

organisational substructure, by women, women managers, male managers and senior management and this will be discussed in the following section.

5.1 Policies and strategies for call centres to reduce gender inequality

Research question four is: What effective policies and strategies are available for call centres to reduce gender inequality? However, in order for such strategies and policies to be in place, it can be argued that there has to be, not only an awareness of the existence of gender inequality within organisations, but also a view that it is not legitimate, and this will be discussed in the next section.

5.1.1 Legitimacy and degree of awareness of gender inequality

The legitimacy of gender inequality is where organisations and corporations may find inequality illegitimate, and they will try to reduce it. For some other organisations with, for example, rigid establishments, inequality might be legitimate. Usually, the legitimacy of inequality is affected by political and economic conditions. In the interviews this was discussed in terms of equal opportunities within the call centres. The final aspect of Acker's (2009) framework is about potential solution to change, in particular, the invisibility of the perceived legitimacy of existing processes and structures that disadvantages women.

Except for one of the respondents working in an outsourcing company, the remaining respondents had an awareness of equal opportunity policies in their

call centres. Some of the respondents below explain the gender-equal opportunity condition in call centres.

Respondents CM6 and K2, when asked about the equal opportunity policies in the company, both agreed that their organisations have the necessary policies. However, respondent K2 said that

“Maybe the policies are there because they have to be there.” K2

She pointed out that they don’t implement those policies.

“I don’t think that a conscious effort is being made to adhere to those policies.” K2

Another manager, CM9, agreed with K2 and said there were definitely policies, an employee handbook, and processes like grievances, unfairness, inequality, or bias. There was awareness how to raise it and how to go about dealing with gender inequality; however, she did say that Outsourcer6 was not an old shiny place to work for due to these reasons

“It's not, you know, the pressure of work is unbelievable. And the pay is very poor. And, you know, they don't always look after their people very well, you know, and sometimes, and they're not always the fairest. But there was never any inequality. You know, if you know, if they weren't a good employer, they weren't a good employer to everyone regardless.” CM9

Respondent CM6 stated:

“It did feel a little bit disingenuous when you’re sitting there kind of reading these well-versed policies and documents, little videos

they've done and all this sort of thing, you know. But then you're actually at the ground level; you're seeing the attitudes towards them, it's quite different." CM6

She said that the attitude needs to be changed, and the company should take it seriously to impact employees' behaviours.

"So, it wasn't necessarily that they were writing the policies with earnest, but not necessarily making sure they were landing at the lower levels."CM6

In the same company but at a different location, Respondent CM3 had a very different view and said that:

"I have never felt at a disadvantage. Or I've never felt that I've been being given opportunities because I'm a female." CM3

Additionally, CM3 mentioned:

"Because they're always having to tick things off to say, oh, we're being diverse... and I've always been given a fair opportunity."
CM3

Regarding policies for a fair opportunity in the company, she said that

"They have a lot of policies in place. They have big networks, they have networks, we call them the Inhouse2 networks."CM3

The first network was explained by CM3:

"So, one network, it's about wellbeing one is about LGBT. One is for parents. One is for inclusivity and diversity. So, there's a lot of stuff I believe." CM3

CM3 also pointed out that:

“And every day, I get some kind of communication from the business around all of these networks where we can join, we have guest speakers, we have articles sent to us so that we can broaden our mindset around all these topics, you know, and as a manager, I need to be across all these networks.” CM3

Respondent CM3 said there is no intentional inequality; however, she felt that:

“For some reason, and I feel that the recruitment team probably needs to do more work looking at their adverts, I feel some posts just appeal more to males than it does to females.”CM3

Specific, to the issue, CM3 added:

“And the only time I have really experienced that is probably more when I was an operation services manager because there were so many males and a lot of white males. So that made me did think [that it was because] of that area of the business [which focused on] budgets and numbers.” CM3

CM8 highlighted some of the initiatives that call centres took regarding awareness about gender equality. For example, publishing the gender equality report, they have launched initiatives such as a ‘woman in tech’ program where different women come and talk about their experiences. Women who worked for a long time in the call centre said there was not much awareness in their companies regarding equality before. However, companies have been trying to be equal in the past five or six years. In Outsourcer1, the manager said there is a lot of talk around gender in her call centre. The call centre is trying to be a responsible business and close the gender pay gap in the call centre. K2 added that his call centre certainly has more awareness, and they would get information about what language to use in specific scenarios. CM14 talked

about her company, it is running a program looking to recruit women engineers, and they have a programme to support women.

So, these comments from the interviewees confirm that most of the companies have gender equality policies in place. However, they suggest that there are issues around implementation. Managers pointed out that there are policies in place in their call centres; however, they are not implemented and suggested if the company has the policy, they need to make sure it is implemented.

The degree of awareness of gender inequality is part of the organisational sub-structure. In terms of this, there was a general level of awareness of gender inequality in call centres amongst the women respondents, and they were aware that there was a lack of women at the director level in their organisations. In terms of the organisations themselves, under the Equality Act 2010 (Gender Pay Gap Information) Regulations, since 2017, organisations with 250 employees or more have had to publish details of their gender pay gap on their website, as well as report the results to the UK government. In formulating their report, organisations are encouraged to examine the reasons for their pay gap by examining gender imbalances in starting salaries, bonuses, promotions, turnover, performance appraisal, support for part-time working and support for caring responsibilities (Government Equalities Office, 2021). This should increase the degree of awareness of call centres in terms of their gender pay gap and its causes. It should also, hopefully, educate organisations on the lack of legitimacy of gender inequality.

Outsourced call centres were identified by two interviewees as 'heavy on men', and they had recently recruited one woman as director. One of the managers working in the IT sector said that there are no women in senior positions in the company, which is affecting the company image, so the company is trying to recruit women, so they look good. One of the great examples of supporting women in the call centre was Inhouse1(bank) which changed the entire first floor of the call centre to a creche for their employees. Organisations also seemed to be increasing awareness of the importance of equality and diversity through several initiatives. However, there were also disturbing reports of sexual harassment, though this was increasing viewed as negative behaviour by organisations.

5.1.2 Regulatory agencies

Managers who worked in the communication industry talked about Ofcom and its impact on day-to-day business. Ofcom (Office of Communications) is a regulatory body for broadcasting, telecommunications and postal services in the UK, and it makes sure that people get the best from broadband, mobile services, and watches over radio and television and postal services. Their job also includes promoting competition between the companies. Ofcom provides advice to people and registers complaints from customers and businesses, which assists them in taking action against companies when they let down their customers (Ofcom, 2020). Managers stated that the regulatory agency plays a vital role in the call centre industry. If the outsourcing company is not performing well or has an issue with Ofcom, the company will cancel the outsourcing contract and bring the activities in-house. Two managers agreed

when asked if they think that call centres are managed better when they are in-house.

They both mentioned that some of the teams had been brought back in-house.

“... now that contract is ending, and I believe some of the teams or a couple of the teams are coming back inhouse so I think I think the social media team, and there’s like a payments team, a team of deals with electronic payment stuff. , I think they’re coming back in house and the rest of the campaigns they’re all been moved to the India call centres.”

Outsource1 has lost a contract due to compliance explained by CM13

“Outsourcer1 was failing on a lot of their compliance points. And it gets to the point where do you know the risk is too great.” CM13

She explained that Ofcom is very patient. They usually give you plenty of warnings before getting action. Besides Ofcom, she added, there is also the FCA (the Financial Conduct Authority), a financial regulatory body in the UK. The FCA regulates financial firms providing services to businesses and people and maintains the integrity of the financial market (CfA, 2012).

CM13 elaborated that Inhouse5 company has sales insurance, which means that they need to obey their rules, and she pointed out that FCA is strict.

“For anything that is related to insurance sales, we are regulated by the FCA. Which is I mean, it’s a whole different size of beast...FCA, you have no room.”CM13

She also pointed out the importance of these regulatory bodies and the impact that they have on businesses. Call centres need to keep that in mind before

making any decision or introducing any policy. It can be observed that companies need to take complaints seriously and keep complaints to a minimum.

5.1.3 Potential solutions to reduce inequality

All managers were asked what they thought would be the best solution to reduce gender inequality. They pointed out the call centres need to be more open and honest about their policies and bring awareness regarding their policies to all tier employees. They said companies need to take equality seriously, starting from advertising, hiring, training, progression, and pay. The maternity and paternity leave needs to be reviewed to allow people to go and start a family when it is suitable for them and their personal life.

Being flexible was also pointed out by CM11 who said:

“Being a bit more flexible with things like, you know, working hours, shift patterns, that kind of stuff.” CM11

They thought that would help women as women usually go part-time due to childcare responsibility, and that this shouldn't affect women's careers. And the management needs to be supportive of women. CM11 said companies need to give more thought to shift patterns in a way that fits people's home life, and provide hours that suit, though she admitted this could be challenging. CM11 also gave an example of an initiative taken by Inhouse1:

“They actually...they converted the whole bottom floor of their offices into a creche space. So, people brought the kids in, dropped them off went to work. So the creche was in the building.” CM11

Two managers, CM13, CM8 pointed out that men need to be on board, and there should be conversation and education about gender equality. The younger generation needs to be educated about it as well. Respondent CM4 suggested that having role models will help immensely in the call centre as well.

“It would be good to see, for example, I don’t if I look now, I can’t see an Indian director.” CM4

CM3 also suggested that minorities should be part of the executive and management too:

“For me to aspire to be. And certainly, if I look at the black community within our contact centre, there’s no black team leader, there’s no black call centre manager, and there’s no black head office. And there’s no black director. So that certainly is an area that we need a rap for recruitment.” CM3

She also pointed out that in job adverts:

“The job description makes it more current and relative to show that we’ve got flexibility with working now. And you don’t have to be on-site you can work from home.” CM3

“Need to delve into I don’t know the psychology behind some of these adverts as well, the way they’re worded because certainly more of the analytical and number orientated roles.” CM3

CM3 highlighted the point of number-oriented jobs.

“Like reports and things like that they seem to somehow just always recruit, get a male interest and then recruit from that area.”
CM3

The importance of understanding employees was suggested by CM15 and having the right plan in place for working mothers. They should have mentors and a long-term plan for them and support them to progress in their careers. Interestingly, several respondents referred to the COVID pandemic and pointed out that this offered women the opportunity to work from home. This would significantly help some women, as they could work from home and manage family life. Most of the employees emphasised the better working hours during this time.

The 5.1 points answered the questions of What effective policies and strategies are available for call centres to reduce gender inequality?

6.1 Summary and Conclusion

This chapter has presented and discussed the key themes from the interviews. The interviewee data answered all of the interlinked parts of the conceptual framework. The table provided in section 5.1 links the themes to the objectives and to the framework. It has examined the development of call centres in Scotland and shown the importance of the sector to Scotland. It has also presented details of the different types of call centres. In terms of the shape and degree of gender inequality, it presented evidence of occupational segregation. It showed that despite there being an overall dominance of women in call centre employment, there was evidence of horizontal occupational segregation, with women working in customer facing roles and men working in IT. It also presented evidence of vertical occupational segregation with men dominating the higher levels of management. It found

that it is difficult to quantify the pay gap for the sector's women in management due to the secrecy surrounding salaries in call centre organisations and the issues over the SIC code used in the Gender Pay Gap reports.

The research also examined the organisational processes and practices. It is clear that the flat organisation structure offers only a small number of opportunities for promotion. However, at the junior and middle management levels there is a focus on internal promotion, at least in in-house call centres. In terms of the organization of the work, it found evidence of a long hour's culture in management. It found differences of opinion on management style, but overall, a recognition that many women managers handled the softer aspects of the management role while men focused on the more quantifiable aspects such as numbers. The research found evidence of mentoring, though this tended to be found in in-house call centres. It also found evidence of the importance women placed on networking. The research also found evidence of an awareness of inequality, although this had occurred in more recent years. It also discovered instances of sexual harassment and mixed responses to this by organisations.

In terms of family life and caring responsibilities, information was presented on the difficulties of combining caring responsibilities with managerial roles. Interestingly it also found that educational level did not seem to be a factor in promotion.

This thesis used a qualitative research method to examine gender regimes in call centres, and this chapter provides a synthesis of the results. In light of the

framework, research findings, and literature review, four questions were answered.

Chapter 5 - Conclusion, Recommendations, and Future Research

5.1 Introduction

This concluding chapter aims to review the research, re-examine the research objectives, and demonstrate the degree to which these objectives have been achieved and the research questions addressed. The chapter will also discuss the implications of the research findings and offer recommendations for future research. Additionally, it will explore the contributions of this research, and finally, it will address the limitations and potential directions for future investigations.

5.2 Review of the aim and objectives of the research

The aim of this research was to explore the ways in which gender inequality regimes influence the context of women in management in call centres in order to better inform organisational policies and practices on diversity and equality in call centres.

To accomplish this aim, the research had the following four objectives:

- 1) Establish the level of women's representation in managerial positions within call centres in Scotland;
- 2) Explore women's perceptions of organisational factors that constitute gender inequality in call centres;

3) Identify the perceived barriers to women's progression in management in call centres.

4) Explore potential solutions to reduce the impact of gender inequality regimes on women's progression in management through improved organisational policies and practices.

Firstly, this thesis draws on Acker, Connell, and McDonald's frameworks, which have been reviewed and further developed. Additionally, insights into the call centre industry in Scotland have been provided, explaining its developmental history and the representation of women within it. This thesis has addressed these objectives thoroughly and rigorously by employing qualitative research methods. Thematic analysis of interview data demonstrated that each objective has been met as outlined. Primary data has been gathered directly from managers at the operational level in call centres across Scotland to demonstrate evidence of gender regime practices employed in this environment.

Furthermore, the data regarding managers' perceptions and experiences of female managers has been analysed using thematic analysis, assisted by NVivo, in accordance with the specified guidelines. Finally, the implications of this research have been clearly articulated, and recommendations have been made for the contact centre industry based on the key findings identified in the study. The researcher is confident that the research objectives and aims have been achieved. The following table outlines the connections between the

research objectives, the themes from the results chapter, the elements of the gender inequality regimes framework, and the research questions

Table 5.1 Themes answering the research objectives

Research Objectives	Themes and Sections	Framework	Research Question
Research Objective One: Establish the level of women's representation in managerial positions within call centres in Scotland.	Occupational segregation (4.3)	Occupational segregation	Research question one (RQ1): What is the level of women's representation in managerial positions within call centres in Scotland?
Research Objective Two Explore women's perceptions of organisational factors that constitute gender inequality in call centres.	Occupational segregation (4.3) Pay gap (4.4) Organisational Processes (Ideal Worker) (4.5) Motherhood, family and caring responsibilities, marital status (4.5.3) Legitimacy and degree of awareness of gender inequality (4.9)	Occupational segregation Pay gap Marital status Motherhood Degree of awareness of gender inequality Legitimacy of inequality Organisational processes (Ideal worker)	Research Question Two (RQ2): What do managers think about factors that constitute gender inequality in their call centres?
Research Objective Three: Identify the perceived barriers to women's progression in management in call centres.	Interactions in the call centres (4.6) Barriers and facilitators to women's career progress to management (4.3.5) Culture of the call centre (4.8)	Stereotyping Organisational culture Organisational interactions	Research Question Three (RQ3): What barriers do women face while progressing in call centre management, and how do they successfully navigate them?

	Workplace behaviour and interaction (4.10)		
Research Objective Four: Explore potential solutions to reduce the impact of gender inequality regimes on women's progression in management through improved organisational policies and practices.	Potential solutions to reduce inequality (4.11)	Key elements of the conceptual framework listed above are reviewed.	What are available effective policies and strategies for call centres to reduce gender inequality?

5.2.1 Objective one: Establish the level of women's representation in managerial positions within call centres in Scotland.

Establishing the level of women's representation in managerial positions within call centres in Scotland is challenging. As demonstrated, the ONS collects data on women in call centres. However, it defines call centres as outsourced call centres only and differentiates those working in call centres in SOC 7211. However, in-house call centres can be found across many industries. For example, in banking, women at a clerical level can be found in call centres and bank branches. In other words, call centre employment is not separated from other types of sectoral employment. The same applies to women in management, and, as such, it is not possible, for example, in banking, to separate those managers who work in the different types of managerial employment, including call centre employment. There was a similar finding from the 2012 labour market report, which found that it is not

possible to find data on the industry as a whole, including all sectors (CfA, 2012). However, the women respondents were asked about this, and from their responses, it can be seen that while women are over-represented in Customer Advisors, at the team leaders' level, it becomes equal, and at the Operation Managers, their representation in more senior positions is under-represented, at only 22 per cent.

This research found an underrepresentation of women in senior management roles, particularly within outsourced call centres. Women face significant barriers and challenges in advancing to leadership positions, which limits their ability to influence organisational policies and decision-making. The research investigates the theoretical underpinnings of this gender inequality, identifying the covert and embedded mechanisms contributing to women's slower progression to senior management compared to their male counterparts. A similar perspective is highlighted by (Ely, 1995; Caleo and Heilman, 2014; Metz and Kulik, 2014). This perspective understands gender as an identity shaped by power and status differentials, which are deeply embedded within organisations' social systems and hierarchical structures.

The theories and relationships identified also suggest that gendered social status enhances the categorisation of women and men as different social groups (Powell, 2014), which contributes to the persistence of a glass ceiling that blocks women from advancing to top-level leadership positions within organisations (Eagly and Karau, 2002).

However, it has also been identified that women's representation in in-house call centres is slightly better than in outsourcing call centres. The hiring for team leaders in the call centre was mostly internal, with only one respondent stating that her call centre managers were hired externally, and these were primarily men who were paid better than women managers. Of course, this figure comes from a small sample of women managers and, as such, cannot be generalised to the industry as a whole. However, a key finding of this research and contribution to knowledge is the difficulty of discovering the levels of women's representation in management in Scotland and the fact that more information can only be uncovered through more robust government statistics and further research.

One key factor distinguishing call centres from other sectors is their flat organisational structure regarding the managerial hierarchy, which is supposed to help women in their career progression (Acker, 2006a; Belt, 2002). While it, combined with the turnover of Customer Advisors, does support women's career progression up to the Team leader role, it is difficult for women to progress due to the lack of availability or promotion opportunities. In addition, many of these senior posts are held by men. That would suggest that a flat organisational structure does not help decrease vertical gender segregation, and this fits with findings from Puzio and Valshtein, (2022) when men are working in feminised fields, they are promoted to higher-paying and masculine forms of work more often than women. This contradicts Acker's (2006a) and Belt's (2002) assertion that flat organisational structures help women's management progress. Other aspects of the

inequality regime are also evident in call centres, including less than robust recruitment and selection processes, the importance of mentors and networking and the stereotyping of management jobs.

This research has achieved its first objective. The perceptions of women participants indicate that women's representation in senior management positions is low in call centres in Scotland. Those are a few women who have reached higher organisational echelons. Most women tend to be concentrated in customer service roles at the lower ends of the hierarchy. Both horizontal and vertical segregation were observed in the call centres, whether in-house or outsourced. The gender inequality regimes are manifested in the organisational structure, systems, and practices, which negatively impact women's progression to senior management. The findings align with previous research that has identified the under-representation of women in senior leadership positions.

5.2.2 Objective two: Explore women's perceptions of organisational factors that constitute gender inequality in call centres.

Chapter 4 details women's perceptions of the organisational factors that constitute gender inequality in call centres. As the conceptual frameworks posit, these factors are the shape and degree of gender inequality and the organisational sub-structure. It is difficult to establish the shape and degree of gender inequality in call centres. For example, as discussed in the previous section, it is difficult to establish the shape and degree of occupational segregation. Establishing the pay gap for the sector is challenging due to a

lack of government statistics and weaknesses in the gender pay gap reporting. In this, we have examined a possible source of gender disparities in pay even when women manage to reach similar levels of the organisational ladder as men. However, the respondents clearly stated that occupational segregation in management and a pay gap exist in call centres.

The research showed that despite being a new industry, call centre work is organised based on Acker's 'unencumbered white man'. As a result, promotion is only possible for full-time employees who are prepared to work long hours and travel as required. The research revealed that societal-related barriers are most prominent within which marriage and motherhood during the prime of a career significantly hampered career development. It was interesting to discover that some women were putting off having children until they had climbed the career ladder.

Call centres have a mixed reputation. The offshoring of call centres to countries such as India with cheaper labour costs was problematic, and many companies acquired a poor reputation, particularly for complaints, so much so that sectors such as banking moved their call centres back to the UK. The negative publicity of the call centres, together with issues of high turnover, which still remains a problem, meant that call centres were not seen as a positive employment choice. This is reflected in the research discovery that none of the respondents joined call centres as a career move. Many began as part-time employees to suit their individual circumstances at the time, for example, as students or with preschool children, and they viewed their work in

call centres as temporary employment until they began a full-time career in another sector. However, this is not usually the case in other industry sectors. It is also important to point out that many respondents felt 'ashamed' of working in a call centre.

This perception of call centres as a less-than-positive or accidental career choice is one of the differences between call centres and other sectors. However, their inequality regimes are similar to those of other industries and show evidence of a glass ceiling. Their inequality regimes comprise the same elements as other sectors. The shape and degree of inequality show evidence of occupational segregation, a gender pay gap, the gender division of labour in the home and similar issues of marital status and motherhood. There are also similarities with other sectors regarding the organisation of the work, including presenteeism as well as extended hours and their effects on family life. For an industry that employs a majority of women, its work at management levels appears structured based on the 'unencumbered white man'.

Call centres can take steps to reduce gender inequality in their management. They can develop diversity initiatives that aim to change the composition of women managers in the leadership team. They should recruit, retain, and promote employees into management. For the policies to be successful, managers in the call centre should support them.

5.2.3 Objective three: Identify the perceived barriers to women's progression in management in call centres.

Women have worked in call centres since their inception in the 1970s and 1980s. However, the number of women holding managerial positions is patchy, although women possess higher education qualifications and experience than men. This research investigates the existence of barriers that prevent women from filling top management positions as the proportion of women employees varies significantly across call centres, with more women confined to junior-level positions.

There are a range of perceived barriers to women's progression in management in call centres. These include career pathways that 'filter' out (Bartol, 1978) part-time working women and ensure they remain at the level of Customer Advisor. Women managers also perceived assertiveness as a requirement of their call centre management style, but this proved to be a barrier as it was seen as a negative trait in women but a positive trait in men. Stereotyping was another barrier, with men being seen as leaders and heroes, and the respondents believed these stereotypes were culturally embedded. If these barriers appear insurmountable for many women, mentoring was seen in a more positive light, with organisations offering career support through mentoring and networking, enabling women managers to build social capital. While the acquisition of social capital is encouraged in call centres, human capital is less important. Educational qualifications are not valued as in most other organisations, and lack of these is not a barrier to progression.

In addition, little training and development is offered to prepare women for management. It is also evident from the research that there is often a less-than-robust approach to recruitment and selection in call centres. Most call centres recruit staff internally to promoted posts up to Operation Manager. However, this usually takes a less-than-transparent route and is seen as a barrier to fair selection. This is related to the call centre's culture and its norms and processes that allow gender biases to pass into decision-making. There is a lack of clarity about the promotion recruitment and pay negotiation standards. That is perceived as the reason decisions are made in favour of men. Another barrier related to women's progress is the gender wage gap. In addition, the lack of women in leadership is a barrier (Eagly and Carli, 2007a), a feature of most call centres.

Gender disparities in the workplace are among the critical social issues of the modern era that policymakers, organisations, and researchers alike are eager to understand and amend. These disparities in the workplace are seen as a simple but powerful indicator that something is amiss in how women and men fare in the workplace. The research identified that 41% of women managers said that they had experienced sexual harassment in a call centre. Managers were scared of reporting the harassment as they were scared of losing their jobs. The MeToo movement has made the issue of sexual harassment more public, and something needs to be done. It will be interesting to see if that behaviour becomes less acceptable in the workplace. One respondent has also raised discrimination based on race, which is seen as an area of future

research. In summary, this objective shows many barriers to women's progression into management positions in call centres.

5.2.4 Objective four: Explore potential solutions to reduce the impact of gender inequality regimes on women's progression in management through improved organisational policies and practices.

From the literature, some solutions to reduce inequality can be found. Organisational compliance structures provide one set of tools for change with anti-discrimination legislation.

Using Acker's framework, it was found that managers believe that flexible working arrangements are essential for women and assist them in their career development. Therefore, call centres must provide flexible working conditions, such as working from home and flexible working hours. Having this facility provided by the call centre would assist women in balancing their work life and family responsibilities, and it could be argued that it would also help with employee turnover.

Fostering gender equality in call centre organizations requires a comprehensive, company-wide approach driven by senior leadership. Strategies may include retaining and developing female talent, addressing skill gaps, and cultivating an inclusive work culture. Transparency around compensation and equal rewards and recognition, regardless of gender, caste, race, sexuality, or ethnicity, can further promote fairness. Additionally, providing training on gender and sexuality awareness, as well as family-friendly policies such as childcare facilities and pregnancy benefits, can help

support women's career advancement. Individual factors like education, self-perception, self-efficacy, and motivation also shape women's professional trajectories.

YekinniOjo et al. (2017) The research indicates that for women to progress in their professional development, they must demonstrate increased self-assurance and readiness to embrace challenges. Concerted organizational initiatives to address gender disparities, combined with women's dedicated efforts to hone their skills and leadership abilities, can pave the way for greater gender parity in call center management roles.

Fernando et al. (2014) The research indicates that competencies such as interpersonal skills, leadership, personal integrity, commitment, and adaptability positively contribute to women's career advancement and success.

Shin and Bang (2013) stated that women's lack of confidence to succeed affects their career prospects because they are likely to blame themselves when they fail. Some internal factors noted by Astin (1984) Individual characteristics such as age, gender, race, personality attributes, educational attainment, self-assurance, determination, and drive have been found to shape women's career trajectories. The perception that women's lower self-confidence is a primary factor contributing to their slower advancement compared to men is a common observation in the literature.

Risse (2020). The women managers interviewed for this research were aware of the gender inequality in call centres and noted that, in some instances, call centres were taking action to reduce it.

Regarding the legitimacy and awareness of gender inequality, it is clear from the research that most organisations have equality and diversity policies in place. However, it was equally clear that women managers believed that there were differences between policy and practice. In outsourced call centres, in particular, focusing on tight targets and profits meant that gender equality was not a high priority for most organisations.

Cultural environments tend to be problematic for women when they actively undervalue women's contributions. Addressing this issue necessitates significant changes in middle managers' attitudes, a departure from existing human resource management practices, and a broader acceptance of the need for cultural shifts across multiple industries.

(Elvitigala et al. 2006). Research indicates that organisational culture factors are strongly associated with women's career advancement. Implementing policies to mitigate work-family conflicts may serve as an example of addressing gender inequalities (Greenhaus and Beutell, 1985). Specifically, companies should manage the competing demands on women managers' time, as the interference between work and family responsibilities can contribute to increased stress, health issues, and employee turnover. The research further indicates that organizational culture and policies are key factors in fostering gender equality in career progression.

In summary, this section has outlined a range of issues that call centres could use to reduce the impact of gender inequality regimes on women's progression in management.

5.3 Implications and Recommendations

This research has generated a series of practical implications based on its key findings. These implications are organised in accordance with the key themes explored in the Literature Review chapter. They are intended to inform contact centre management, both at the general and operational levels, as well as senior managers and policymakers.

5.3.1 Implication for Employees and Organisations

The research findings provide a series of practical implications for employers and organisations, offering actionable steps to address gender inequality in Scottish call centres.

Call centres must implement more comprehensive policies and procedures to address and prevent sexual harassment effectively. HR departments in call centres need to play a role in supporting employees' reporting of such incidents. Once an employee shares information about harassment, it must be addressed appropriately instead of discouraging others from coming forward, particularly in outsourced call centres. Employers must also proactively educate managers and employees on acceptable and unacceptable behaviour. Diversity and sensitivity training can help encourage inclusive workplace cultures that respect all employees, regardless of gender.

The childcare challenge is not just an organisational issue but a broader societal one that requires significant social and political transformation. The difficulties women face in balancing work and family responsibilities poses a significant barrier for women to be promoted to senior roles. Call centres must implement more flexible work arrangements and support systems for Managers. Both in-house and out-sourced call centres need to introduce family-friendly policies, such as paid maternity leave, flexible working hours, parental leave, childcare facilities and job sharing for women managers in call centres to combat the gender inequality experienced by women. Call centres should reevaluate their lack of flexible working options and job-sharing opportunities for women managers. Moreover, flexible working hours and part-time work are even more crucial for women, particularly when they return from maternity leave. The call centre culture needs to change, as it does not adequately support women managers who wish to work part-time.

The research findings on gender inequality regimes in call centres and the challenges faced by women in management indicate essential implications for organisations and employers. The issues raised include horizontal and vertical segregation, discriminatory practices, and work arrangements that favour men. Call centre leadership should actively promote women to more leadership and decision-making roles, leveraging the skills and expertise they can contribute. This would empower women with positions of influence, enabling them to positively shape their own experiences and those of other women in the workplace.

To promote women's career advancement, organisations must address the internal barriers holding them back. This change can be challenging, as societal norms and national cultures often influence organisational culture, impacting the workplace environment. Furthermore, these changes are particularly important given the need to improve performance, attract and retain women's talent, and enhance the reputation of the respective call centres.

Call centres must have transparent recruitment, selection, and promotion processes. Interviews, assessments, and performance reviews should be based on objective criteria and avoid gender-biased decision-making. As call centres recruit internally, they should ensure women have equal access to training and development opportunities to advance into leadership positions.

In addition, call centres need to have clear wage standards and be transparent about them. Transparency around pay is crucial to address the gender pay gap and ensure that women are paid equitably for their work.

Senior managers must be held accountable for effectively addressing harassment issues; they are often reluctant to remove those who engage in such behavior from leadership positions roles.

Early identification of sexual harassment behaviour (e.g. Through staff surveys, exit interviews).

Call centres must implement policies to support women's work-life balance, such as flexible scheduling and parental leave. They should also reform the

structures and processes prioritising long work hours. To retain talented women, call centres should offer mentorship and sponsorship programs to help them navigate their careers and overcome the barriers they face. These initiatives are particularly crucial for outsourcing call centres, where work-life balance can be more challenging. Integrating these strategies and addressing the core issues affecting women in call centres can help organisations unlock the full potential of their female talent and create a more equitable and inclusive workplace.

5.3.2 Implications for Government and Policymakers

The research findings reveal widespread gender inequality in call centres. The implications for Scotland are that the government should critically evaluate the efficacy of existing anti-discrimination legislation in the call centre context. Legislation will only be successful if it is effectively enforced through the rule of law.

During the interviews, call centres employing 250 or more staff were found to publish annual gender pay gap reports. Establishing a similar mechanism requiring call centres above a certain size to publicly disclose reports on the representation of women in their management positions would also be valuable. Managers acknowledged that this legislation was helpful, as pay disparities at the senior level in call centres were found to be high. These call centres recognised the need to review their pay gaps, which have been identified as an ongoing issue.

The government can provide financial incentives and grants to call centres to commit to closing their gender pay gaps and promoting more women into leadership positions. Scotland also needs to enhance the availability of affordable childcare options, including after-school and holiday programs, to support working women.

Furthermore, the government can allocate funding and resources to support call centres, particularly outsourced ones lacking resources, in implementing mandatory training on unconscious bias, preventing sexual harassment, and promoting diversity and inclusion in the workplace.

Finally, collaboration between researchers, call centre industry leaders, and the government in sharing best practices could be valuable in addressing these issues.

6.3.3 Original contribution

This study aimed to make both theoretical and practical contributions to advancing gender equality within the call centre management domain. First, it theoretically enriched the existing body of knowledge in this field, joining three frameworks (Acker, 2012; Connell, 2006; McDonald, 2015). Second, the research offers practical implications for human resource management practitioners and organisations to create more gender-balanced and inclusive environments.

The area of women in management in call centres is under-researched and has not been looked at from a woman's perspective, particularly at the senior management level. This thesis adds to the body of knowledge on women in

management in call centres, filling a gap in the literature in both theoretical and empirical ways. In terms of a theoretical contribution, this thesis has constructed a conceptual framework entitled the gender inequality regime, combining aspects from existing frameworks (Acker, 2012; Connell, 2006; McDonald, 2015).

This study's empirical contribution is to provide research demonstrating the key elements of the gender inequality regime as they apply to call centres and their women in management. Firstly, the study uncovered and analysed the shape and degree of inequality in call centres by researching the organisational structure, occupational segregation, the gender pay gap, marital status and motherhood. In doing so, it produced a key finding and contribution to knowledge in uncovering the lack of robust government statistics on occupational segregation and the gender pay gap, which compounds the difficulties associated with discovering the levels of women's representation in management in Scotland and the gender pay gap experienced by these women.

A second key finding and contribution to knowledge concerning the effects of the flat organisational structure on severely limiting women's promotion opportunities is the opposite of Acker's belief that a flat structure would enhance women's opportunities. The study showed no reduction in power differentials in call centres with flat hierarchical structures, nor did they provide more opportunities for women to enter senior management positions. On the contrary, the study found that when fewer opportunities exist, more people

compete for them, and women occupy fewer positions. Not many opportunities were available in the call centres studied, where the structure was flat. Women had to fight harder to access those limited senior roles in the In-house call centres, where the structure was more hierarchical.

Secondly, the research meticulously outlined the organisational sub-structure of call centres. It did so by thoroughly investigating the call centres' organising processes and practices, including work organisation, organisational careers and stereotyping. In doing so, it highlighted the barriers to women's career progression and demonstrated that they were similar to those experienced by women in other industry sectors. The research also explored the degree of awareness of gender inequality and the legitimacy of gender inequality. It found that 41% of women respondents had experienced sexual harassment in call centres.

The research integrated marital status and motherhood into the conceptual framework, showing their effects on women's choices regarding how to manage their domestic and childcare responsibilities alongside their work responsibilities.

The researcher used in-depth interviews to capture the nuanced ways gender inequality is experienced in call centres. To sum up, this thesis makes a theoretical and empirical contribution to the knowledge of women in management in call centres in Scotland.

5.4 Future Research

This research's findings and conclusion suggest future research on women in management in call centres. This research used interviews with women managers to examine call centres in Scotland. It would be useful to examine call centres all over Scotland using a case study approach that involves a wider range of organisations.

In addition, future studies could utilise comparative case studies of call centres across various regions or countries to better understand how cultural and regulatory environments affect gender equality results. This may include comparing call centres located in urban versus rural areas in Scotland or contrasting Scotland with other nations that have a notable presence of call centres industries. Additionally, researchers could investigate the role of national culture and how it impacts gender equality in call centres across different countries, comparing, for instance, call centres in Scotland with those in India or the USA.

Furthermore, this research focused specifically on the views of women managers, except for one male interviewee. Future research could expand the scope to examine the experiences of non-managerial female employees in call centres and could investigate the different experiences of men and women in call centres in Scotland through case studies research.

The study provides important insights into the gendered dynamics of call centre employment in Scotland, highlighting the challenges faced by women in advancing to managerial roles within this sector. Further research is needed

to deepen our understanding of the complex interplay of organisational practices, cultural norms, and structural barriers that shape women's career progression in call centres.

Future research should examine call centres after COVID-19 to determine whether working at home affects women's career progress. It will also be useful to explore the long-term effects of remote work on gender roles and career progression in call centres. This could involve comparing the experiences of women working remotely versus those working on-site and assessing the impact on productivity, job satisfaction, and career advancement opportunities.

Future research should also examine occupational segregation and the pay gap, using government statistics as a starting point only. This could be carried out through case study research in a number of call centres

Deepen the analysis of intersectionality by exploring how gender intersects with other social categories such as race, class, age, and disability to shape the experiences of women in call centres. This could involve focusing on specific demographic groups within the call centre workforce, such as immigrant women or women with diverse backgrounds disabilities.

5.5 Summary

This chapter outlines the primary findings, and their implications based on research conducted in the Scottish call centre industry. It also emphasizes both theoretical and practical contributions to knowledge, followed by a discussion of research limitations. Ultimately, an examination of these findings has uncovered several areas of interest that are proposed for future research on gender inequality regimes in call centres, which could enhance our understanding of the topic within this specific context.

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Appendices

Appendix 1 Sample Of Consent Form

Consent form

Title of Project: 'An investigation into gender regimes in management in call centres: a study of call centres in Scotland'.

Name of Researcher: Safia Khalid B00137574@studentmail.uws.ac.uk

Supervisor: Dr Kae Reynolds kae.reynolds@uws.ac.uk

I acknowledge that participants will be referred to by an abbreviation.

- All names and other material likely to identify individuals will be anonymised.
- The material will always be treated as confidential and kept in secure storage.

Please tick box

I confirm that I have read and understood the information provided on the participation request email for the above study and have had the opportunity to ask questions.	<input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/>
I understand that my participation is voluntary and that I am free to withdraw within a year of giving consent, without providing any explanation.	<input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/>
I understand that any information recorded in the research will remain confidential and no information that identifies me will be publicly available.	<input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/>

I agree to take part in the above study.	<input type="checkbox"/>

Name of Researcher:	
Signature:	

Name of Participant	
Signature	Date

Information Sheet

Dear Julia Murphy,

Thank you for agreeing to consider my request to interview you for my PhD research project. The title of the research is 'An investigation into gender regimes in management in call centres: a study of call centres in Scotland'.

The aim of the research is to explore the ways in which gender inequality regimes influence the context of women in management in call centres in order to better inform organisational policies and practices on diversity and equality both in call centres and in wider contexts.

In this regard, I am now seeking your formal 'informed consent' to be interviewed.

Given the current circumstances this will be a virtual interview for example, using Zoom. The interview is expected to last for one hour. It is important that you know that you can withdraw from the research at any time, either during the interview itself or by contacting me any time within a calendar year of the date of giving your consent. You do not need to give reasons for exercising your right to withdraw or change your consent status level and there will be no repercussions as a result.

The participants in the research will be referred to by a pseudonym. All names and other material likely to identify individuals will be anonymised. The material will be treated as confidential and kept in secure storage at all times. As part

of the research your opinions will be sought but you will not be named in the research or any subsequent publications.

If you have any further enquires feel free to contact me or my supervisor detailed below.

Thank you in advance for your consent and for participating in my PhD research project.

Contact Details:

PhD Researcher (Safia Khalid)

Email: [REDACTED]

Mobile [REDACTED]

School of Business and Creative Industries
The University of the West of Scotland
Paisley Campus
High Street
Paisley
PA1 2BE

Supervisor (Dr Kae Reynolds)

Email: [REDACTED]

Tele: [REDACTED]

School of Business and Creative Industries
The University of the West of Scotland
High Street
Paisley
PA1 2BE

This research was granted ethical approval by the University of the West Scotland Ethics Committee reference number:12054

Appendix 3 Interview Guide

Interview Guide

Research title: 'An investigation into gender regimes in management in call centres: a study of call centres in Scotland'.

Interview Questions will be based on the following themes; however, other questions may arise throughout the course of the interview.

Tell me about your role in the organisation? (for example, job title)

Could you give me some information about your call centre (how old, how many people work here, does it have any other sites)?

Can you tell me about how you came to get the job?

What level are you at in your organisation?

What is the hierarchy of jobs in your organisation? (management levels)

How long have you worked in this role?

Do you have teams in your call centres? How many? Structure?

What is your next career step?

How does someone in your organisation get to the top in management?

Can you walk me through your career story? (university, role model, mentor)

How would you compare career advancement in this call centre compared to your previous job?

Do you want a higher position in the company?

To what extent there any barriers to your career goals?

So, please tell me how you deal with these barriers.

How do you network?

To what extent is there or isn't there inequality against women in your organisation?

Do you think there are any other forms of inequality in your organisation, e.g. race, religion, sexual orientation, ethnicity?

Do you feel you have been discriminated against during your career? On what grounds?

What do you think of the gender mix your organisation?

To what extent is the organisation aware of inequality?

To what extent has the mix of men and women changed during your career in the call centre?

What do you think of the pay system in call centres?

Do you think there is a pay gap in your organisation?

How many male and female managers work in your call centre? Prompt1: At what levels?

To what extent is there gender segregation in your call centre?

Prompt1: Vertical Propmt2: Horizontal

Are there more men working part-time or women working part-time?

Prompt: Reasons for working part-time?

Can you tell me about your personal experience of gender equality or inequality in the call centre?

Do you think there are barriers for women to reach senior-level positions?

If yes, what are the barriers? So, please tell me how you overcome them.

What are the biggest issues for you in your role?

Tell me how you balance your personal life and work-life (prompts; marital status, split of time, children, childcare, etc.)

Do you think there are different styles of management between men and women?

Do you think your performance is judged in the same way as your male colleagues?

Have you experienced any difference in behaviour between male and female managers, for example, in meetings or socially outside work?

What is the recruitment process in the call centre? What is the promotion process in the call centre? How do you feel about the promotion process in your call centre?

In your opinion, do men and women get equal opportunities in your organisation.

Does your organisation have equal opportunity policies? Do they work?

Do you have any suggestion on how best we could improve gender equality/inequality?

Appendix 4 Glossary of abbreviations

ACD Automatic Call Distributor

CSR Customer Contact Representative

CSL Customer Service Leader

PABX Private Automatic Branch Exchange

PBX Private Branch Exchange

Appendix 5 Characteristics of the Respondents

Code	Role/Job Title	Organisational Level	Sector/company	Partnership status	Children	Education	Age	No of people Managing
CM1	Operation Manager	Operation Managers	Inhouse-Banking	Married	None	Part qualified accountant	50-55	About 60 people
CM2	Operation director/consulting company	Director	Outsource	Married	Three	Postgraduate degree in HRM	55-60	1000 to 2500 people
CM3	Sales Centre Manager	Operations Manager	Inhouse	Single	None	Bachelor of Law-LLB	35-40	100-200 people
CM4	Head of Customer Contact Services	Head of Customer Services	Inhouse-Banking	Married	One	College level	50-55	800 people
CM5	Team Manager/Deputy Operation Manager	Team Leader	Outsource,	In relationship	One	Bachelor's Degree, Communication and Public Relations	35-40	20-30
CM6	Team leader	Team leader	Inhouse	Single	None	Diploma in Law	30-35	5-15
CM7	Accredited Trainer	Team Leader	Outsource	Widow	Two	Bachelor's degree	55.60	Not applicable in current job

CM8	Head of the Customer experience	Head of the Customer Services	Inhouse	In relationship	None	BA(Hons) Degree, Media Communications	30-35	Not applicable in current job
CM9	Operations Manager	Operations Manager	Outsource	Single	None	High School	30-35	120
CM10	Customer Management	Operation Manager	Outsource	Single	None	Level4 Diploma	35-40	120
CM11	Data protection Director	Director	Inhouse	In relationship	One	High School	50-60	230
CM12	Senior Operation Manager (Executive office)	Operations manager	Inhouse	Married	None	Bachelor's degree	31-35	Not applicable in current job
CM13	Chanel Executive (Commercial)	Executive	Inhouse	Married	Non	High school	30-35	Not applicable in current job
CM14	Sales Manager	Operation Manager	Inhouse	Single	one	High school	50-55	90 people
CM15	Senior Partner Manager (Site Director)	Director	Inhouse	Married	one	High school	50-55	1200 people

K1	Team Leader	Team Leader	Outsource	Married	Two	Bachelor's degree,	40-45	Not applicable in current
K2	Sales Operation Manager	Operations Manager	Outsource, Global company.	Married	Two	NVQ Training, High school	35-40	40 people

Source: The author (2023)

Appendix 7 NVivo Screenshot

Nodes							
Name	Files	References	Created By	Created On	Modified By	Modified On	Search Project
Work behaviours and interactions		7	32 SK	06/12/2020 23:10	SK	21/09/2021 18:28	
Stress and sickness and turnover		7	21 SK	06/12/2020 23:35	SK	21/09/2021 18:38	
Organisation culture		13	48 SK	06/12/2020 22:57	SK	19/07/2024 11:46	
Structure of the call centre and inequality regimes		0	0 SK	06/12/2020 20:28	SK	19/07/2024 11:18	
Why call centres are based in Scotland		5	16 SK	27/12/2020 17:38	SK	19/07/2024 11:45	
In House and Outsource		14	93 SK	06/12/2020 23:13	SK	22/09/2021 00:48	
Bringing outsourced call centres back inhouse		2	7 SK	26/08/2021 15:31	SK	19/07/2024 11:50	
Sexual Harassment and Sex discrimination		15	80 SK	06/12/2020 22:31	SK	11/09/2021 23:38	
Respondents characteristics		2	2 SK	01/09/2021 11:51	SK	30/11/2022 17:35	
Percentage of women in management		17	128 SK	06/12/2020 21:11	SK	19/07/2024 11:51	
The reason behind the high or low number of women in management or IT		7	22 SK	22/08/2021 15:25	SK	19/07/2024 11:53	
Pay Gap		16	73 SK	06/12/2020 21:03	SK	21/09/2021 18:28	
Rewards and benefits		2	3 SK	28/12/2020 14:38	SK	21/09/2021 14:27	
Bonuses for managers		3	7 SK	28/12/2020 14:40	SK	19/07/2024 11:53	
Organising processes and practices		0	0 SK	07/12/2020 15:08	SK	19/07/2024 11:55	
Technological change		2	5 SK	27/12/2020 18:59	SK	19/07/2024 11:55	
Stereotyping		13	47 SK	06/12/2020 22:59	SK	19/07/2024 11:39	
Promotion at the company and performance		11	25 SK	06/12/2020 21:03	SK	19/07/2024 11:56	
Employee turnover		2	6 SK	27/12/2020 17:43	SK	04/09/2021 11:47	
Does remote working women more flexibility		4	6 SK	24/12/2020 07:52	SK	02/09/2021 00:14	
Covid and customer service and support		6	18 SK	24/12/2020 07:44	SK	12/09/2021 00:05	
Are advisors happy with remote working		1	1 SK	24/12/2020 07:50	SK	19/07/2024 11:39	
Organisational processes (ideal worker)		0	0 SK	06/12/2020 22:37	SK	19/07/2024 11:34	
Working hours and workload		16	53 SK	06/12/2020 22:39	SK	11/09/2021 23:40	
Recognition for Extra work		3	4 SK	06/12/2020 22:42	SK	01/09/2021 22:31	
Legitimacy and degree of awareness of gender inequality in the call centre		0	0 SK	06/12/2020 22:51	SK	19/07/2024 11:38	
Potential solutions to reduce inequality		13	27 SK	17/12/2020 17:00	SK	19/07/2024 11:36	
Degree of awareness of gender inequality		10	24 SK	06/12/2020 22:52	SK	19/07/2024 12:02	
Commitment to equal opportunities legislation		14	26 SK	06/12/2020 22:56	SK	19/07/2024 12:01	
Interactions in call centres		0	0 SK	06/12/2020 23:43	SK	19/07/2024 11:40	
Traveling as part of the job		2	4 SK	26/08/2021 15:16	SK	19/07/2024 11:43	
Organisational support		7	13 SK	16/12/2020 14:24	SK	19/07/2024 11:59	
Networking		8	16 SK	16/12/2020 14:24	SK	19/07/2024 11:41	
Networks, Mentoring and Career support and it is importance		14	36 SK	06/12/2020 22:58	SK	19/07/2024 11:44	
Human Capital		0	0 SK	16/12/2020 14:30	SK	16/12/2020 14:30	
Training		9	22 SK	16/12/2020 14:31	SK	20/09/2021 15:49	
Recruitment and Selection		15	62 SK	06/12/2020 22:35	SK	10/09/2021 15:02	
Education		8	22 SK	16/12/2020 14:31	SK	10/09/2021 14:56	
Gendered Divisions in call centres		17	101 SK	06/12/2020 21:02	SK	19/07/2024 11:32	
Number of people managing call centre departments		7	38 SK	20/08/2021 13:30	SK	19/07/2024 12:01	
Gendered Divisions		17	186 SK	06/12/2020 23:03	SK	19/07/2024 12:07	
The reason that they did not like or like call centre job		4	11 SK	28/12/2020 21:41	SK	19/07/2024 12:10	
Reasons for joining call centre		11	20 SK	22/12/2020 19:15	SK	10/09/2021 15:00	
Reasons for changing job		14	39 SK	06/12/2020 20:23	SK	21/09/2021 18:28	
Promotion opportunities for women		9	21 SK	06/12/2020 23:34	SK	19/07/2024 12:08	
Career future plan		10	18 SK	06/12/2020 23:37	SK	10/09/2021 15:28	
Barriers and facilitators to women's career progress to management		17	89 SK	06/12/2020 23:41	SK	19/07/2024 12:09	
Motherhood, family and caring responsibilities		13	76 SK	06/12/2020 23:06	SK	21/09/2021 18:28	